

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

By

Nethravathi P. S

A Research Report Submitted for the fulfillment of the award

of

Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate

Program in

(Business Intelligence Appraisal using Face Recognition)

Under Supervision of

Prof. Dr. P. S. Aithal, Vice Chancellor,
Srinivas University, Karnataka, India

Institute of Computer Science & Information Sciences
Srinivas University

(A Statutory University under UGC Act, Govt. of India)
Mangaluru- 574 146, Karnataka, India

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

By

Nethravathi P. S

A Research Report Submitted for the fulfillment of the award

of

Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate

Program in

(Business Intelligence Appraisal using Face Recognition)

Under Supervision of

Prof. Dr. P. S. Aithal, Vice Chancellor,

Srinivas University, Karnataka, India

**Institute of Computer Science & Information Sciences
Srinivas University**

(A Statutory University under UGC Act, Govt. of India)

Mangaluru- 574 146, Karnataka, India

CERTIFICATES

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Srinivas Nagar, Mukka- 574 146, Mangalore.

(Private University Established by Karnataka Govt. ACT No.42 of 2013, Recognized by UGC, New Delhi, & Member of Association of Indian Universities, New Delhi)

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Dr. Nethravathi P.S., has completed her Research work at Institute of Computer Science and Information Science, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore as a Research Centre leading to the award of Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate Program in Artificial Intelligence System in Health Care under the Guidance of Prof. Dr. P. Sreeramana Aithal, Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka for the topic 'Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis Using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation And Body Orientation' and further I deem the work fit for the submission as a Research report leading to the award of Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate Program.

Dean
College of Computer Science and Information Science
Srinivas University

RESEARCH SUPERVISOR REPORT

This is to certify that the Research Report entitled “Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation” submitted to Srinivas University, Karnataka, India by Nethravathi P. S., for the award of Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate in Business Intelligence Appraisal using Face Recognition is a record of bonafide research work carried out by him under my supervision. The Research Report (consist with the Publications) has reached the standard of regulations for the award and it has not been previously formed for the award of any qualifications or any other similar title to the candidate or any other person.

Prof. (Dr.) P. Sreeramana Aithal,
Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University,
Mangaluru- 574 146, Karnataka, India

DECLARATION

Declaration

I, **Nethravathi P. S.**, (Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate Scholar) hereby declare that the research work presented in this form of Research Report is prepared by me based on my publications (which are never submitted for any qualifications) and all the works have been connected to reach the theme of the topic and its interdisciplinary area. The descriptions and narrations found are purely original and authentic. Moreover, I am responsible for all the contents included in the publications and research report.

Hence, once again I declare that the entire work in this research report is original for the award of *Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate Scholar* of **Srinivas University, Karnataka, India.**

Nethravathi P. S.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to express my special appreciation and thanks to my PDF supervisor, Prof. Dr. P. Sreeramana Aithal, Vice-Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangalore, for encouraging my research and for allowing me to grow as a research professor. Your advice on both research as well as on my career have been invaluable.

I am wholeheartedly grateful to Sri. CA. A. Raghavendra Rao, President, A. Shama Rao Foundation, Mangalore and also Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangalore, for encouraging me by providing all facilities to carry out this work. I wish to express my sincere thanks to Dr. P. Srinivas Rao, Vice-president, A. Shama Rao Foundation, Mangalore and also Pro-Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangalore, for their support.

I would always be thankful for my family, my mother Smt. Janaki Sathyanarayana Rao and my father Sri P. R. Sathyanarayana Rao, for their tireless efforts and support in every path I take to achieve my dreams and goals. I would also like to thank my beloved husband, Mr. M.D. Kumar and my only daughter Ms. Rajatha Kumar for keeping me motivated when things were most challenging and supporting me for everything throughout my career. A special thanks to my beloved pet Ms. Dolly for keeping me always happy when I am stressed.

I am thankful to Prof. Subrahmanya Bhat, Dean, Institute of Computer Science and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, City Campus, Mangalore and Dr. Praveen B. M., Research Director, Srinivas University, Mangalore for moral support and encouragement. I am also thankful to my colleagues Dr. Vaikunth Pai and Dr. Krishna Prasad K, for their kind help and encouragement throughout the period of my research work.

I take this opportunity to thank ocean of my friends for their assistance during various stages of my research work. I would like to thank God Almighty for giving me the opportunity and guidance to achieve my goal and to be successful.

Nethravathi P. S

Paper Publications

List of Paper Publications

The following is the details of Paper Publications in respect of Post-Doctoral Research Fellow Certificate Program *in Business Intelligence Appraisal using Face Recognition* as per the title of the work ‘*Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation*’ in the specified term.

Serial No.	Title of the Paper	Publication Description	Appeared in	Role
1	Real-Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions and Head Pose Estimation	International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML), 6(1), 301–312.	Journal	Authored
2	Real Time Body Orientation Recognition for Customer Pose Orientation	International Journal of Management, Technology and Social Sciences (IJMTS), 7(1), 390-399.	Journal	Authored
3	A Study on Employee Retention as a Tool for Improving Organizational Effectiveness	International Journal Of Management, Technology, And Social Sciences (IJMTS), 6(2), 121-132.	Journal	Authored
4	Coin-Based Mobile Charger using Solar Tracker	International Journal Of Applied Engineering And Management Letters (IJAEML), 5(2), 68-77.	Journal	Authored
5	A Study on Requirement Specifications and Modifications During the Software Development Life Cycle in M/S Kakunje Software Private Limited	International Journal Of Case Studies In Business, IT, And Education (IJCSBE) 2021, 5(2), 142-161.	Journal	Authored
6	A Study on Optimization and Allocation of Requirements during the Software Development Life Cycle in Digital Align Private Limited	International Journal Of Case Studies In Business, It And Education (IJCSBE), 6(1), 451–469.	Journal	Authored

Patent Publication

List of Patent Publication

The following is the details of Patent Publications in respect of Post-Doctoral Research Fellow Certificate Program *in Business Intelligence Appraisal using Face Recognition* as per the title of the work '*Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation*' in the specified term.

Serial No.	Title of the Patent	Patent Filing Details	Role
1	System for productivity determination using Machine Learning based Face Recognition	Patent Application No: 2021103335 Date of File: 14 th day of June 2021	IP Australia (Australian Patent) Authored & Granted
2	Advance Employee Retention and Feedback System in Industry Using Machine Learning,	20 2021 106 820.5 18 th January 2022	German Patent Authored and Granted
3	System for Management of ventilators for Covid patients in hospital using blockchain	Patent Application No: 202141021200 Date of File: 11 th Day of May 2021	Indian Patent Office (IPO) and World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) Awaiting for the grant
4	Intelligent system & Method to protect and secure environment of premises using IOT Network	Patent Application No: 2021104977 Date of File: 5 th Day of August 2021	IP Australia (Australian Patent) Authored & Granted
5	System And Method For Detection Of Faults In Gas Meter Using Compound Internet of Things (IoT) Sensors	Patent Application No: 202131014317 Date of File: 30 th Day of March 2021	Indian Patent Office (IPO) and World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) Awaiting for the grant
6	System For Secure Authentication and Inter-Communication Among Networked IoT Devices	Patent Application No: 2021102117. Date of File: 21 th Day of April 2021 (Australian Patent)	IP Australia (Australian Patent) Authored & Granted
7	System and Method for Analyzing Transaction Data in Cryptocurrency Trading Using Artificial Intelligence Model	Patent Application No: 2021102149. Date of File: 22 th Day of April 2021	IP Australia (Australian Patent) Authored & Granted
8	System and Method For Human Resource Management to Improve Services of Supermarket	Patent Application No: 202141013317 Date of File: 26 th Day of March 2021	Indian Patent Office (IPO) and World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO)

	using Computerized Online Platform		Authored Awaiting for the grant
9	Computer Implemented Method for Specific Response and Interaction from Retailers according to User Generated Search Requests	Patent Application No: 202141040541 Date of File: 7th Day of Sept. 2021	Indian Patent Office (IPO) and World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) Authored Awaiting for the grant

CONTENTS

No. of Contents/ Headings	List of Contents	Page No.
	Title Page	i
	Certificate from Research Centre	iii
	Research Supervisor Certificate	iv
	Declaration	vi
	Acknowledgement	viii
	List of Paper Publications	x
	Patent Publication	xii-xiii
	Content Page	xv
1	Research Proposal	1-3
Paper Publications in Core area		
2	Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions and Headpose Estimation	4-15
3	Real Time Body Orientation Recognition for Customer Pose Orientation	16-25
4	A Study on Employee Retention as a Tool for Improving Organizational Effectiveness	26-37
5	Coin-Based Mobile Charger using Solar Tracker	38-47
6	A Study on Requirement Specifications and Modifications During the Software Development Life Cycle in M/S Kakunje Software Private Limited	48-67
7	A Study on Optimization and Allocation of Requirements during the Software Development Life Cycle in Digital Align Private Limited	68-86
Patent Publication		
8	System for productivity determination using Machine Learning based Face Recognition	87-101
9	Advance Employee Retention and Feedback System in Industry Using Machine Learning,	102-117
10	System for Management of ventilators for Covid patients in hospital using blockchain	118-138
11	Intelligent system & Method to protect and secure environment of premises using IOT Network	139-143
12	System And Method For Detection Of Faults In Gas Meter Using Compound Internet of Things (IoT) Sensors	144-164
13	System For Secure Authentication and Inter-Communication Among Networked IoT Devices	165-178
14	System and Method for Analyzing Transaction Data in Cryptocurrency Trading Using Artificial Intelligence Model	179-195
15	System and Method For Human Resource Management to Improve Services of Supermarket using Computerized Online Platform	196-224
16	Computer Implemented Method for Specific Response and Interaction from Retailers according to User Generated Search Requests	225-244
17	Conclusion	245-246

Research Proposal

RESEARCH PROPOSAL - Post Doc Research Fellow in Computer Science

NAME OF CANDIDATE : Dr. Nethravathi P. S.
RESEARCH FIELD : Business Intelligence Appraisal Using Face Recognition
TOPIC OF RESEARCH : Business Intelligence Appraisal Based on Emotion Detection through Facial Feature Recognition

ADVISOR: Dr. P. S. Aithal
M.Sc. (Physics), M.I.T. (IT), M.Sc. (E-Business), M.Tech. (IT), Ph.D. (Physics),
Ph.D. (Management), PDF (PRL, Ahmedabad & CREOL, USA). Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University

Abstract

Predicting the customer behaviour and understanding them to improve business is an important part in Business Intelligence. It is necessary to determine the customer needs and wants in framing market strategies. This understanding and behaviour are to be analysed on the basis of the information given by the customer. In today's business environment, people are more mobile oriented and better informed. The personalized, individualized, and relevant information of the customers are required for business intelligence appraisal. Study on online customer behaviour and their purchase pattern has been experimented under various context over these years. There are only few studies directly investigated the relation between psychology and online customer behaviour. Humans share emotions which are exhibited through facial expressions. Detection, extraction, and evaluation of these facial expressions will allow for automatic recognition of human emotion in images. Hence this work analyses the psychological factors of the customer based on Face recognition Technique.

This work mainly focuses on the behavioural data analysis of the customers. The face recognition model extracts the emotion and other features of a customer. The required features will be extracted and will be further analysed to evaluate a person interested in buying the products or not. This helps to concentrate more on the interested customers thereby reduces manpower in guiding customers in any business.

Keywords: Business Intelligence, Emotion Detection, Face Recognition, Multiple Regression, Feature Extraction.

Introduction

One of the important issues in service organizations is to identify the customers, understanding their dynamic behaviour and preferences. Today's companies are focusing more on increasing their profit by expanding their sales by cross selling. It is important to know the customer preferences, credentials, emotions, psychological factors etc. in formulating business strategies which is a part of Business Intelligence (BI). The main objective is to formulate a close association with the customer to encounter the customer needs and wants. Understanding customer behaviours is a complex task which happens with course of time, situation, demographic characteristics of individual, personalities, cultural background etc. Every human being has unique psychological characteristics, which influences behaviour and responses of the social and physical environment. Customer buying pattern always influenced by their personality. Hence many businesses make use of these personality attributes in the marketing strategies.

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

The aim of this work is to understand the personality factors of a customer as it helps to create opportunities. The objectives of this work are: -

- Improves business opportunities
- By using face automation technique, it is possible to select the interested customers
- Number of customers can be increased by making purchase time minimum
- To identify the role of credentials like income-group, age-group in purchasing a product at the time of first visit to the online store.
- Evaluating the interest of the customer in buying the product with Face extraction and Feature extraction method.

Methodology

Figure 1: depicts the detection and recognition implementation proposed in this work.

As soon when a customer enters to a business, the model captures his image by observing his willingness to purchase a product. In the next step the required features will be extracted. These factors will be linked with the business intelligence credentials. The outcome of this stage is utilised to recognize emotion. These emotions used further with the existing model to evaluate the customer willingness towards purchasing a product. This helps business to identify the interested customer's in purchasing the product.

End Result

A business intelligence appraisal based on emotion detection using face recognition is proposed to implement in this model. When the customer visits first time to a store, the model captures the image and extracts the required behavioural features. These features will be linked with the existing behavioural features of the built model.

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

Final evaluation of business intelligence will be done by comparing the features. When similar matches available after comparison stage, then the products will be recommended to the new customer. This work helps business stores to identify individual purchasing power of a customer when he/she visits first time. With the help of this model, it is possible to analyse the customer willing towards buying a product.

References

- [1] Nethravathi, R., Sathyanarayana, P., Vidya Bai, G., Spulbar, C., Suhan, M., Birau, R., & Ejaz, A. (2020). Business intelligence appraisal based on customer behaviour profile by using hobby based opinion mining in India: a case study. *Economic research-Ekonomska istraživanja*, 33(1), 1889-1908.
- [2] Liao, S. H., & Chung, Y. C. (2011, December). The effects of psychological factors on online consumer behavior. In *2011 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management* (pp. 1380-1383). IEEE.
- [3] Gangai, K., & Agrawal, R. (2016). The influence of personality traits on consumer impulsive buying behaviour. *International Journal of Marketing and Business Communication*, 5(1). 1-8.
- [4] Nethravathi, P. S., & Karibasappa, K. (2017). Augmentation of the customer's profile dataset using Genetic Algorithm. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation (IJRSI)*, IV, 33-39.
- [5] Nethravathi, P. S., & Karibasappa, K. (2017). Business intelligence appraisal of augmented data based on existing customers' dataset obtained by genetic algorithm using multiple correlation technique. *IARJSET*, 4(7), 81-85.
- [6] Nethravathi, P. S., & Karibasappa, K. (2016). Business intelligence appraisal of the customer dataset based on weighted correlation index. *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Research*, 3(6), 31-41.
- [7] Nethravathi, P. S., & Prakash, K. E., (2019). Customer Relationship Management System, *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 6(2), 283-286.

Real-Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions and Head Pose Estimation

Nethravathi P. S.¹ & P. S. Aithal²

¹ Professor, Institute of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India.

OrcidID: 0000-0001-5447-8673; Email: nethrakumar590@gmail.com

² Professor, Institute of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India.

OrcidID: 0000-0002-4691-8736; Email: psaithal@gmail.com

Subject Area: Computer Science.

Type of the Paper: Conceptual Research.

Type of Review: Peer Reviewed as per [C/O/P/E](#) guidance.

Indexed In: OpenAIRE.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6592194>

Google Scholar Citation: [IJAEML](#)

How to Cite this Paper:

Nethravathi, P. S., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Real-Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions and Head Pose Estimation. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 6(1), 301-312. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6592194>

International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)

A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India.

Crossref DOI : <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJAEML.2581.7000.0138>

Received on: 04/04/2022

Published on: 31/05/2022

© With Authors.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution-Non-Commercial 4.0 International License](#) subject to proper citation to the publication source of the work.

Disclaimer: The scholarly papers as reviewed and published by the Srinivas Publications (S.P.), India are the views and opinions of their respective authors and are not the views or opinions of the S.P. The S.P. disclaims of any harm or loss caused due to the published content to any party.

Real-Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions and Head Pose Estimation

Nethravathi P. S. ¹ & P. S. Aithal ²

¹ Professor, Institute of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India.

OrcidID: 0000-0001-5447-8673; Email: nethrakumar590@gmail.com

² Professor, Institute of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India.

OrcidID: 0000-0002-4691-8736; Email: psaithal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Background/Purpose: *Quantification of consumer interest is an interesting, innovative, and promising trend in marketing research. For example, an approach for a salesperson is to observe consumer behaviour during the shopping phase and then recall his interest. However, the salesperson needs unique skills because every person may interpret their behaviour in a different manner. The purpose of this research is to track client interest based on head pose positioning and facial expression recognition.*

Objective: *We are going to develop a quantifiable system for measuring customer interest. This system recognizes the important facial expression and then processes current client photos and does not save them for later processing.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *The work describes a deep learning-based system for observing customer actions, focusing on interest identification. The suggested approach determines client attention by estimating head posture. The system monitors facial expressions and reports customer interest. The Viola and Jones algorithms are utilized to trim the facial image.*

Findings/Results: *The proposed method identifies frontal face postures, then segments facial mechanisms that are critical for facial expression identification and creating an iconized face image. Finally, the obtained values of the resulting image are merged with the original one to analyze facial emotions.*

Conclusion: *This method combines local part-based features with holistic facial information. The obtained results demonstrate the potential to use the proposed architecture as it is efficient and works in real-time.*

Paper Type: *Conceptual Research.*

Keywords: Customer monitoring, Convolutional neural network, Head pose estimation, Facial expression recognition, Facial analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION :

The usual way is for a salesperson to study client attitude when he/she watching or shopping phase and then recall customer interest. However, every salesperson needs special talents for this job, and each spectator may interpret consumer behaviour differently. In this aspect, only a few extraordinarily tactful and competent salespeople can have good salesperson-customer interactions [1]. According to [2], subjective emotional perception-based approaches may not always represent the human emotional state appropriately. On the other hand, automatic measurements provide a more exact and dependable result. As a result, developing non-invasive, objective, and quantifiable measures for tracking client interest is crucial.

Knowing the choices using various tools such as brain images [3], EEG [4], [5], eye tracking ([6]; [7]), heart rate registration [8], and other approaches have been a recent topic in the existing literature. Customer behavior classification [9]; [10] and customer face analysis studies have also been used in several studies [11].

Estimating a client's graphic focus of attention is one approach to gauging their interest. Assessment of head posture is used in research on the visual focus of attention [12]. Moreover, identifying client

opinions for selling a product is a quickly growing and difficult research field. The intuitive decision-making process is substantially influenced by one's mood [13]. People who are in a good mood assume that everything is well and that they are safe in their surroundings. When they're in a poor mood, though, they believe things aren't going well and that an incident is approaching, and needs their attention. Customers' emotions and moods must be considered by marketers [14]. According to [15], identify as positive or negative feelings, the surprise isn't included and difficult as well [16].

Our goal is to design a deep learning system for tracking client interests. The proposed method detects the visual centre of attention by first recognizing the human face and then estimating head posture orientation. This work could be useful for identifying things like marketing campaigns and other company efforts that clients could be interested in. Salespeople can also make changes to their marketing materials based on client feedback. This software could also help salespeople respond more effectively to customer emotions, leading to higher satisfaction.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

The suggested study's main contributions can be stated in four points:

(1) A system for measuring customer interest that is non-invasive, objective, and quantifiable is proposed.

(2) Because the suggested work will not save facial photos, personal privacy is protected. The system processes current client photos and does not require them to be saved for later processing. If there is a need to keep track of a customer's facial expressions, de-identified iconized face photos can be saved. Face expression data is included in iconized face photos while maintaining personal privacy.

(3) A three-cascade CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) model with multiple tasks is suggested. The third CNN combines raw face images with iconized image confidence values. Part-based information is included in the confidence values of iconized images, whereas holistic details are included in raw face images. Improved facial expression detection is possible thanks to the combination of part-based and holistic data.

(4) The system recognizes and localizes the facial apparatuses that are crucial for detection in the facial component segmentation stage, which results in an ionized image. The CNN permits guided training at the facial expression recognition stage by compelling the earlier layers of the architecture.

Provides more details are mentioned in the subsequent sections and are organized as shown below. Section II gives a brief idea about the literature survey on the existing state-of-the-art methods related to the defined methodology. Section III demonstrates the proposed method. Section IV contains the results, analysis, discussions, and inferences. Section V concludes the paper with some details regarding the future directions.

3. LITERATURE SURVEY :

Several publications in the literature describe how to use images or videos to solve real-world problems. For video processing, speed is critical, and many frameworks are being developed to improve it [17], [18]. Real-world challenges include object identification [19], text detection ([20],[21]), facial expression recognition [22], head position estimation [23], and so on. The two main elements of this work, facial expression recognition, and head pose estimation studied in this section.

A. Facial expression recognition:

It is a growing area with applications in avatar animation [24], smart environments [25], robotic [26], medical [27], traffic [28], and human-computer interaction [29]. In their early research, the six universal facial expressions described by Ekman and Friesen, namely disgust, happiness, fear, rage, sadness, and surprise, are typically used [30].

Geometric-based and appearance-based algorithms for facial expression recognition have been identified [31]. The features derived from positional correlations between facial components focus on geometric-based approaches. Appearance-based features determine face texture [32]. Local binary pattern (LBP) operator [33], histogram of oriented gradients (HOG) [34], principal component analysis (PCA) [35] etc.

B. Head pose estimation:

This has been studied for a variety of applications, including visual surveillance [36], driver attention [37], the visual focus of attention [38], and robotics. Appearance-based approaches compare a fresh

head image to a set of head posture templates to determine which perspective is the most similar. Appearance-based approaches have the drawback of being limited to predicting discrete pose positions [39].

Furthermore, certain templates require lengthy image comparisons. Geometric information or facial landmark locations are used for head posture estimation in model-based techniques. The accuracy of model-based approaches is determined by the number and quality of geometric signals derived from the image. Dimensionality reduction strategies are used in manifold embedding techniques like PCA used picture projection into a PCA subspace and compared the results [40]. According to [39], a consistent dataset to train the parameters is required for nonlinear regression.

CNNs [39] are a nonlinear regression technique. CNNs give high-accuracy results for head pose orientation difficulties described as a CNN technique for estimating head posture. Three CNNs make up their network, each of which corresponds to one of three head posture types: yaw, pitch, or roll. To estimate head posture, used a combination of both models estimated head posture and located landmarks using global and local data collected from a CNN. For head posture estimation, employed CNN and adaptive gradient methods.

4. RESEARCH GAP :

The literature shows that none of the existing methods used a cascade of the best deep learning architecture in each element and explored how it works. As we already cited, there is substantial evidence that the use of cascaded CNNs has the potential to provide the most optimized and robust results. Hence, in this study, we proposed a three-cascaded CNN architecture to analyze customer satisfaction in real-time.

5. METHODOLOGY :

The Viola and Jones Algorithm [41] is used to trim each facial image to remove background information and leave only expression and head pose-specific data. The suggested method employs the Viola and Jones algorithm, which allows for rapid feature assessments while simultaneously lowering the complexity of every border. As demonstrated in Eq. 1, the integral picture at the location x, y contains the total pixels above and left of x, y when this coordinate is included.

$$jj(x, y) = \sum_{x' \leq x, y' \leq y} j(x', y') \quad (1)$$

Where $j(x, y)$ is a raw image and $jj(x, y)$ is an integral image. Using Eqs. 2 and 3, the integral image may be considered [82]. Where $a(x, y)$ denotes the cumulative row total, $a(x, -1)$ denotes zero, and $jj(-1, y)$ denotes zero.

$$a(x, y) = a(x, y-1) + j(x, y) \quad (2)$$

$$jj(x, y) = jj(x-1, y) + s(x, y) \quad (3)$$

The proposed system's initial stage determines whether the consumer looks correct item. For the suggested system that groups ahead versus non-frontal profile, the coarsest level head position estimation is sufficient. Non-frontal faces are ignored when frontal faces are presented to CNN-2 for segmentation. The CNN-1 has been trained to estimate 0°, 45°, 90°, 130°, and 180° of head posture (Figure 1).

Fig. 1: Sample Image snapshots with different head pose positions (Compiled by the Authors)

(Note: All the colored images can be used only for the Srinivasa University journals. For the rest of the journals, either you can replace the same with your students' image or you can delete the image)

CNN 1: We apply differentiable Neural architecture search (NAS) to adapt the backbone network design for the pose estimation problem. Figure 1 shows the complete information, including the Differentiable neural architecture search, Efficient backbone, Efficient head, and Cost optimization.

Stage	Output size	Layer	
		Small	Large
Input	256 × 256	---	
Conv3 × 3	128 × 128	[32, s2]	
SepDepth3 × 3	128 × 128	[16, s1]	[24, s1]
NAS Stage1	64 × 64	[24, s2]	[32, s2]
		[24, s1] × 3	[32, s1] × 5
NAS Stage2	32 × 32	[32, s2]	[64, s2]
		[32, s1] × 5	[64, s1] × 7
NAS Stage3	16 × 16	[64, s2]	[96, s2]
		[64, s1] × 9	[96, s1] × 9
NAS Stage4	16 × 16	[96, s1] × 8	[160, s2] × 10
TransConv	32 × 32	[64, s2]	
TransConv	64 × 64	[32, s2]	

Fig. 2: Neural architecture search architecture (Compiled by the Authors)

CNN 2: Faces such as the mouth, eye, and brow areas are separated from the rest of the image by the CNN-2. The problem of face section clustering is framed as a binary classification problem of facial component vs. backdrop. According to our tests, the threshold value of 80% was calculated. Figure 5 depicts the image's construction block steps. The output is two channels, one of which provides confidence values for facial components and the other of which contains confidence values for the background. The higher component confidence value in the fully linked layer creates iconized facial images. Additionally, two channels' confidence values are passed to the CNN-3's input for guided image training and more powerful face expression identification. A movable window is used for testing, as stated in 71.

CNN 3: The standard Xception model inspired this architecture. SeparableConv is the modified depthwise separable convolution, as shown in Figure 2. SeparableConvs are taken as Inception Modules.

The proposed method for consumer interest monitoring uses CNNs to complete the three learning steps. The method begins with CNN-1 detecting frontal faces. The frontal pictures are then split using CNN-2 in order to maintain facial components such as essential and critical facial expression traits. Finally, CNN-3 uses CNN-2's fully connected layer confidence values together with raw facial photos to classify facial expressions. The proposed CNN design is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 3: Standard Exception Architecture (Compiled by the Authors)

Fig. 4: Complete workflow of the proposed architecture (Compiled by the Authors)

Fig. 5: Sample Image which shows the non-overlapping parts. Black is the ignored part, Green is the facial component and red is the background in image C which shows the built and labeled part. B is the real one and A is the sample divided image.

6. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS :

The planned deep learning architecture was built by the Keras library with Tensor Flow as the back-end. The Radboud Face Database (RaFD) was used to train and test the network. Totally 8040 photos were utilized, while 1206 frontal pictures were used for detection from RaFD (for angry, pleased, etc). The identification sets for training and testing were separated into two equal halves. Any image of the same person is not included in the testing or training sets. Raw facial photos are used to train algorithms in the head pose estimation portion. Although the suggested system can categorize a head posture as a frontal or non-frontal profile. Table 2 shows the head posture estimate confusion matrix for RaFD.

Table 1: Head pose estimation on RaFD: Confusion Matrix (Compiled by the Authors)

Actual	Predicted (in %)				
	0	45	90	135	180
0	98.66	1.34	0	0	0
45	0	99.11	0.89	0	0
90	0	0	100	0	0
135	0	0.82	0	99.18	0
180	0	0	0	0	100
Average:	99.43				

The Karolinska Directed Emotional Face (KDEF) was also used here. KDEF is ideal for assessing proposed system performance since it incorporates both head posture angle and facial emotions. KDEF consists of 4900 photos with five different viewing angles and seven different facial expressions. Four thousand nine hundred photos utilized to estimate, while 840 frontal images were used for facial expression identification. Because there are few photos in these sets, they were divided into two groups to train (90%) and testing (10%). Table 3 shows the KDEF's head posture estimate confusion matrix.

Table 2: Head pose estimation on KDEF: Confusion Matrix (Compiled by the Authors)

Actual	Predicted (in %)				
	0	45	90	135	180
0	99.02	0.98	0	0	0
45	0	100	0	0	0
90	0	0	100	0	0
135	0	0	0	100	0
180	0	0	0	0.84	99.16
Average:	99.64				

For the construction of training masks, and face component segmentation procedure, all pictures are trimmed to contain facial regions of the brows, eyes, and mouth. After that, the Face++ toolkit (Face++ 2017) was utilized to identify facial important points. The toolbox can recognize 83 critical areas on a human face. 45 important spots make training masks and a polygon was formed by connecting each critical point.

Fig. 6: Sample image from the database with Generating Flow

The system was trained on a 5-channel input for facial emotion recognition (Table 3 shows the RaFD confusion matrix for face look identification and when it is used to recalculate the accuracy of positive and negative expressions, positive expression (happy) has a 95.11 percent accuracy while negative expression (anger, disgust, fear, and sadness) has a 92.88 percent accuracy. The KDEF step output is also given in Table 4.

Table 3: Classification Confusion Matrix on KDEF Database: Facial Expressions (%) (Compiled by the Authors)

Actual\Predicted	Anger	Disgust	Fear	Happy	Sad	Surprised
Anger	95.92	1.11	0	0	2.97	0
Disgust	2.01	95.66	0	0	0	2.33
Fear	0	0	88.23	0	10.00	1.77
Happy	0	3.11	0	95.11	1.78	0
Sad	3.85	4.55	0	0	92.34	0
Surprised	0	0	0	0.77	0	99.23

Table 4: Classification Confusion Matrix On KDEF Database: Facial Expressions (%) (Compiled by the Authors)

Actual\Predicted	Anger	Disgust	Fear	Happy	Sad	Surprised
Anger	89.12	3.14	0	0	7.74	0
Disgust	0	91.66	0	0	8.34	0
Fear	0	0	84.23	0	11.23	4.54
Happy	0	0	0	98.11	0.34	1.55
Sad	5.66	0	0	0	94.34	0
Surprised	0	0	0	1.77	0	98.23

Because the RaFD database contains strange expressions, our system may experience certain mistakes. Figure 7 depicts a visual representation of some of our mistake instances. This work equated to previous studies on facial expression recognition. The comparison findings are shown in Table 5. Table 6 shows the time stages of CNN and the overall execution time, with approximate values for one picture. The segmentation procedure takes up a significant amount of time, as shown in the table.

Fig. 7: Misclassification of results and its visualizations (Compiled by the Authors)

All the image used in the paper are taken from the same databases used in the study. The proposed pipeline is intended for photos with a resolution of 576 * 512 pixels and discrete facial components. CNN-1 and CNN-3 use 64x64 images as inputs, while CNN-2 uses 576x512 images. If the segmentation step is skipped in order to save time, performance drops by 13% (85.12 percent for raw image input vs. 95.11 percent for 5-channel data).

Table 5: Facial emotion recognition of proposed method with other studies on RaFD/KDEF databases (Compiled by the Authors)

Methods	Database	Accuracy (in %)
<i>HoG + NNE [1]</i>	RaFD	93.75
<i>Surf Boosting [64]</i>	RaFD	90.64
<i>Gabor F. + GLCM [36]</i>	RaFD	88.41
<i>LSiBP + SVM[68]</i>	KDEF	84.07
<i>HoG + AdaBoost [38]</i>	KDEF	87.20

Table 6: Execution time for CNN Structures (Compiled by the Authors)

CNN Structures	Task	45	90	135	Time
1	Estimation of Head Pose				-0.02
2	Segmentation of Facial Component				-0.13
3	Recognition of Facial Expression				-0.80
Total Exen., Time = 0.31 Sec. for one image					

Fig. 8: Train and test curves of unaligned face images (Compiled by the Authors)

The details of hyper parameters and their values are Threshold 0.005, Learning rate 0.10, Input channels 3 5 5, regularization strength of 0.0005 and the Batch-size 3. The train and test of the aligned face are regular and saturated well, but the unaligned looks are quite different. But they still saturate at the same number of epochs, but the variations can be observed in Figure 6.

7. RESEARCH AGENDA :

- (i) A unique deep learning system for automatic head posture estimation and face emotion identification is presented in this article.
- (ii) This research is the first step in developing a noninvasive, quantifiable approach for tracking client interests.

8. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS :

The suggested system is made up of three CNN structures in a cascade. The first CNN's task is to estimate head posture. Face segmentation was taught to the second CNN structure. The third CNN was programmed to recognize and classify facial expressions. The last two steps allow for guided picture grouping and the integration of part-based and holistic data. On the RaFD dataset, testing test results showed 99.43 percent precision posture prediction and 93.20 percent accuracy for face appearance detection. The average accuracy of positive and negative emotions is 93.99.

The proposed approach can aid in the measurement of relevant marketing and product likability as well as the quantification of the client's interest. It can also be used to identify sales-boosting company initiatives. According to customer feedback, marketing efforts can alter their methods. The future direction includes the temporal analysis of the data and the optimization space used in the architecture. Track human faces and use object localization so that the system can watch and index an individual's facial expressions over time. Exploring the proposed architecture with people of different regions and cultural backgrounds and testing it on various other domains.

REFERENCES :

- [1] Menon, K., & Dubé, L. (2000). Ensuring greater satisfaction by engineering salesperson response to customer emotions. *Journal of retailing*, 76(3), 285-307. [Google Scholar](#)
- [2] Menon, K., & Dubé, L. (2000). Ensuring greater satisfaction by engineering salesperson response to customer emotions. *Journal of retailing*, 76(3), 285-307. [Google Scholar](#)
- [3] Langleben, D. D., Loughhead, J. W., Ruparel, K., Hakun, J. G., Busch-Winokur, S., Holloway, M. B., ... & Lerman, C. (2009). Reduced prefrontal and temporal processing and recall of high "sensation value" ads. *Neuroimage*, 46(1), 219-225. [Google Scholar](#)
- [4] Ohme, R., Reykowska, D., Wiener, D., & Choromanska, A. (2009). Analysis of neurophysiological reactions to advertising stimuli by means of EEG and galvanic skin response measures. *Journal of Neuroscience, Psychology, and Economics*, 2(1), 21-30. [Google Scholar](#)
- [5] Cook, I. A., Warren, C., Pajot, S. K., Schairer, D., & Leuchter, A. F. (2011). Regional brain activation with advertising images. *Journal of Neuroscience, Psychology, and Economics*, 4(3), 147-160. [Google Scholar](#)
- [6] Wedel, M., & Pieters, R. (2000). Eye fixations on advertisements and memory for brands: A model and findings. *Marketing science*, 19(4), 297-312. [Google Scholar](#)
- [7] Ungureanu, F., Lupu, R. G., Cadar, A., & Prodan, A. (2017, October). Neuromarketing and visual attention study using eye tracking techniques. In *2017 21st international conference on system theory, control and computing (ICSTCC)*, 553-557. IEEE. [Google Scholar](#)
- [8] Micu, A. C., & Plummer, J. T. (2010). Measurable emotions: How television ads really work. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 50(2), 137-153. [Google Scholar](#)
- [9] Popa, M., Rothkrantz, L., Yang, Z., Wiggers, P., Braspenning, R., & Shan, C. (2010, October). Analysis of shopping behavior based on surveillance system. In *2010 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man and Cybernetics*, 2512-2519. IEEE. [Google Scholar](#)
- [10] Liu, J., Gu, Y., & Kamijo, S. (2017). Customer behavior classification using surveillance camera for marketing. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 76(5), 6595-6622. [Google Scholar](#)
- [11] Kasiran, Z., & Yahya, S. (2007). *Facial expression as an implicit customers' feedback and the challenges*, 377-381. IEEE. [Google Scholar](#)
- [12] Sheikhi, S., & Odobez, J. M. (2015). Combining dynamic head pose-gaze mapping with the robot conversational state for attention recognition in human-robot interactions. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 66(1), 81-90. [Google Scholar](#)
- [13] Karu-Salo, I. (2013). The effect of universal emotions on customer behaviour. *Estonian Business School*. 1-72. [Google Scholar](#)
- [14] Sangeeta, S. (2013). Module-6 Consumer Behavior. *Vinod Gupta School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology: India*. 20(1), 6-23. [Google Scholar](#)
- [15] Ekman, P., & Friesen, W. V. (2003). *Unmasking the face: A guide to recognizing emotions from facial clues*, 10(1). 1-197. [Google Scholar](#)

- [16] Laros, F. J., & Steenkamp, J. B. E. (2005). Emotions in consumer behavior: a hierarchical approach. *Journal of business Research*, 58(10), 1437-1445. [Google Scholar](#)
- [17] Yan, C., Zhang, Y., Xu, J., Dai, F., Li, L., Dai, Q., & Wu, F. (2014). A highly parallel framework for HEVC coding unit partitioning tree decision on many-core processors. *IEEE Signal Processing Letters*, 21(5), 573-576. [Google Scholar](#)
- [18] Yan, C., Zhang, Y., Xu, J., Dai, F., Zhang, J., Dai, Q., & Wu, F. (2014). Efficient parallel framework for HEVC motion estimation on many-core processors. *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology*, 24(12), 2077-2089. [Google Scholar](#)
- [19] Yan, C., Li, L., Zhang, C., Liu, B., Zhang, Y., & Dai, Q. (2019). Cross-modality bridging and knowledge transferring for image understanding. *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia*, 21(10), 2675-2685. [Google Scholar](#)
- [20] Yan, C., Xie, H., Chen, J., Zha, Z., Hao, X., Zhang, Y., & Dai, Q. (2018). A fast Uyghu text detector for complex background images. *IEEE Transactions on Multimedia*, 20(12), 3389-3398. [Google Scholar](#)
- [21] Yan, C., Xie, H., Liu, S., Yin, J., Zhang, Y., & Dai, Q. (2017). Effective Uyghur language text detection in complex background images for traffic prompt identification. *IEEE transactions on intelligent transportation systems*, 19(1), 220-229. [Google Scholar](#)
- [22] Oztel, I., Yolcu, G., Öz, C., Kazan, S., & Bunyak, F. (2018). iFER: facial expression recognition using automatically selected geometric eye and eyebrow features. *Journal of Electronic Imaging*, 27(2), 23-30. [Google Scholar](#)
- [23] Riener, A., & Sippl, A. (2014). Head-pose-based attention recognition on large public displays. *IEEE computer graphics and applications*, 34(1), 32-41. [Google Scholar](#)
- [24] Zalewski, L., & Gong, S. (2005, June). 2d statistical models of facial expressions for realistic 3d avatar animation. In *2005 IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR'05)*, 2(1), 217-222. IEEE. [Google Scholar](#)
- [25] Kim, J. B., Hwang, Y., Bang, W. C., Lee, H., Kim, J. D., & Kim, C. (2013, January). Real-time realistic 3D facial expression cloning for smart TV. In *2013 IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics (ICCE)*, 240-241. IEEE. [Google Scholar](#)
- [26] De Carolis, B., Ferilli, S., & Palestra, G. (2017). Simulating empathic behavior in a social assistive robot. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 76(4), 5073-5094. [Google Scholar](#)
- [27] Yolcu, G., Oztel, I., Kazan, S., Oz, C., Palaniappan, K., Lever, T. E., & Bunyak, F. (2017, November). Deep learning-based facial expression recognition for monitoring neurological disorders. In *2017 IEEE International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedicine (BIBM)*, 1652-1657. IEEE. [Google Scholar](#)
- [28] Zhang, Y., & Hua, C. (2015). Driver fatigue recognition based on facial expression analysis using local binary patterns. *Optik*, 126(23), 4501-4505. [Google Scholar](#)
- [29] Terzis, V., Moridis, C. N., & Economides, A. A. (2013). Measuring instant emotions based on facial expressions during computer-based assessment. *Personal and ubiquitous computing*, 17(1), 43-52. [Google Scholar](#)
- [30] Ekman, P., & Friesen, W. V. (1971). Constants across cultures in the face and emotion. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 17(2), 124-136. [Google Scholar](#)
- [31] Pons, G., & Masip, D. (2017). Supervised committee of convolutional neural networks in automated facial expression analysis. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, 9(3), 343-350. [Google Scholar](#)

- [32] Perumal Ramalingam, S., & Chandra Mouli, P. V. S. S. R. (2018). Modified dimensionality reduced local directional pattern for facial analysis. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, 9(3), 725-737. [Google Scholar](#)
- [33] Zhao, G., & Pietikainen, M. (2007). Dynamic texture recognition using local binary patterns with an application to facial expressions. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 29(6), 915-928. [Google Scholar](#)
- [34] Ghimire, D., & Lee, J. (2012). Histogram of orientation gradient feature-based facial expression classification using bagging with extreme learning machine. *Advanced Science Letters*, 17(1), 156-161. [Google Scholar](#)
- [35] Sobia, M. C., Brindha, V., & Abudhahir, A. (2014, February). Facial expression recognition using PCA based interface for wheelchair. In *2014 International Conference on Electronics and Communication Systems (ICECS)*, 1-6. IEEE. [Google Scholar](#)
- [36] Chen, C., & Odobez, J. M. (2012, June). We are not contortionists: Coupled adaptive learning for head and body orientation estimation in surveillance video. In *2012 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 1544-1551. IEEE. [Google Scholar](#)
- [37] Alioua, N., Amine, A., Rogozan, A., Bensrhair, A., & Rziza, M. (2016). Driver head pose estimation using efficient descriptor fusion. *EURASIP Journal on Image and Video Processing*, 2016(1), 1-14. [Google Scholar](#)
- [38] Ba, S. O., & Odobez, J. M. (2008). Recognizing visual focus of attention from head pose in natural meetings. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part B (Cybernetics)*, 39(1), 16-33. [Google Scholar](#)
- [39] Patacchiola, M., & Cangelosi, A. (2017). Head pose estimation in the wild using convolutional neural networks and adaptive gradient methods. *Pattern Recognition*, 71(1), 132-143. [Google Scholar](#)
- [40] Murphy-Chutorian, E., & Trivedi, M. M. (2008). Head pose estimation in computer vision: A survey. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 31(4), 607-626. [Google Scholar](#)
- [41] Viola, P., & Jones, M. J. (2004). Robust real-time face detection. *International journal of computer vision*, 57(2), 137-154. [Google Scholar](#)

Real Time Body Orientation Recognition for Customer Pose Orientation

Nethravathi P. S.¹ & P. S. Aithal²

¹ Professor, Institute of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore
Orcid ID: 0000-0001-5447-8673; Email ID: nethrakumar590@gmail.com

² Professor, Institute of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore
Orcid ID: 0000-0002-4691-8736; Email ID: psaithal@gmail.com

Area/Section: Computer Science.

Type of the Paper: Research Article.

Type of Review: Peer Reviewed as per [C|O|P|E](#) guidance.

Indexed in: OpenAIRE.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6556192>

Google Scholar Citation: [IJMTS](#)

How to Cite this Paper:

Nethravathi, P. S., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Real Time Body Orientation Recognition for Customer Pose Orientation. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 7(1), 390-399. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6556192>

International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)

A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India.

CrossRef DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJMTS.2581.6012.0197>

Received on: 26/03/2022

Published on: 18/05/2022

© With Authors.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution-Non-Commercial 4.0 International License](#) subject to proper citation to the publication source of the work.

Disclaimer: The scholarly papers as reviewed and published by the Srinivas Publications (S.P.), India are the views and opinions of their respective authors and are not the views or opinions of the SP. The SP disclaims of any harm or loss caused due to the published content to any party.

Real Time Body Orientation Recognition for Customer Pose Orientation

Nethravathi P. S.¹ & P. S. Aithal²

¹ Professor, Institute of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore
Orcid ID: 0000-0001-5447-8673; Email ID: nethrakumar590@gmail.com

² Professor, Institute of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore
Orcid ID: 0000-0002-4691-8736; Email ID: psaithal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Background/Purpose: *One of the most significant areas in marketing is consumer position analysis. Retailers can assess the extent of client interest in the goods based on customer pose data. Due to occlusion and left-right similarity difficulties, pose estimation is problematic. We describe a CNN-based solution that includes the body orientation and visibility mask to overcome these two challenges. It provides global information about posture configuration using simple gaits in a retail setting. When a person looks to the right, for example, the left side of his or her body is hidden by the body orientation. In the same way, the person faces the camera, the right shoulder will most likely be on the image's left side. A novel Deep Neural Network design is used to merge body orientation and local joint connections. Second, the visibility mask simulates each joint's occlusion state. Because body orientation is the major source of self-occlusion, it is inextricably tied to it. Detecting an occluding object (such as a shopping cart in a retail setting) might provide give visibility mask prediction clues. Global body position, local joint connections, client mobility, and occluding obstructions are all taken into account in the final advised method. Finally, we run a number of comparison tests to see how effective our technique is.*

Objective: *This work presents customer posture estimation, and a visibility mask to build a prototype for inner and self-occlusion. It also concentrates on local joint connections, global body orientation, and customer mobility.*

Methodology: *The suggested technique is depicted in its entirety in Figure-2. To figure out which portion of the human picture is concealed, we employ stance markers to identify the viewable areas. The landmarks in the occlusion zone have a lower confidence score when we extract posture landmarks. As a result, it is possible to obtain visible masks incorporating occlusion information. We employ visible signs to assist the hidden individual in three ways. To begin, visible masks are utilized to detect viewable parts and to construct spatial masks that filter noise caused by occlusions.*

Findings/Results: *The proposed method outperforms to overcome left-right similarity difficulties, the network incorporates body orientation information, and the visibility mark layers are introduced into the network to enhance the efficiency of occluded joints.*

Conclusion: *For customer pose estimation, A novel architecture using the concepts of Deep Learning is proposed and the occluding object detection clearly provides inter-occlusion by object cues. As a result, local joint connection, the global body orientation, and occluding object and human motion.*

Paper Type: *Research article.*

Keywords: Customer monitoring, Deep neural network, Pose estimation, Surveillance camera, Visibility mask, Convolutional neural network, Body orientation

1. INTRODUCTION :

Customer posture analysis is critical for retail businesses on a commercial level. Traditionally, retailers have analysed customer shopping behaviour using cash register or credit card records. The black box, on the other hand, still contains the customer's shopping experience at the store. Client positions such as

stretching an arm, standing or leaning over may provide some information about the consumer's behaviour and level of interest in the product in practise. It is essential to estimate the customer postures from the security camera. As a result, scholars are growing more interested in using surveillance cameras to estimate client posture.

Another challenge is self-occlusion and inter-occlusion by other objects. If a person stands to the right of the camera, the left side of his or her body will most likely be hidden. Inter-occlusions, on the other hand, can be caused by a variety of factors. In a retail establishment, shopping baskets are the most typical source of inter-occlusions. The problem of left-right comparison, which comes from the proportion of the human body, is another stumbling block in pose estimation. A person's left shoulder, for example, seems to be almost similar to right one when viewed from behind.

Body orientation is a type of feature which enhances the knowledge about a person's overall postural arrangement. The eight distinct ways the body can be orientated are depicted in Figure 1. We may deduce that if a person is facing right, the body orientation is obstructing his or her left body. We may determine that if a person is facing the camera, his or her right shoulder is on the image's left side. We propose a unique deep neural network design to overcome this.

Fig. 1: The orientation of the body which is divided into 8 different direction and the change is for every 45° (Compiled by the authors)

Each element of the visibility mask indicates whether or not each joint is visible. The word "visibility mask" was invented by Haque et al. Only in the top view images did they utilize the visibility mask for self-occlusions. More adjustable view angles, as well as self-occlusion and object inter-occlusion, are now available when using the visibility mask. In other cases, as mentioned in a binary vector was used to express the occlusion. Regardless of how different systems represented occlusions, none of them took into account the link between joint occlusion and body position. Body orientation, we believe, is an

important part of the occlusion model. Our proposed technique may additionally pass diverse occlusion information according to different body orientations, in addition to solving the left-right similarity problem. Furthermore, in our system, we incorporate the detection of occluding objects. For visibility mask prediction, it appears to be an inter-occlusion clue. According to our observations, the occluding objects are primarily shopping baskets at retail outlets. (The main occluding part of the shopping cart is also the basket on the cart.)

Three elements can be said about our work's contributions. To show self-occlusion and tackle the left-right similarity problem,

- First to introduce body orientation in customer posture estimate. Novel deep learning architecture combines this with local pair-wise joint connection.
- Second, we use the visibility mask to model both inter and self-occlusion. Body orientation is also linked to the visibility mask.
- Third, local joint connections, global body orientation, customer mobility, and occluding objects are all taken into account in this approach.

The next parts, which are organized as follows, give further information. The literature evaluation of existing latest and robust methods that are relevant to the proposed methodology is summarized in Section II. Section III goes through the recommended strategy in detail. Section IV contains the results, analyses, disputes, and conclusions. Section V concludes the paper by laying out some of the project's future directions.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

- (1) To introduce body orientation in customer posture estimate. Novel deep learning architecture combines this with local pair-wise joint connection.
- (2) To check the use of the visibility mask to model both inter and self-occlusion. Body orientation is also linked to the visibility mask.
- (3) To local joint connections, global body orientation, customer mobility, and occluding objects are all taken into account in this approach.

3. LITERATURE SURVEY :

Researchers developed a variety of methods for estimating human pose based on various data. One of these methods attempted to estimate the pose using global silhouette information [1][18]. Other studies looked at individual human body elements to determine the overall stance. Pictorial Structures [2], for example, recognised where biological components were located. To mimic the interactions between surrounding joints, Deformable Part Models (DPM) were utilised [3] [20]. Pishchulin et al. [4] creates a better and robust model. The Histogram and other custom attributes were used in all of these solutions [5].

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) extensively used in number of computer vision applications and the performance is better than any machine learning methods [6]. Based on micro-videos, CNNs have been utilised in application industries to estimate popularity [7] and venue category. Toshev et al. [8] reported a novel study in the pose estimation task. They proposed the DeepPose, which uses several cascaded CNNs to estimate human pose. The methods for estimating pose with CNN may be loosely classified into two groups. The joint positions were immediately output by the first group [9]. However, because there is only one prediction per image, this type of technique was difficult to optimize. To enhance the number of candidates, the second group of approaches created probabilistic heatmaps of joints.

Furthermore, flexible optimizations, such as the Deformable Parts Model (DPM) [10], might be applied based on the joint heatmaps. Many DPM variations of the multiple stream Message Passing (MP) methodology on top of an FCN were suggested in [11] [19]. The MP technique from [11] is used in this study to apply the recommended model, that integrates the pairwise joint model with orientation of the body. Learning the occlusion structure for the obstructed joints was one technique to deal with the occlusion problem [12]. A binary mask was also used to mimic self-sealing [13] and object inter-occlusion [14]. Despite the fact that coined the term "visibility mask," it was only used in the paper to describe the occlusion component from a top view photo.

4. RESEARCH GAP :

Predicting the customer behaviour and understanding them to improve business is necessary to determine the customer needs and wants in framing market strategies. This understanding and behaviour are to be analysed on the basis of the information given by the customer. The personalized, individualized, and relevant information of the customers are required for business intelligence appraisal. Study on online customer behaviour and their purchase pattern has been experimented under various context over these years. There are only few studies directly investigated the relation between psychology and online customer behaviour. Humans share emotions which are exhibited through facial expressions and their movements. Detection, extraction, and evaluation of the expressions will allow for automatic recognition of human emotion in images. Hence this work analyses the psychological factors of the customer based on Emotional Recognition Technique. There hasn't been a work published that models the relationship between occlusion, body orientation, and consumer happiness. This work contains occluding object identification for modelling inter-occlusion, as well as customer satisfaction classification, in addition to body orientation for modelling self-occlusion. A CNN-based architecture model is suggested for analyzing client pose orientation in real-time using body orientation recognition.

5. METHODOLOGY :

Fig. 2: The complete Flow of the proposed methodology (Compiled by the authors)

The suggested technique is depicted in its entirety in Figure 2. In finding the portion of the human picture is concealed, stance markers utilized to identify the viewable areas. The landmarks in the occlusion zone got low confidence score when we extract posture landmarks. As a result, it is possible to obtain visible masks incorporating occlusion information. We employ visible signs to assist the hidden individual in three ways. To begin, visible masks are utilized to detect viewable parts and to construct spatial masks that filter noise caused by occlusions. This is where the pose orientation characteristic is found. Second, visible landmarks include occlusion information, which indicates which sections are obscured and which are visible. As a consequence, the visible mask is used to build a posture embedding. Pose embeddings efficiently used to adjust channel-wise feature responses, choosing visible channel features while suppressing non-visible ones. The pose-embedded feature branch is what it's called. The visible masks, on the other hand, reveal which regions of the image are masked during testing. The query and gallery photographs are compared using the most common visual component features, which are organized into parts on the global feature map.

ResNet50 [15], which, like previous state-of-the-art systems [16], excludes the final average pooling and completely related layers, forms the backbone of our method. When given a human picture I with a size of H*W, the original ResNet50 generates a feature map with a spatial dimension of H/32W/32. We increase the spatial dimension of the obtained feature map to H/16W/16 and alter the stride of conv4 1

to 1 to extract a more relevant feature map [16]. A broader spatial feature map makes it simpler to distinguish the targeted individual. The recovered feature map is represented by the letter F.

We generate spatial masks using the position information of visible landmarks in the pose-masked feature branch. S_j^{conf} and λ , respectively, signify the confidence score and the threshold, denote the positions of the posture markers. P_j denotes the position of the j^{th} landmark, whereas c_x and c_y give the coordinates of the j^{th} landmark, $j = 1, \dots, N$. We may get visible landmarks using spatial position information P. For creating the posture embedding that comprises the occlusion information in the pose-embedded feature branch, a visible landmark vector p belongs to $\{0, 1\}^N$ is produced.

$$P_j = \begin{cases} (c_x, c_y) & \text{if } S_j^{conf} \geq \lambda \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (j = 1, \dots, N) \quad \text{----- (1)}$$

S_j^{conf} and the threshold, respectively, signify the confidence score along with the threshold. The visible landmark vector p has a p_j element that specifies whether or not the j^{th} landmark is hidden. As a consequence, the visible landmark vector p encodes the occlusion and creates posture embedding.

$$p_j = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } S_j^{conf} \geq \lambda \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad \text{----- (2)}$$

Locations of visible landmarks P are employed to create spatial masks. $P_j = (c_x, c_y)$ is the resultant posture mask, which is a Gaussian heatmap with the centre at the observable pose markers (c_x, c_y) . With $P_j = 0$, the spatial posture will be set to zero for the unseen landmarks. Each posture mask is denoted by $M_j, j = 1, \dots, N$. The posture masks M are downscaled to the spatial size of F via bilinear interpolation. To generate N feature maps $M_j, j = 1, \dots, N$, each pose mask M_j is multiplied by the feature map F. The pose-masked feature maps reduce the occlusion information by focusing on the observable body components and occlusion portions.

The observable feature matrix p is utilized to create the posture embedding in the pose-embedded characteristic branch. In the global feature, the posture encoding is employed as channel gates. It's difficult to encode the pose embedding appropriately because p has a tiny dimension while the global feature map F has a huge dimension (2048). As a result, we use a one-layer convolution layers to reduce F's channel dimension and construct a new convolutional feature F with a developmental continuum of 1024. To create the posture embedding p , we utilize two totally linked regions and a sigmoid activation layer finally. By multiplying F channel-wise and utilizing the pose encoding p as channel gates, the body position feature map F_{pc} is generated. The pose-embedded feature f_{pc} is built using a max-pooling layer. The occlusion information is encoded implicitly via the pose-embedded feature f_{pc} . PCB [16] is similar to our limited feature branch. In contrast to PCB, our system examines visual mask features in frequently visited places and incorporates occlusion information via observable landmarks. The feature comparison in the visible limited area reduces the occlusion component in the occlusion picture.

6. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS :

We used two types of datasets in the studies. The customers pose dataset (Items of Customer's Interest (ICI) dataset), which is supplemented by the Leeds Sports Pose (LSP) dataset [17]. The ICI and LSP datasets are used to supplement to increase the robustness of the posture data's human variability. The proposed deep learning architecture was built using the Keras library with Tensor Flow as the back-end. The LSP dataset was considered for both the training and testing of the network [14].

The LSP dataset is a well-known standard for human posture estimation. They're employed to broaden the customer dataset's diversity. 1000 persons were used for training and 1000 people were used for testing in the LSP dataset. Each picture in LSP has 14 joint locations determined and a visibility mask, as mentioned above. The LSP dataset, on the other hand, contains no orientation labels. In fact, this collection contains a large number of complicated sports photos that cannot be simply oriented. As a result, we manually select a subset from LSP. The body orientations of these subgroups can be classified into one of eight ways. It means that the feet are usually at the bottom and the heads are usually at the top of the photos in the selected subsets, similar to how customers are placed in a store. Poses with the following conditions in the considered dataset are not permitted:

(1) The heads are lower than the waists; (2) The feet are higher than the waists; (3) The entire body is horizontal. This is referred to as Orientational LSP in this case (OLSP). The backgrounds of OLSP are removed using FCN-8 s person segmentation [28]. The customer place is then dilated by a circular construction with a radius of 25 pixels. Figure 1 shows some OLSP background subtraction examples. Customer behaviour in a real-life buying setting must be examined in order to detect customer interest. There is a shopping situation as well as typical situations such as walking, looking around stuff, and talking to each other in a real-life store. However, we need settings that represent people and products in order to accurately study customer behaviours when purchasing. We used the ICI (item of customer interest) dataset for this, which included surveillance recordings of various customer actions such as pausing in front of a product and gazing at it. The videos in the dataset were found on YouTube, where they searched in multiple languages to increase the variety and quantity of videos. A total of 72 videos were picked by average span of 9.7 seconds. The videos have a fixed frame rate of 20 fps and a resolution of 720 x 480 pixels, respectively. The recordings taken by real-world CCTV surveillance cameras, with varying perspectives, lighting circumstances, and resolution quality, make up the dataset. The Percentage of Correct Key points (PCK) is a commonly used indicator for evaluating posture estimate. The anticipated joint that is closer to the true joint than a specific distance is the appropriate key point. On the other hand, our technique not only generates joint locations but also prominence masks. To assess the outcomes of both the visibility mask and joint locations, we used the Visibility sensitive Percentage of Correct Keypoints (VPC) [3]. The following is how the VPCK is defined: The number of invisible joints is P_{inv} , the number of visible joints is P_v , and the number of visible joints is PC_v . Accuracy_{inv} is the rate at which an unseen joint may be detected. The visibility threshold for all of the joints is set to 0.5 since we let the 0 be completely occluded and the 1 be completely visible.

$$VPC = (PC_v * P_v) + (Accuracy_{inv} * P_{inv}) / (P_v + P_{inv}) \quad (3)$$

Table 1: Results Performed in the Entire Dataset Using the VPC (%) (Compiled by the authors)

Method	Overall	Head	Shoulder	Elbow	Waist	Hip	Knee	Ankle
HOG + MP	33.01	42.11	36.23	33.21	28.23	21.24	38.87	31.22
Inception V4	47.18	46.23	44.84	39.23	51.44	52.29	55.12	41.11
Xception	75.63	82.29	80.12	78.21	71.23	77.23	71.23	69.12
Cascaded CNN	81.31	84.11	86.23	89.11	76.11	81.23	74.21	78.23
ResNet	86.19	94.23	94.11	81.23	83.10	87.23	81.11	82.38
Proposed Method	90.20	99.23	94.23	85.12	83.18	88.11	89.23	92.32

The above-mentioned Table-4 gives testing values after applying the dataset. The total outcome curves at various thresholds are depicted in Figure 4. The visibility mask is not formed by the technique in experiments (1) and (2). (2). As a result, the values for experiments (1) and (2) in the table are the standard PCK values. In Table 1, the VPCK (or PCK) threshold is 0.09 of body height. Figure 3 depicts the comparison instances.

These findings reveal a number of intriguing facts.

- (1) To reach the best results, the offered strategies aggregate the most data.
- (2) Handcrafted features methods perform worse than deep learning methods.
- (3) To improve the VPCK in general (or PCK), orientation information is playing a vital role.

ResNet, on the other hand, has just a slight improvement in orientation. Because the ResNet can only make one prediction per image, this is the case. If no other possibilities are available, the orientation data is unlikely to correct the forecast. (4) Orientational message passing layers, such as rows 1 and 4 in Fig. 3, can help with the left-right similarity problem. The right (blue/cyan) and left (red/purple) limbs are rectified from the other side. (5) As seen in the data in Fig. 3 at row 4, columns 1 and 4, the basket heatmap can aid in the identification of occluded joints. (6) The optical flow can help estimate moving joints like the wrists in rows 1 and 3, columns 1 and 4, in Fig. 3. Incorporating the optical flow or basket heatmap into ResNet techniques, on the other hand, is difficult. For each frame the results are obtained from the methodology in 0.018 seconds making it a real-time application.

Fig. 3: Train and test curves of unaligned face images (Compiled by the authors)

Fig. 4: Overall VPCK Threshold

- (1) To overcome left-right similarity difficulties, the network incorporates body orientation information.
- (2) The visibility mark layers are introduced into the network to enhance the efficiency of occluded joints.
- (3) The proposed architecture incorporates a number of best practices from related works, including optical flow, posture heatmap, and visible landmark vector.

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS :

For customer pose estimation, a novel architecture using the concepts of deep learning is proposed. Furthermore, the occluding object detection clearly provides inter-occlusion by object cues. As a result,

local joint connections, the global body orientation, occluding object, and human motion to address the occlusion problems and the left-right similarity, the proposed network combines the visibility mask and the body orientation. Information is all taken into account as part of a single deep neural network architecture. In future work, we intend to address customer pose estimates in numerous consumers' inter-occlusion. Further optimizations can be done to improve the effectiveness of the system. The robustness of the systems needs to be explored with data from various regions. The impact of the VPCK on customer satisfaction in different shopping sectors needs to be explored.

REFERENCES :

- [1] Sminchisescu, C., & Telea, A. C. (2002). Human pose estimation from silhouettes. a consistent approach using distance level sets. In *10th International Conference on Computer Graphics, Visualization and Computer Vision (WSCG'02)*, 10(1), 1-10. [Google Scholar](#)
- [2] Dantone, M., Gall, J., Leistner, C., & Van Gool, L. (2013). Human pose estimation using body parts dependent joint regressors. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 1(1), 3041-3048. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [3] Eichner, M., & Ferrari, V. (2012). Appearance sharing for collective human pose estimation. In *Asian Conference on Computer Vision*, 138-151. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [4] Pishchulin, L., Andriluka, M., Gehler, P., & Schiele, B. (2013). Poselet conditioned pictorial structures. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 588-595. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [5] Dalal, N., & Triggs, B. (2005). Histograms of oriented gradients for human detection. In *2005 IEEE computer society conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (CVPR'05)*, 1(1), 886-893. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [6] LeCun, Y., Boser, B., Denker, J., Henderson, D., Howard, R., Hubbard, W., & Jackel, L. (1989). Handwritten digit recognition with a back-propagation network. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 2(1), 396-404. [Google Scholar](#)
- [7] Zhang, J., Nie, L., Wang, X., He, X., Huang, X., & Chua, T. S. (2016). Shorter-is-better: Venue category estimation from micro-video. In *Proceedings of the 24th ACM international conference on Multimedia*, 1415-1424. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [8] Toshev, A., & Szegedy, C. (2014). Deeppose: Human pose estimation via deep neural networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 1653-1660. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [9] Carreira, J., Agrawal, P., Fragkiadaki, K., & Malik, J. (2016). Human pose estimation with iterative error feedback. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 4733-4742. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [10] Felzenszwalb, P. F., Girshick, R. B., McAllester, D., & Ramanan, D. (2009). Object detection with discriminatively trained part-based models. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 32(9), 1627-1645. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [11] Chu, X., Ouyang, W., Li, H., & Wang, X. (2016). Structured feature learning for pose estimation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 4715-4723. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [12] Chen, X., & Yuille, A. L. (2015). Parsing occluded people by flexible compositions. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 3945-3954. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [13] Haque, A., Peng, B., Luo, Z., Alahi, A., Yeung, S., & Fei-Fei, L. (2016, October). Towards viewpoint invariant 3d human pose estimation. In *European Conference on Computer Vision*, 160-177. Springer, Cham. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)

- [14] Rafi, U., Gall, J., & Leibe, B. (2015). A semantic occlusion model for human pose estimation from a single depth image. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshops*, 67-74. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [15] Dosovitskiy, A., Fischer, P., Ilg, E., Hausser, P., Hazirbas, C., Golkov, V., & Brox, T. (2015). FlowNet: Learning optical flow with convolutional networks. In *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*, 2758-2766. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [16] Andriluka, M., Pishchulin, L., Gehler, P., & Schiele, B. (2014). 2d human pose estimation: New benchmark and state of the art analysis. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 3686-3693. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [17] Johnson, S., & Everingham, M. (2010). Clustered Pose and Nonlinear Appearance Models for Human Pose Estimation. In *bmvc*, 2(4), 1-5. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [18] Tafazzoli, F., & Safabakhsh, R. (2010). Model-based human gait recognition using leg and arm movements. *Engineering applications of artificial intelligence*, 23(8), 1237-1246. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [19] Yang, W., Ouyang, W., Li, H., & Wang, X. (2016). End-to-end learning of deformable mixture of parts and deep convolutional neural networks for human pose estimation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 3073-3082. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)
- [20] Yang, Y., & Ramanan, D. (2012). Articulated human detection with flexible mixtures of parts. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 35(12), 2878-2890. [Google Scholar](#) [Crossref](#)

A Study on Employee Retention as a Tool for Improving Organizational Effectiveness

Nethravathi P. S.¹, P. S. Aithal², Gayathri Babu J.³, Sonia Soans⁴, & Honey Jayaraj⁵

¹ Professor, College of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore
Orcid ID:0000-0001-5447-8673; Email: nethrakumar590@gmail.com

² Professor, College of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore
Orcid ID:0000-0002-4691-8736; Email: psaithal@gmail.com

³ HOD, Department of MBA, Shree Devi Institute of Technology, Mangalore
³Email: gaai3bj378@gmail.com

⁴ Lecturer, University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Sultanate of Oman
Orcid ID:0000-0002-4964-1197; Email: sonia_soans1234@gmail.com

⁵ Shree Devi Institute of Technology, Email: honeyjayarajp@gmail.com

Area/Section: Management.

Type of the Paper: Research Analysis.

Type of Review: Peer Reviewed as per [C/O/P/E](#) guidance.

Indexed in: OpenAIRE.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5526251>

Google Scholar Citation: [IJMITS](#)

How to Cite this Paper:

Nethravathi, P. S., Aithal, P. S., Gayathri Babu, J., Sonia Soans, & Honey Jayaraj (2021). A Study on Employee Retention as a Tool for Improving Organizational Effectiveness. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMITS)*, 6(2), 121-132. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5526251>

International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMITS)

A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India.

CrossRef DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJMITS.2581.6012.0161>

© With Author.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution-Non-Commercial 4.0 International License](#) subject to proper citation to the publication source of the work.

Disclaimer: The scholarly papers as reviewed and published by the Srinivas Publications (S.P.), India are the views and opinions of their respective authors and are not the views or opinions of the SP. The SP disclaims of any harm or loss caused due to the published content to any party.

A Study on Employee Retention as a Tool for Improving Organizational Effectiveness

Nethravathi P. S.¹, P. S. Aithal², Gayathri Babu J.³, Sonia Soans⁴, & Honey Jayaraj⁵

¹ Professor, College of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore
Orcid ID:0000-0001-5447-8673; Email: nethrakumar590@gmail.com

² Professor, College of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore
Orcid ID:0000-0002-4691-8736; Email: psaithal@gmail.com

³ HOD, Department of MBA, Shree Devi Institute of Technology, Mangalore
³Email: gaai3bj378@gmail.com

⁴ Lecturer, University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Sultanate of Oman
Orcid ID:0000-0002-4964-1197; Email: sonia_soans1234@gmail.com

⁵ Shree Devi Institute of Technology, Email: honeyjayaraj@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Background/Purpose: Human sources are those who make the group of workers of a company. It's also recognized via manpower, skills, labour, employees etc. Human Resource department of a business enterprise performs human useful resource control. It entails various elements of the employment consisting of compliance with labour regulation and employment standards, management of worker benefits, and various other sports related to recruitment and choice of the employee. Worker retention is regarding the efforts with the aid of which employers try and retain the personnel in their team of workers. Retention turns into the strategies in place of the final results. Preserving the worker for long duration of time is known as retention. Retention strategies of the organization need to have the capacity to attract and hold their staff. Organizational effectiveness refers to a company's ability to achieve the goals it sets out to achieve. It's far the performance of the organization, group or an organization to fulfill its goal. Six Sigma is a methodology that makes a specialty of improving the overall efficiency of a business process.

Objective: This work is carried out at Dinesh Foods, Kannur. Dinesh foods are a subsidiary unit of Kerala Dinesh Beedi Workers Co-op Society. The objective of this study is to observe and to recognize how worker retention facilitates in growing the organizational effectiveness of Dinesh Foods. It additionally assists to investigate diverse retention techniques followed and also the employee turnover within the unit. This work investigates the worker retention is a device for increasing the organizational effectiveness.

Design/Methodology/Approach: For the purpose of study the data was collected through primary and secondary source. Questionnaire was distributed among the workers for collecting necessary data for the study, financial statement of the company to study about the financial stability of the organisation and annual report of the company.

Findings/Results: This research is done to find out whether the employee retention in the organisation helps in improving the organisational effectiveness. Varies conditions applied for the hypothesis and it can be proved that the employee retention is a tool for increasing the organisational effectiveness. Based on the analysis, findings and suggestions Dinesh Foods, Kannur can give more concentration towards retaining the employees in the organisation as it is important in any organization.

Conclusion: This study focusses on whether employee retention is a tool for improving the organisational effectiveness. It is found that the employee retention is a tool for improving organisational effectiveness and employee retention helps in increasing the productivity.

Paper Type: Case study-based Research Analysis

Keywords: Human Resource, Organizational effectiveness, Business Enterprise, Employee Retention, Financial Stability

1. INTRODUCTION :

The structure of the global food processing enterprise is to be changing continuously for assembly or satisfying the customer needs and expectations [1] [2]. The purchaser inside the market will demand a wide kind of high first-rate and differentiate products. The agencies inside the industry will introduce the various innovative sales codes for the success in industry. The supermarket, discounters, convenience store, hypermarket and grocery retailers etc. are to be the new emerged innovations in the current years [3].

Nearly 25 trillion U.S dollars made in international market [4] and most of leading international outlets are to be the US and European firms, they are the aggressive leaders with in the retail sector. The pinnacle worldwide grocery store agencies are to be contributing 30% of the whole international supermarket sales. The pinnacle 15 international supermarket groups sales account are to be extra than 30 consistent with cent of the world supermarket contribution. In 2020 the food market revenues are to be expected \$3.03trillion and additionally their cord indicates that there's a compound annual boom rate (CAGD) of four 5% from 2015 to 2020. Huge increase of the world huge packed grocery store is mainly because of the growing demand from the rising economies. The India and China are expecting to show an enormous increase inside the packaged food market. The majority of the pinnacle meals processing companies are seeking to improve their brand consciousness through the numerous promotional activities. The businesses are spending a chief portion of finance for the promotional activities [5]. The Nestle and Kraft meals devices are pinnacle agencies in spending or investing closely on promotional and growing brand consciousness for helping product differentiation.

1.1 Food industry in India:

India is likely to overhaul China and it has all the possibility to develop the top most important diet and position in farming region. India is identified one of the most manufacturer of food. Our country is in the 5th manufacture, consume, exportation and expected growth. India is well known for food processing industry is in a rapid boom stage, it will increase the sector meals alternate in each year.

The food manufacturers presently worth for US \$39.71 billion and the enterprise, could assume to grow at US \$65.4 billion by using 2018. The total food and grocery account reveal that the 31% of total food and grocery consumption is in India and contributing around 17 percent of manufacturing GDP, 13% cent of Indians export and six percent of overall commercial investment. A successful business case will define the problem, all possible solutions, and provide sufficient information, including uncertainties, to decision-makers so they can determine the best course of action for the organization [6] [7]. The most common technique for auditing and analysing a company's entire strategic position and environment is the SWOC Analysis. Its goal is to advance ways for creating a firm-specific business model that best aligns an organization's resources and competencies with the demands of the environment in which it operates. [8]. Table 1 below depicts SWOT analysis of the food industry.

1.2 Major players in Indian food processing:

ITC Limited, Cadbury India Ltd, PepsiCo India Holdings, Nestle India, Britannie Industries Ltd, HUL, MTR Foods Ltd, Godreg, etc.

Table 1: The SWOT Analysis of Food Industry

STRENGTH	WEAKNESS
(1) The central government has granted agro processing priority sector status due to abundant raw material availability. (2) A large network of manufacturing plants spread across the country (3) Domestic market is vast.	(1) There is a scarcity of suitable infrastructure facilities. (2) Working capital requirements are higher. (3) Linkages between research organisations and industry are insufficiently formed. (4) Raw material seasonality. (5) Insufficient quality control and testing techniques in accordance with international standards. (6) Due to a huge number of intermediaries, the supply chain is inefficient
OPPORTUNITY	THREAT

(1) A huge agricultural and material base with a lot of agro-processing possibilities. (2) Agri-export zones (AEZs) and food parks are being established to provide additional incentives for the development of greenfield ventures. (3) Changing consumption patterns and rising income levels (4) Changing lifestyles and a favourable demographic profile (5) Integration of recent technological advances like electronics, material science and biotechnology, among others, offers enormous potential for quick advancement.	(1) Affordability and culture (2) Fresh-food preferences (3) Excessive taxation (4) Excessive packaging
---	--

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

- (1) To analyse whether employee retention is a tool for improving organisational effectiveness in Dinesh Foods, Kannur.
- (2) To analyze employee benefits helps in retaining the employees in Dinesh Foods, Kannur.
- (3) To study the effect of job satisfaction in retaining the employees in Dinesh Foods, Kannur.
- (4) To find out whether job security is a determinant factor for retaining the employee in Dinesh Foods, Kannur.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW :

The success of a company is determined on the competence of its employees; if employees are retained for a long time, the company's goodwill will increase [9]. However, it is a high-quality endeavour to maintain all of the employees in a happy stage. During their investigation, the researchers discovered that the current working environment may be the most important factor in retaining their employees. If the working atmosphere is pleasant, employees are more likely to contribute to the success of their company. Employee retention is a well-known fact that goes hand in hand with work happiness. Alternative features such as flexible work, a fun and enjoyable work environment, career opportunities, recognition, and so on are important factors in retaining employees. They investigated workers' perceptions of the current system in the beverage business by taking 329 samples (Ramakrishnan S and Maran K. 2016) [10].

Organizational way of life and employee assurance is the gauging tool for employee retaining. Authors performed by taking 200 trails from Coimbatore industry and automobile spare parts. They found that if the business culture is very good then, the employees will be motivated and loyal towards the company. The firm's way of life is very important in Indian context and the it will bring their personnel more committed. If obligations get doubled then, performance also reaches too high. The employees could be influenced more of their self-esteem, respect, job design and other retention factors (Anita J and Farida Begum N. 2016) [11].

Authors say that employee retention has a good association between remuneration aspects and corporate culture. They discovered that compensation coverage and organisational culture are the most powerful determinants of employee retention. They also mentioned that, there is a positive relation between these two factors in retaining the people in the workplace. It is a big challenge for an organization to preserve key abilities. Employees wage negotiations and rewards allows to preserve all range of employees. (Maqsood Haider et al. 2015) [12].

The principal factors that have an effect on the employee retention in medical area in India, authors collected around 150 datasets from three unique companies in Chennai. It is observed that the companies must create a good atmosphere to make people stay with them. HR must plan the future career path of their own working people by promotions and other facilities. HR should look at future retain dedicated people by improving job satisfaction and help continuous and constant help to encourage personal (Latha Suresh & R. Krisahnaraj 2015) [13].

The authors conducted research with 10 MNCs with 10 samples from each. By random sampling method they picked the respondents. They inspected the effect of three R's (Respect, Recognition and Rewards) by grading the satisfaction of the respondents. The employees were happy with the implementation of 3 R's and are secure closer to the policy implantation. Some activities like yoga and

other leisure activities initiated by the management to refreshen them (Sultana Nazia and Bushra Begum 2013) [14].

The employees' emotional perception of employees was analyzed. Retention is not possible in a single plan but it should constant best plan for natural requirement. They said that employee retention is supportive for best performance and growth in production of the product. Trusted employees contribute a lot and involve in major decision-making process with their abilities. To solve these issues, mentally employees should be happy and it helps corporates to retain them for long (Memoona et al. 2013) [15]. A study carried out on co-relation with employee involvement as an independent variable and effectiveness as a dependent variable. Involvement changed into scaled by means of empowerment, team orientation and capability development. Organisational effectiveness became measured by profitability, productiveness and market share. Outcomes showed that employee involvement definitely stimulated organisational effectiveness. An extensive evaluation of literature indicates that employee empowerment as a device has not been sufficiently studied in terms of organisational effectiveness. Even though the concept isn't new in India, it's far but to advantage maturity in comparison to that of the foreign research. Most of the research in India has focused on applications and practices instead of on its intrinsic value to the organisation. The studies have constrained to the level of job commitment and employee's job satisfaction (Das Simanchala, Tapas Ranjan 2017) [16].

Another study on sought to examine the relationship among knowledge sharing, organisational mastering and organisational effectiveness. Organisational effectiveness was defined as the outcome of managerial effectiveness and operational overall performance. It was hypothesized that organisational learning and knowledge sharing, positively affect organizational effectiveness. (Yang 2007) [17].

To attain the organisational goal with a purpose to bring about organisational effectiveness, it is very important to have a good mind set, feeling of willingness to work with dedication. This is a crucial tool for evaluating people involvement. If the employees are more involved and interested, it leads them to empower in the work place. Many works proved that, where employee involvement is more effective, they were given significance for their works. This shows that management must give some power to its employees in making decision and apply whenever required. This can improve their participation level and they would turn out to be actively engaged resulting employee retentions (Eileen M. Traut 2012) [18].

To find the relationship between the employee retention and other various factors, the data collected and the data has categorical variables that can be summarized as a series of counts and usually listed in a tabular format known as a contingency table [19]. To find out the association between the rows and columns, chi-square test will be utilized.

It is realized from the above survey that; a statistical tool helps to determine the differences between the training collections in the proportions of the risk factor of interest. Chi-square test and the logic of hypothesis testing were utilized [20] [21].

4. RESEARCH-METHODOLOGY :

Main goal of this work is to find out whether employee retention is a tool for improving organisational effectiveness. A statistical tool, Chi – square Analysis is applied for the hypothesis selected listed below:

4.1 Hypothesis-1

H0 – No substantial association among organisational effectiveness by employee retention and increase in productivity by employee retention in Dinesh Foods, Kannur.

H1 - There is a significant relationship between organisational effectiveness by employee retention to improve employee retention in Dinesh Foods, Kannur.

By testing the above hypothesis, it can be proved that the employee retention is a tool for increasing the organisational effectiveness or not. The below given hypothesis would support the study.

4.2 Hypothesis-2

H0 – No substantial association among employee retention and the benefits provided to employees in Dinesh foods, Kannur.

H1 – one can find relationship with employee retention and the benefits provided to employees in Dinesh foods, Kannur.

4.3 Hypothesis-3

H0 – No relationship with the satisfaction level of various factors and employee retention in Dinesh Foods, Kannur.

H1 – There is relationship with the satisfaction level of various factors and employee retention in Dinesh Foods, Kannur.

5. ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION :

5.1 Hypothesis -1

Correlation Coefficient Analysis is applied for the above-mentioned factors of Hypothesis-1 and found the following value.

Table 2: Correlation between the employee retention with organisational effectiveness and increase in productivity.

Statement	Parameters	Employee retention improves the organisational effectiveness	Employee retention increases the productivity
Employee retention improves the organisational effectiveness	Pearson Correlation (PC)	1	.764**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
	N	40	40
Employee retention increases the productivity	PC	.764**	1
	Sig.	.000	.000
	N	40	40

Correlation significant is seen in 0.01 level.

Interpretation

From the analysis, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) got is 0.764. It is in between 0 and 1. After the analysis if we got a value which is between 0 and 1; it indicates that the variables are positively correlated. In this analysis the coefficient is 0.764 which indicates that the variables are correlated positively. If the variables are positively correlated then, relationship exists and improved production among organizational effectiveness and employee retention. So, it is proved that the employee retention is a tool for improving organisational effectiveness.

5.2 Hypothesis-2

After applying correlation for the hypothesis-2 mentioned above, the following results obtained and listed in the following Table 3.

Table 3: Showing the correlation between employee retention and the benefits provided

Statement	Parameters	Employee retention	Employee benefits
Employee retention	Pearson Correlation	1	.577**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
	N	40	40
	PC	.577**	1
Employee benefits	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
	N	40	40

** . Correlations in 0.01 level.

Interpretation

From the analysis, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient got is 0.577. It is in between 0 and 1. After the analysis if we got a value which is between 0 and 1, it indicates that the variables are positively correlated. If the coefficient is of negative then the two variables are negatively correlated. Positive correlation means if one variable is increasing then the other also will increase and negative correlation means one variable will get increase while the other variable will get decrease. In this analysis the coefficient is 0.577; it indicates that the variables are positively correlated and there is relationship between the variables under study. Here employee retention and employee benefit have a significant relationship between each other as the coefficient is positively correlated.

5.3 Hypothesis-3

For the final hypothesis-3, the Chi – Square Analysis are performed. The result from this test is as shown below in Table 4.

Note: The factors that are considered are working environment, company’s rules and regulations, job in the organisation, working hours and refreshment time, morale among the coworkers, job security and welfare measures.

5.4 Sub-hypothesis 1

H₀ – No association between satisfaction level of working environment

H₁ – There is relationship between the satisfaction level of working envt.,

Table 4: Chi-square analysis between the working environment and employee retention

Parameters	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	31.837 ^a	2	.000
Likelihood Ratio	37.386	2	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	22.877	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	40		

a. 2 cells (33.3%) < expected 5. The min. predictable count is 2.70.

Interpretation

By doing the analysis, the value obtained is 0.000; which is less than the standard value. The standard value is 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis should reject and alternative hypothesis must accept. It is proved that there is a significant relationship between the satisfaction level of working environment and employee retention in Dinesh Foods.

5.5 Sub hypothesis-2

H₀ – There is no significant relationship between the satisfaction level of rules and regulations in Dinesh Foods and employee retention in Dinesh Foods, Kannur.

H₁ – There is a significant relationship between the satisfaction level of rules and regulations in Dinesh Foods and employee retention in Dinesh Foods, Kannur.

Table 5: Chi square analysis between the rules and regulations and employee retention

Parameters	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.510 ^a	2	.000
Likelihood Ratio	20.187	2	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	13.186	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	40		

a. 2 cells (33.3%) < than expected 5. Min predictable count =60.

Interpretation

By doing the Chi-Square analysis, the value obtained is 0.000. The standard value is 0.05. As a result, the resulted value is lower to standard value. The null hypothesis is refused, other hypothesis is accepted when obtained value is less than the standard one. We will accept the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis in this situation because the obtained value is less. We will accept the other hypothesis and discard the null hypothesis. The alternative hypothesis is there is significant relationship between the satisfaction level of rules and regulation in Dinesh Foods and employee retention in Dinesh Foods. So, it is proving that the satisfaction level of employees in rules and regulation of the company can affect the retention of the employee in the organisation.

H₀ – There is no significant association among the satisfaction level of job in Dinesh Foods and employee retention in Dinesh Foods, Kannur.

H₁ – We have seen relationship here.

Table 6: Chi square analysis between the job and employee retention

Parameters	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.026 ^a	1	.000		
Continuity Correction ^b	11.549	1	.001		
Likelihood Ratio	18.553	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	13.675	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	40				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have count < expected 5. Min. expected=5.40.

b. Calculated for a 2x2 table.

Interpretation

By doing the Chi-Square analysis, the value obtained is 0.001. The normal value is 0.05. Hence the obtained value is lower than the standard one. When the obtained value is lesser than the standard then the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. In this case as the obtained value is less than the standard, so we will accept the alternative hypothesis and will reject the null hypothesis. There is substantial link among the satisfaction level of job in Dinesh Foods and employee retention in Dinesh Foods. So, it is demonstrated that the satisfaction level of employees with the job that they are performing in the company can affect the retention of the employee in the organisation.

H₀ - No substantial association between the satisfaction level of working hour and refreshment time

H₁ -Satisfaction level of working hour and refreshment time relation is found.

Table 7: Chi square analysis between the working hour and refreshment time and employee retention in Dinesh Food, Kannur

Parameter	Value	D _f	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	23.193 ^a	2	.000
Likelihood Ratio	28.272	2	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	17.824	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	40		

a.2 cells (33.3%) < expected 5. Min expected=3.30.

Interpretation

By doing the Chi-Square analysis, the value obtained is 0.000. The standard value is 0.05. Hence the obtained value is low. When the obtained value is lower compared to standard value, then the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted. In this case as the obtained value is less than the standard, we will accept alternative hypothesis and refuse the null hypothesis. Alternatively, satisfaction level of working hours over refreshment is found. So, it is proved that the satisfaction level of employees regarding the working hours and refreshment time in the company effect the retention of the employee in the organization.

H₀ There is no relationship with coworkers in Dinesh Foods and employee retention in Dinesh Foods, Kannur.

H₁ – Relationship found here.

Table 8: Showing the Chi square analysis between the relationship with coworkers and employee retention.

Parameters	Value	D _f	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	23.193 ^a	2	.000
Likelihood Ratio	28.272	2	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.531	1	.112
N of Valid Cases	40		

a.2 cells (33.3%) have counts less than expected 5. The minimum expected count is 1.80.

Interpretation

By doing the Chi – The value of square analysis, obtained is 0.112. The standard value is 0.05. Hence obtained value greater than standard value. When the obtained value is more than the standard then the

null hypothesis is accepted and alternative hypothesis is rejected. In this case as the obtained value is more, one can accept null and reject alternative one. The null hypothesis is there is no significant relationship between the satisfaction level of association with the coworkers in Dinesh Foods and employee retention in Dinesh Food. So, it is proved that the satisfaction level of employees regarding the relationship between the coworkers in the company have no impact in the retention of the employee of an organization.

Sub hypothesis-6

H₀-Satisfaction level of job security is not there.

H₁ -Substantial relationship among the satisfaction level of job security at Dinesh Foods and employee retention in Dinesh Foods, Kannur.

Table 9: Chi square analysis between the job security and employee retention

Parameters	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig.(1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	20.952 ^a	1	.000		
Continuity Correction ^b	17.898	1	.001		
Likelihood Ratio	25.955	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	20.429	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	40				

a.0 cells (0.0%) have counts less than expected 5. Minimum expected count is 5.40.

b. Performed for 2x2 table

Interpretation

By doing the Chi-Square analysis, the value obtained is 0.000. The standard value is 0.05. Hence, obtained count is lower than the standard value. When the obtained value is less than the standard then the null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is acknowledged. In this case as the obtained value is less than the standard value, we will accept the alternative hypothesis and will reject the null hypothesis. The alternative hypothesis is there is a link between the satisfaction level of job security at Dinesh Foods and employee retention in Dinesh Foods. So, it is proving that the satisfaction level of employees regarding the job security in the company effect the retention of the employee in the organisation.

Sub hypothesis-7

H₀ -Satisfaction level of welfare measures not found.

H₁ – Association is found with satisfaction level of welfare measures.

Table 10: Chi square analysis between the welfare measures and employee retention

Parameters	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.254 ^a	1	.004		
Continuity Correction ^b	6.273	1	.012		
Likelihood Ratio	11.773	1	.001		
Fisher's Exact Test				.004	.003
Linear-by-Linear Association	8.048	1	.005		
N of Valid Cases	40				

a. 1 cell (25.0%) < expected 5. Expected is 3.90.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Interpretation

By doing the Chi – Square analysis, the value obtained is 0.005. The standard value is 0.05. Hence the attained value is less than the normal value. When the obtained value is less than the standard then the null hypothesis is excluded and alternative hypothesis is accepted. In this case as we received low value, alternative hypothesis is accepted and will reject the null hypothesis. The alternative hypothesis is there is a significant association among satisfaction level of welfare measures provided to the employees in

Dinesh Foods and employee retention in Dinesh Foods. So, it is proved that the satisfaction level of employees regarding the job security in the company effect the retention of the employee in the organization.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION :

Most of the workers in the organisation is female. So, there are concentrating to empower the women in the society. The nature of the employment of workers is permanent. Majority of the respondent is of the opinion that the employee retention helps in improving the organisational effectiveness. Organization give continues attention towards the incentives and perks offered to the employees. Majority of the respondent is of the opinion that the organisation encourages them to take part in training programs that improves the skills and competencies and also agree that the training program conducted always helps in career development.

- Most respondents have the opinion that the organisation gives appropriate recognition and reward for their performance.
- The respondents agree that there is employee retention in the organisation.
- The work load depends upon the seasonal demand for the product.
- The basic facility provide are very good in the opinion of the employees but every unit does not have canteen facility for their refreshment.
- The organisation provides various benefits like ESI, PF, Gratuity, Bonus, Incentives, Overtime pay and extra payment for the more units produced.
- Majority of the respondents thinks that implementation of three R's can increase the rate of employment retention in the organisation.
- The respondents strongly agree that management support employees when they are tackled with any problem and also in balancing their work life along with their personal life.
- Organisation always approaches the employees in an honorific way and also employees can communicate with the top-level authority without any barriers.
- Employees are not included in the decision-making process.
- Employee retention has an important role in increase in the productivity. As if the employees are working for many years continuously, they become expert in the job and can perform better.
- The employees are very well satisfied with the working environment, rules and regulation of the organisation, job, working hours and refreshment time, morale in the organisation, job security and as well as welfare measures provided to the employees.
- The employees retain in the organisation till the retirement. Because they receive many benefits. As this is a subsidiary of co-operative society, they receive all the benefits received by the employees of cooperative society.
- The retirement age is 58 years.
- Employees are mostly attracted to the benefits provided and job security.
- The employee retention is a tool for improving organisational effectiveness and also employee benefit helps in employee retention.
- Various satisfaction factors have studied and all the factors other than the morale with the co-workers have significant relationship with the employer retention.

Retention of employees becoming very important for any organization. Employees or human resource are the important asset of any organization. Retaining the same employee for more years is important because the experienced one can perform better, the organisation can reduce hiring cost, high potential can be maintained etc. Employees in the today's world are different. Successful organisation realizes that an effective employee retention plan will help the organisation in sustaining their leadership and growth in the market place.

In this work it is found that the employee retention is a tool for improving organisational effectiveness. Employee retention helps in increasing the productivity as well. Organisational effectiveness is how effective an organisation is in achieving its objective. Increasing the productivity will be an objective of the organisation. Employee benefit will help in retaining the employees in the organisation. The various factor's satisfaction level also helps in retaining the employees. So, employee retention is very much important in every organisation for achieving its objective, which will ultimately lead to improving organisational effectiveness.

7. SUGGESTIONS :

The company should take initiative to improve the general working condition, welfare and recreational facilities because they are the hygienic factor whose absence will demotivate the employees.

The company should make arrangement for a forum where the employees can express their opinion / suggestions which will help the organisation to understand the problem of the employees and can take necessary decisions.

Canteen facility should be making available in all the units or at least any refreshment arrangements.

Representative of employees should involve in the decision-making process. They should give chance to participate in taking decisions regarding the problems they are facing.

There should not have any barriers for the communication with the top-level management. There should be a proper hierarchy for the communication and it should be communicated to the employees.

The supervisor should make sure that the work load in the organisation is divided properly and all the employees are engaged.

The employees should provide with more monetary benefits for the betterment of the performance.

Effective training program should conduct to make the employees up to date with the technological advancement and to increase the skill and performance.

REFERENCES :

- [1] Survey on Retail market worldwide – Statistics & Facts, conducted by Statista Research Development, 2021, <https://www.statista.com/topics/5922/retail-market-worldwide>.
- [2]. Brody, A. L., & Lord, J. B. (Eds.). (2007). *Developing new food products for a changing marketplace*. CRC Press.
- [3] Jaw, B. S., & Liu, W. (2004). Towards an integrative framework of strategic international human resource control: The case of Taiwanese subsidiaries in the People's Republic of China. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 15(4-5), 705-729.
- [4] Vision, S., & Plan, A. (2005). Published by Rabo India Finance Pvt. Ltd. For *Ministry of Food Processing Industries in India*.
- [5] Deckard, G. J., Borkowski, N., Diaz, D., Sanchez, C., & Boissette, S. A. (2010). Improving timeliness and efficiency in the referral process for safety net providers: application of the Lean Six Sigma methodology. *The Journal of ambulatory care management*, 33(2), 124-130.
- [6] Aithal, P. S. (2017). An effective method of developing business case studies based on company analysis. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 2(1), 16-27.
- [7] Ramnarayan, S., & Gupta, N. (2011). Introduction to organization development. *Organization Development: Accelerating Learning and Transformation*, 1-22.
- [8] Aithal, P. S., & Kumar, P. M. (2015). Applying SWOC analysis to an institution of higher education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 5(7), 231-247.
- [9] Rampersad, H. K. (2005). Total performance scorecard: the way to personal integrity and organizational effectiveness. *Measuring Business Excellence*.
- [10] Ramakrishnan, S & Maran. (2016). A study on employees' perception on retention strategy based on present working environment in beverage industry, *International Journal of Recent Scientific Research*. 7(7), 12536-12540.
- [11] Anitha, J. (2016). Role of Organisational Culture and Employee Commitment in Employee Retention. *ASBM Journal of Management*, 9(1), 1-19.
- [12] Maqsood Haider, Aamir, Abdul Hamid, Hashim. (2015). A literature Analysis on the Importance of Non-Financial Rewards for Employees' Job Satisfaction. *Abasyn Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(2), 341-354.
- [13] Latha Suresh & Krishnaraj, R. (2013). The principal factors that have an effect on the retention in pharmaceutical sector in India. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*, 2(1), 30-39.

- [14] Sultana Nazia & Bushra Begum. (2013). Role of Learning Management System in Retention of Employee in BPO Industries in Chennai City, *Journal of Business and Management*, 14(2), 8-16.
- [15] Memoona et al. (2018). Behavioural Efficiency: An Emerging Term in Management Sciences, *Pakistan Economic Review*, 1(1), 69-102.
- [16] Das Simanchala & Tapas Ranja. (2017). Employee Empowerment and 132organizational effectiveness: An Empirical study on Central Public Sector Enterprises in India, *ITHHAS The Journal of Indian Management*, 7(4), 40-51.
- [17] Jen Te Yang. (2007). Knowledge sharing: Investigating appropriate leadership roles and collaborative culture, *Tourism Management*, 28(2), 530-543.
- [18] Trauth, E. M. (2012). The culture of an information economy: Influences and impacts in the Republic of Ireland, *Springer Science & Business Media*, 1-445.
- [19] Moore, D. S., & Kirkland, S. (2007). *The basic practice of statistics* (Vol. 2). New York: WH Freeman.
- [20] Sharma, A. K. (2005). *Text book of correlations and regression*. Discovery Publishing House.
- [21] Kothari, C. R. (2004). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*. New Age International.

Coin-Based Mobile Charger using Solar Tracker

Nethravathi P. S.¹, P. S. Aithal², Sonia Soans³, & Nayana Yadav⁴

¹ Professor, College of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore. OrcidID:0000-0001-5447-8673; Email ID: nethrakumar590@gmail.com

² Professor, College of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore. OrcidID:0000-0002-4691-8736; Email ID: psaithal@gmail.com

³ Lecturer, University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Sultanate of Oman. OrcidID:0000-0002-4964-1197; Email ID: sonia.soans1234@gmail.com

⁴ HOD, Department of MCA, Shree Devi Institute of Technology, Mangalore. Email ID: mnavanavadav@gmail.com

Subject Area: Computer Science.

Type of the Paper: Research Paper.

Type of Review: Peer Reviewed as per [C|O|P|E|](#) guidance.

Indexed In: OpenAIRE.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5506227>

Google Scholar Citation: [IJAEML](#)

How to Cite this Paper:

Nethravathi, P. S., Aithal, P. S., Sonia Soans, & Nayana Yadav, (2021). Coin-Based Mobile Charger using Solar Tracker. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 5(2), 68-77. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5506227>

International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)

A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India.

Crossref DOI : <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJAEML.2581.7000.0104>

© With Authors.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution-Non-Commercial 4.0 International License](#) subject to proper citation to the publication source of the work.

Disclaimer: The scholarly papers as reviewed and published by the Srinivas Publications (S.P.), India are the views and opinions of their respective authors and are not the views or opinions of the S.P. The S.P. disclaims of any harm or loss caused due to the published content to any party.

Coin-Based Mobile Charger using Solar Tracker

Nethravathi P. S.¹, P. S. Aithal², Sonia Soans³, & Nayana Yadav⁴

¹ Professor, College of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore.

OrcidID:0000-0001-5447-8673; Email ID: nethrakumar590@gmail.com

² Professor, College of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore.

OrcidID:0000-0002-4691-8736; Email ID: psaithal@gmail.com

³ Lecturer, University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Sultanate of Oman.

OrcidID:0000-0002-4964-1197; Email ID: sonia.soans1234@gmail.com

⁴ HOD, Department of MCA, Shree Devi Institute of Technology, Mangalore.

Email ID: mnayanavadav@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Background/Purpose: Mobile phone industry is a booming industry in the market in the present times. This industry is growing tremendously not only in urban areas but also in villages. For communication and other various purposes people use Mobile phones. Hence the usage of mobile is much more than before ten years. In urban areas there are many resources available for charging but in rural areas most of the time charging facilities are unavailable and load shedding causes a lot of problems. Sometimes the battery becomes low during conversations or even an important transaction, and an urgent charging becomes necessary.

Objective: The major objective of this work is by inserting a coin in public places, one can charge the mobile phone. It will be helpful for the people who are using mobile phones outside their homes/offices, need to use the coin based mobile phone charger to charge the mobile. To transmit and receive the IR (Infrared) signal, an IR transmitter and IR receiver will be used at the receiving end. A coin needs to be inserted between IR transmitter and receiver, which will change the polarity of the pulses in Signal Conditioning Unit (SCU) input. To activate the 230V charger, the relay will be ON and then the charger is used to charge the mobile phone.

Design/Methodology/Approach: Coin-based Mobile charger using solar tracker designed to provide a completely different service to people staying in rural areas. For controlling applications, 8051 microcontroller-based circuits used for programming. Power grid is the used for charging and the energy obtained from the sun is used when grid power is not available. MATLAB is utilized for coding to find the edge of the coin comparing it to the image clicked by the camera and to avoid coin duplication

Findings/Results: A simple and effective mobile charger has been implemented, which allow users to charge their phones in an emergency in public areas. This device uses very few components with a microcontroller 8051-based circuit. Usage of stepper motors allows accurate sun tracking. After reviewing the data, it was discovered that it is possible to capture good volume of sun energy when compared with fixed panel system. This method is more efficient, less costly and easier to use.

Conclusion: This work uses solar power as solar energy and generates more energy for free of cost. This system also uses external grid power in the absence of solar energy which will be helpful in the rural areas since villages face load shedding most of the time.

Paper Type: Research paper on the success story and contributing factors of coin based mobile charger using solar system.

Keywords: Mobile Charger, Solar Power, MATLAB, IR Transmitter, 8051 Microcontroller.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Mobile phones are necessity now. Gone are the times when mobile phones were considered as luxury. Mobile phones are used for communication and for various purposes like bank transactions, gas booking, online payments, purchases, in fact everything that was being done physically outside the house is possible using a mobile phone. This leads to a major issue that is the usage of battery. Carrying a power bank is bulky and not dependable for a long time. Hence charging the phone is the utmost necessity now. If a person forgets to charge the phone before going out or is deprived of charging due to power failure at home, he is in a big problem. As simple as receiving the OTP during a bank transaction to making major usage of the phone, a charged phone is always a confidence for the user.

This system is designed to charge a mobile when the mobile gets connected to a charging point in public. Initially a coin needs to be inserted. According to the type of coin the mobile will be charged and the percentage of charging will be shown. The Indian currency coins are utilized in this system. Based on the no. of coin inserted to system, number of mobiles can be charged at the same speed [1].

To avoid duplication of coins, a camera is used to take image of the coin and the same will be compared with the existing database. If a correct coin is detected with the match of the database, the mobile gets charged, otherwise it will display a message to insert the correct coin on the LCD screen. When the user fixes his mobile to the adopter and insert a coin, then, the phone gets a micro-pulse for charging, because it will depend on the currency to notify the percent of charge that the battery will get. Using image processing, the duplication of coin can be avoided.

For monitoring the mechanical movement of the solar panel, a stepper motor is used and LDRs are placed as the architecture of the proposed system. Depending on the movement of the sun, the intensity of the LDRs will change. If the light intensity of LDR is found to be less at any point of charging, then the stepper motor rotates where the LDR intensity less, finds the location of maximum energy of the sun while the ADC displays the reading with respect to the value of LDRs [2][3].

It is clear that the alternative sources of energies are spreading over the world [4]. Sun is one among the base for various energy, the light energy has an amazing charge. This light energy will be converted into electrical energy with this solar panel. The productivity can be improved by setting it towards sun direction [5]. The designed system offers a consistent and inexpensive for aligning a solar panel with the sun. Sun tracking software and simple circuit of microcontroller 8051 is used and the entire power is stored in lead-acid batter.

Now people are comfortable to use the smartphone, which offers latest technologies with best functionality like our personal computers [6]. These phones provide us advanced features namely internet, instant messenger and email facility et. Because of the huge growth in technology day by day, our needs also increasing and becoming more and more sophisticated, hence we need speed, quality and effectiveness [7]. All these features need to be combined in one place and small size. The life of the battery may not be matched with the new smart phone. Buying a phone is totally depending on the customers wants and needs.

It is fact that most of the consumers take their chargers along with them or some of them find in an airport terminal or in retailer etc. This need consumers to approach an outlet and they need to wait for long to charge their mobile phone. The designed charging system are mere band aids to the issue at hand. This system helps consumer to charge wherever they want. It is a general problem, sometimes battery gets discharged in the middle of the communication especially in important times. The designed system overcomes this issue.

The coin needs to be inserted into the insertion slot, then the system detects the coin with the help of a sensor. The mobile will be connected to the charging plug and starts charging with the help of this system.

Initially, when the phone is inserted, the coin is needed to be kept in the slot, it compares the images of the coin with the existing database. If it finds new coin, then it will show on the LCD. Then the mobile will be connected, then charging starts and it depends on the value of the coin. Based on the value of the coin the charging can be Increased. This system can recognize coins of rupees 1, 2, 5 and 10. The LDRs rotates based on the suns energy and obtains maximum sunlight.

Keil programming is used to design the system and installed into the microcontroller by using Flash Magic and MATLAB is used for coin detection. During the night when it is dark or in rainy season, it can be connected to an external power supply also. The system works in both the conditions.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

- (1) To study the use of coin-based method to charge mobile phones in public places.
- (2) To analyse the effectivity of usage of phones outside without the charging condition.
- (3) To study the IR (infrared) transmitter and receiver in signal transmission.
- (4) To research the effectiveness of inserting a coin between the IR transmitter and receiver.

3. LITERATURE SURVEY :

The designed system is unique and can be installed in rural/semi-urban areas. It can be used as people as utilities in public places. This system uses microcontroller, which countdown time for a3 minutes. With the help of LCD display the completing time and actual time left will be showed.

Where the electricity supply is not available all the time and not possible to access grid power, then this system is very helpful. This system is very flexible to use. User need to fix his mobile phone into adopter and placing a coin.

This product works based on the according to the coding written in the 89c51 microcontroller IC. The detector finds the coin and the input is given to the controller. Atmel89c51 microcontroller is used and the charging time period is calculated by using Atmel 89c51 microcontroller.

The survey is executed to know the similar type of work done so far. It is found that, the solar energy/power used to dry or preserve things from ancient times. Vedic literatures also say that, the use of flying machines is powered using the sun [8]. Many research works carried out in designing solar cells. These solar cells and kept in an arrangement to get the required power. P-n junction semiconductor devices doped with 'n' type phosphorous on the top and 'p' type boron on the base. When PV cell kept in the sun, then photons of light strike the electrons and helps to knock p-n junction free of their atoms. Electrons attracted to the positive charge and repelled by negative charge and then connecting wires between the junction the electricity pass in them [9].

Generally, the solar panel faces in one direction as it does not get enough rays of the sun to generate energy [10]. The maximum power optimization will be done to receive more energy from the sun by using LDR. A servo motor is connected through the solar panel. This unique system is helpful where unavailability of grid power [11][12]. Once the user plug in mobile phone into adapter and place a coin, the phone, it charges with micro-pulse. The charging capacity will be displayed with the pre-defined values. User can continue charging by placing a greater number of coins placing one after the other. As number of mobile users increasing day by day in rural areas, this product is helpful for the common public. For controlling applications, a suitable microcontroller is programmed and this system is very compact and lightweight as well.

In case of absence of solar power, the power grid is utilized to run this system. Two different axis tracking mechanism are available. Single-axes tracker follows the sun's east-west movement, whereas two-axis follows sun's altitude angle. A tracking system follow the sun with some specified degree of accuracy and return the collector to its original position at the ned of the day. The conventional sun trackers have a closed-loop control system function, whereas this product can be used with peak power positioning [13]. Operational Amplifiers are used in these types of systems.

4. METHODOLOGY :

This solar based charger system converts light energy into DC current for a range of voltage for charging purpose [14][15]. A coin insertion slot is a machine-driven space is attached with electrical triggering. Following figure-1 explains the step-by-step procedure of the system.

- ✓ User can start the system by placing the coin
- ✓ IR sensor detect the inserted coin
- ✓ If detected, then charging will start, otherwise refund the coin.
- ✓ User connect the charger to mobile
- ✓ If more coins added to increase charging.

Fig. 1: Working of the system

The different sessions implemented for the implementation of this work as follows:

Input & Controller:

A sensor controller, a keypad, a collector and a refund box is fixed in this part. In the beginning, the user inserts the coin then it is checked by a sensor. Sensor is nothing but a load cell, mostly used for digital weight machine. Load cell detects the coin weight and generates some values in terms of voltage. ADCs output is given to the controller; the ADCs value is checked with already stored coin value. If the value does not match then the alarm rings and a message is displayed as "coin duplicate" on LCD display and coin outside by refund box. If coin is original, then message display "coin original" on LCD display and coin collected by collecting box. Controller is a main part of this work. It controls the relay by applying gate pulse, operate DC motor using relay and driver IC and operate stepper motor by programming. All programs will be executing in Keil Uvision 4 and the circuit is run on Proteous simulation. Charging time is 45 minutes as per Rs. 5. Cost of electricity and miscellaneous cost includes the Rs.5.

Output Unit:

Charging probes and collecting box are including in output unit. When the coin is detected and user selects any option Ex. Press 1 for mobile charging then 1st relay is ON for 30 min. After 30 mins charging automatically puts OFF.

The system is designed by using an IR transmitter and receiver for sensing the coin. After placing the coin, it cuts radiation for a second. When it gets interrupted, the receiver gives the pulse output to the SCU. Here comparison of input signal and reference voltage are done. If the sensor input exceeds threshold value, the output value is high. The obtained output is fed to the inverter circuit to invert the pulse to low. This converted low pulse is given to 555 timers as a trigger input. As soon as trigger is received, the output from this is used to trigger the relia for pre-defined interval.

Algorithm for mobile charger

- Start
- Coin Detection. If correct coin is detected, then the coin goes to collection box and switch is ON. And if incorrect coin is detected this coin is go to the refund box and stop the process.
- When switch is on for the charging then charge the Phone (At a time we can connect three to five phones).
- According to the coin battery will charge up to some percentage.
- Once charge the battery up to the given percentage it will stop charging.

Charge Mobile (coin)

Input: Coin.

Output: Charging.....

Process:

```
Display "Please insert coin"  
  
If (valid coin)//  
{  
    Coinval=the value of the coin.  
    LCD displays "Charging"  
}  
else  
{  
    The coin back to the slot.  
}
```

Input operations will be carried out in the system are:

With the use of MATLAB source code, the output for coin detection output can be seen here. The following figure 2 below displays the input consists of 'get live', 'Read Image', 'process' parameters. It consists an image of coin live called 'get live', for reading the image 'Read Image' and to compare with originally stored image it uses 'process' parameters to send the output.

Fig. 2: Input Image to be taken for Detection

In figure 3 below, shows the image taken by the camera and gives the result "Metric Closer to 1 Indicates the Image is Perfectly Round".

Fig. 3: Image for detecting shape of the coin

Figure 4 tells us the MATLAB platform for edge detection where according to the edge of the coin its size we can find out the coin prediction where the density and weight can be used to find the coin correctly.

Fig. 4: Coin Edge Detection

Below in figure 5 one can see that the input image taken by the MATLAB platform to detect the real image test to test its originality as the MATLAB used to compare the size of the coin followed by the image captured.

Fig. 5: Input Image

The image of a coin taken by the web camera that is attached to the system. As we take the images of the coin to test the originality from all the dimensions possible is shown in figure 6.

Fig. 6: Original Image Taken by the Camera

MATLAB code utilized for detecting the edge of the coin with comparing to image clicked by the camera. Here we can see that the camera image along with comparison to detect the coin's edge by comparing it to a picture captured by the camera. The camera image, as well as a comparison in the source code shown below.

Fig. 7: Edge Detection Comparison with camera

In this figure we can see the comparison of the edge detection of the coin is being calculated where we compare the thickness of the coin. The thickness of the coin helps us to find about the originality of the coin.

Different types of phones with different capacities:

Here are different types of devices with different capacities available. It is known that the battery ranges of all the devices vary according to their capacities by using in this system. In the given devices the devices when gets completely charged a signal is send indicating that the device is about to get charged completely. So, these are some of the devices with different battery capacities shown in table 1 below.

Table 1 : Charging Capacities of various brands

No.	Device Brand	Charging (Max) Voltage (V)	Charging (Maximum) Current (oh)
1	Nokia	4.8	1500
2	LG	5.5	2100
3	HTC	5.5	1800
4	Panasonic	3.7	1200
5	Black Berry	3.7	1300
6	Samsung	5.7	3400
7	Sony	4.8	900

The components used for this system are soldered on a PCB. Testing of regulator circuit is performed by connecting voltage between 8V and 18V as the input to voltage regulator. It is observed that the output is constant and the value of the voltage between 4.55V and 5.25 V. The circuit woks efficiently for this value. After testing, the negative output of the regulator is connected to the -ve of USB, positive to +ve point of the USB port. At the end solar panel is connected to the input of the voltage regulator. During testing it is observed that 5V output voltage during sun light. This is the ideal voltage to connect the mobile phone for charging.

The charging is depending on coin inserted. According to diameter of coin, image of coin the battery will charge. That images store in database of system hence we can find the originality and the battery will charge.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION :

A simple and hand efficient mobile charger is implemented and it helps consumers to charge their phones in public places when they are away from their home/office. This product designed by using minimum number of components with the microcontroller 8051 and a stepper motor to enable exact chasing of sun. After texting, it has been shown that the sun tracking systems can collect maximum energy than a fixed panel system with improved efficiency.

The hardware setup for coin based mobile charger using solar tracking system shown below, this setup contains following hardware parts: LDR 1, LDR 2, ATME1 89c51 Microcontroller, Stepper Motor, LCD Display, Motor Driver, Solar Panel, Battery, Coin Detected IR Sensor, Power Supply Unit. The hardware is as shown below in figure 8.

Fig. 8: Experimental Setup

Working:

At the end the working of the system can be expected as follows:

- ✓ User insert coin
- ✓ IR sensor detects the coin
- ✓ If the inserted coin is correct, then LCD display OK, otherwise returns to refund box
- ✓ Display the Selection of mobile for charging

The mobiles phone can be charged in either way

1. Input power from Solar energy
2. From the regulated power supply of 230V will be stepdown to 12V using transformer.

In this work the microcontroller plays very important role and it works based on the instruction received by IR sensor. All the processes of the controller and relays displayed by LCD. Mobile charger pin is used to connect the mobile for charging. The amount for charging is calculated based on the number of coins inserted and mobile gets charged.

The system designed is very effective, secured and unique as it runs on solar energy. This system can be used for Televisions also with little modification. As the system uses intelligent tracking of solar energy, it utilises solar power which is essential in today's life. During summer season it can work significantly. Rural public will get benefit from this system as they won't get electricity most of the times.

70% of the world's population uses mobile phones hence this system is useful to them since communication is becoming a vital part of human lives. Many times, it is not possible to carry mobile charger; if mobile discharges and any important work needs to be done using the mobile and charging sources are unavailable then this system is extremely useful.

This system uses solar power, which is also another major advantage because solar energy is a free source and generates more energy. This system also uses external grid power which comes into effect when solar energy is unavailable. Mostly, in rural areas this system is useful due to the problem of lack of regular electricity.

Solar energy is used in this project since it is a free source of energy that generates more energy at no expense. In the event that solar energy is absent, the system also uses external grid electricity. This will be beneficial to rural areas, as villages frequently experience power outages.

REFERENCES :

- [1] Sridevi, S. B., Suneel, A. S., & Nalini, K. (2013). Coin based mobile charger using Solar tracking system. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Electronics and Communication Engineering (IJARECE)*, 2(1), 741-745.
- [2] Adeppa, A. (2015). Solar tracker with stepper motor control. *Indian Journal of Scientific Research*, 375-381.
- [3] Abas, M. A., Kadir, S. A., & Azim, A. K. (2010, December). Improved structure of solar tracker with microcontroller-based control. In *2010 Second International Conference on Advances in Computing, Control, and Telecommunication Technologies*, 55-59.
- [4] Nema, P., Nema, R. K., & Rangnekar, S. (2009). A current and future state of art development of hybrid energy system using wind and PV-solar: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 13(8), 2096-2103.
- [5] Ahmed, F., Naeem, M., & Iqbal, M. (2017). ICT and renewable energy: a way forward to the next generation telecom base stations. *Telecommunication Systems*, 64(1), 43-56.
- [6] Laura Silver et al. (2021). Use of smartphones & social media is common across most emerging economies. Retrieved August 22, 2021, <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2019/03/07/use-of-smartphones-and-social-media-is-common-across-most-emerging-economies>, 1-9.
- [7] Gadhiya, S. A., Wandra, K. H., & Vaghela, V. B. (2012). Role of mobile augmentation in mobile application development. *IEEE International Conference on Engineering Education: Innovative Practices and Future Trends (AICERA)*, 1-5.
- [8] Kimberly Dumke (2011). The Power of the Sun. Retrieved on August 22, 2021 from <https://www.nationalgeographic.org/article/power-sun>, 1-5.
- [9] Eakburanawat, J., & Boonyaroonate, I. (2006). Development of a thermoelectric battery-charger with microcontroller-based maximum power point tracking technique. *Applied Energy*, 83(7), 687-704.
- [10] Tirmare, A. H., Khandare, V. V., & Mali, P. S. (2015). Solar energy based mobile charger. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, IT and Social Sciences*, 5(6), 22-29.
- [11] Varadarajan, M. S. (2012). Coin based universal mobile Battery Charger. *IOSR Journal of Engineering (IOSRJEN)*, 2(6), 1357-1373.
- [12] Yadav, Y., & Sood, A. (2013). A Comparative Survey on Various Coin Recognition Systems Based on Image Processing. *International Journal of Engineering and Computer Science*, 2(11), 3272-3277.
- [13] Chowdhury, M. E., Khandakar, A., Hossain, B., & Abouhasera, R. (2019). A low-cost closed-loop solar tracking system based on the sun position algorithm. *Journal of Sensors*, 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/3681031>.
- [14] Shufian, A., Rahman, M. M., Ahmed, K., Islam, R., Hasan, M., & Islam, T. (2019). Design and implementation of solar power wireless battery charger. *1st International Conference on Advances in Science, Engineering and Robotics Technology (ICASERT)*, 1-5.
- [15] Dai, D., & Liu, J. (2013). Design of a practical human-powered contactless charger for cellphone. *IEEE Transactions on Consumer Electronics*, 59(3), 476-482.

A Study on Requirement Specifications and Modifications During the Software Development Life Cycle in M/S Kakunje Software Private Limited

Nethravathi P. S.¹ & P. S. Aithal²

¹ Professor, College of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore
Orcid ID:0000-0001-5447-8673; Email: nethrakumar590@gmail.com

² Professor, College of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore
Orcid ID:0000-0002-4691-8736; Email: psaithal@gmail.com

Area of the Paper: Computer Science.

Type of the Paper: Research Case Study.

Type of Review: Peer Reviewed as per [C|O|P|E](#) guidance.

Indexed In: OpenAIRE & CrossRef.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5560269>

Google Scholar Citation: [IJCSBE](#)

How to Cite this Paper:

Nethravathi, P. S., & Aithal, P. S., (2021). A Study on Requirement Specifications and Modifications During the Software Development Life Cycle in M/S Kakunje Software Private Limited. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE)*, 5(2), 142-161. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5560269>

International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)

A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India.

Crossref DOI : <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJCSBE.2581.6942.0126>

© With Authors.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution Non-Commercial 4.0 International License](#) subject to proper citation to the publication source of the work.

Disclaimer: The scholarly papers as reviewed and published by the Srinivas Publications (S.P.), India are the views and opinions of their respective authors and are not the views or opinions of the S.P. The S.P. disclaims of any harm or loss caused due to the published content to any party.

A Study on Requirement Specifications and Modifications During the Software Development Life Cycle in M/S Kakunje Software Private Limited

Nethravathi P. S.¹ & P. S. Aithal²

¹ Professor, College of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore
Orcid ID:0000-0001-5447-8673; Email: nethrakumar590@gmail.com

² Professor, College of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore
Orcid ID:0000-0002-4691-8736; Email: psaithal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Background/Purpose: In order to face the challenge of optimization and allocation of necessary requirements to complete a project within the allocated time period, the project manager must be efficient in applying different technical skills and managerial strategies to the project management process. In order to develop a software and mobile application product, a company schedules different processes as per the specified order and unique requirements. As the history of project management reminds that most of the industries started to implement this concept by observing the success of mega engineering projects because of the effective utilization of project management concept.

Objective: This work is carried out to understand the concepts of project management in software firms. To investigate the implementation and importance of these concepts and to know the role of project manager in managing the process in software development.

Design/Methodology/Approach: Kakunje Software Private Limited, Mangalore, provides excellent and state-of-the-art customized software and hardware solutions as per the necessities of customers. In order to manage the project activities CEO, CFO and CTO all together act as project manager. The software development project management process starts by identifying needs and recommending solutions, which can be delivered to value its stakeholders. At the second phase the actual development will begin and the developed software will be tested according to customer requirements.

Findings/Results: Budgeting, cost management, finance planning etc., represented by CPM and PERT charts by using Microsoft Project and Atlassian JIRA project management software. The project resources, which are used to manage the project and allocation of technical staff are represented by histogram. With the help of Gantt Chart software development project schedule of 5 months are shown.

Conclusion: To manage Kakunje business in an effective and gainful manner, the company managed overall internal and external risks of the project. By using the project management software, the company condensed the project manager's efforts and human errors to manage multiple projects.

Paper Type: Case study-based Research Analysis

Keywords: Project Management, Software Development Life Cycle, Process, Software Company, Requirement Specification.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Software Industry or Information Technology Industry deals with software and hardware development [1]. Maintaining business includes trading, manufacturing, servicing activities. The software industry started since 1953 and first software provider is computer usage company in 1955, IBM and UNIVAC are the commercial computer dears in 1960s. In 1959 computer sciences corporation was founded and helped to develop advanced computer technology and automatic processing technology. Now the world-wide size of software industry estimated as US\$ 429.9 billion [2]. The Project Management is the management activities of initiating, planning, organizing, controlling and closing the assigned

project work by satisfying the requirements and manage cost benefit of the project within assigned time period [3]. The word Project is any activity undertaken which involves research design and proper planning with set of interrelated activities to be executed by an individual or by a team to achieve particular purpose over a fixed cost and time frame, the activities of Project Management is managed by the Project Manager. The Project Manager is a key person who manages the project and overall responsibilities of the success of project by effectively managing the project management activities. It includes project initiation to project closure, technical and non-technical skills to manage a project. The duties of project manager are decision making, developing schedules, project cost management, risk management, project team management, documentation and reporting, contacting with vendors, quality control, etc. [4].

Project Cost Management is the activity which does cost-benefit analysis of the project [5]. It is the method to manage the overall cost of project which helps to generate profit, this activity deals with cost budgeting using historical data and complete the project within budgeted cost, which will include project development cost, labor cost, material costs and to manage risk of the project like inflation, natural disasters, unexpected costs. Project management process is which the general development stages of a project [6].

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

- (1) To study and understand the project management concept in software development companies
- (2) To analyze implementation and importance of project management concept in software development companies.
- (3) To analyze the role and importance project manager in order to manage the software development process,
- (4) To evaluate the impacts and challenges involved in project management to software development companies.

3. METHODOLOGY:

The study is based on data collected from primary sources and secondary sources as shown below:

- The primary sources of data are collected by direct interviewing the CEO and Managing Director, departmental heads and employees of Kakunje Software Private Limited.
- The secondary sources of data are collected by referring few text books related to project management concepts, articles, websites and literature reviews related to project management and software project management concepts, referring finance and cost data of Kakunje Software Private Limited.

4. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Project Management regarded as a high priority as all organizations involved in implementing new undertakings, innovation and challenges. Project may be individually diverse, however over a time, some tools, management techniques and problem-solving techniques results in bringing project to a successful end (Gonovski, V. 2017) [7]. Software project management is a key idea about the planning, monitoring and control of software projects. Projects to produce software are worthwhile only if they satisfy real needs and examine how it can identify stakeholders in a project and their objectives (Cotterell, M., and Hughes, B. 1995) [8]. Project management is the combination of project scope management, project cost management, project time management, project quality management, project human resource management, project risk management, project communication management (Aanbari, F. T., and Kwak, Y. H. 2018) [9]. Project management deals with the pre-determined cost, quality and pre-determined schedule of a project, and is managed by systematic way and the final result should be accepted by others is called success of a project (Almaamari, G., Williams, N., and Atkinson, R. 2017) [10].

There are differences in practicing project management concept with each industry, the maturity of repeated work project is low and the project involving research expansion activity is very high (Korte, R., Smith, K. A., and Li, C. Q. 2018) [11]. Project manager should aware of the project risk involved to complete the project successfully, to manage that he can predict and control the risks by taking reference from similar projects which will save the investment and time Sanz-Llopis, J., and

Ostermann, M. 2020) [12].

Project management office which headed by project manager is team which manages whole activities of project management and they are responsible for project failure, project success and that is result of coordination between them and execution team (Petersen, K. W. 2020) [13]. Project risk management is the process of identification of risk factor, assess the risk effects, developing strategic solutions, implement the solutions, control the risk factors, manage the crisis, recover from the crisis related to project management (Arashpour, M., Abbasi, B., Arashpour, M., Hosseini, M. R., and Yang, R. 2017) [14]. The Project will successful when there is coordination in the management team and executing team, the team coordination and communication should be there with each member to build a project towards the objective (Korte, R., Smith, K. A., and Li, C. Q. 2018) [15].

5. INDUSTRY OVERVIEW:

Kakunje Software Private Limited

Kakunje Software Private Limited is located in Mangalore, the company known for providing excellent and innovative customized software and hardware solutions as per the requirements of customers. The company deals with trading, manufacturing and services which they incorporated to provide e-commerce, technical and project training, website and mobile application designing, software and hardware solutions, electronic and electrical product manufacturing.

2012: Gopala Krishna Bhat Kakunje founded the firm Kakunje Software as a project development center and to provide technical training.

2013: The company established a unit called Techprosoft, which is a Printed Circuit Board (PCB) fabrication unit which develops innovative electronics and electrical devices and involved in software and hardware development.

2014: Kakunje Software registered as Small-Scale Industry under the government of Karnataka, Directorate Industries and Commerce.

2015: Kakunje Software registered and incorporated as company, Kakunje Software Private Limited under government of India ministry of corporate affairs, Corporate Identity Number U722000KA2015PTC083091. The company formed e-commerce site called electronickart.com under online e-commerce act of government of India, in order to trade electronics and electrical products. The company also got export-import license.

2016: Kakunje Software Private Limited considered as a software and hardware business covered under the definition of startup as per notification GSR 180(E) under MSME incubation center, NMAM institute of technology, Nitte, Kakunje Software Private Limited recognized as a startup by the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion, New Delhi. The company registered GST and got GSTIN: 29AAGCK0147D1ZS under government of Karnataka and government of India. Services come under 18% and products under 5% to 18% GST slabs.

Vision: Engineering Ideas

Mission: An Innovative Technology Company That Creates Revolutionary Intelligence

5.1 Organization Structure:

Kakunje Private Limited Company follows functional organizational structure with constructive management policy with democratic leadership style, where the organizational structure follows all tasks should be allocated by and reported to Managing Director, where management policy follows that the top management will consult each teams before taking any major decisions regarding the company, whereas leadership style allows all team members and employees to participate in decision making and exchange their ideas. So, the organizational structure helps them to lead towards success by taking careful decisions, proper work allocation based on employee specialized area of operation and proper supervision for quality management.

- **Chairman, Director:** Shankara Narayana Bhat Kakunje is present Chairman and Director of Kakunje Software Private Limited, the company has two Directors, he is top management of the company who takes part in major decisions in Annual General Meetings.
- **Director:** Malathi S.N Bhat is present Director of Kakunje Software Private Limited and she is the top management of the company who takes part in major decisions of the company.
- **Chief Executive Officer (CEO), Managing Director:** Gopala Krishna Bhat Kakunje is present CEO and Managing Director of Kakunje Software Private Limited and he is the top management

and manages middlelevel management, his activity consist decision making, coordination, strategicmanagement, marketing and human resource management of the company.

- **Chief Finance Officer (CFO):** Chief Finance Officer manages the finance, accounting and banking related issues and helps to maintain proper books of accounts and guides to manage the fund and cost of the company.
- **Web Developing Engineer:** Web developers who develop the websites and web applications.
- **Software and Mobile application Developing Engineer:** Software and app developers develops the personal computer and mobile applications.
- **Electronics Engineer:** Electronics Engineer who are in electronics and electrical product designs and manufacturers and they are into printed circuit board (PCB) designs.

5.2 Information about day-to-day organization activity:

- (1) Engineers who are in to Web, software and mobile application designers are works under the supervision of chief technological officer of the company.
- (2) The work allocation, salary payment and increments for employees being done on the basis of performance analysis report prepared by chief technological officer.
- (3) Employees also provides technical training and project development training for students and learning individuals and engaged with research and development activities.
- (4) Incubation center provided with one software and one hardware trainers to train the students of particular institutions with the support of all units of the company.

5.3 Products and Services:

(A) Products:

- **Automatic gas petrol switch:** Automatic gas petrol switch is the device which will help to run the vehicle by switching in to two fuels like petrol or gas. It is available in manual and automatic mode, in manual mode the person has to switch to next available fuel and in automatic mode the device will automatically switch to next available fuel if another is emptied.
- **Cell fan:** Cell fan is which the controlled through mobile phones using Bluetooth commands that anyone can easily use for office and residential purpose.
- **Intelligent gas trolley:** Intelligent gas trolley can be used for LPG cylinder management for domestic uses, it is an electronic gas weighing machine and displays in LCD by this the remaining gas can be calculated and it alerts when the weight reached below certain level as well as it alerts gas leakages by that it will secure the user.
- **E- attendance:** E- attendance is the system where the attendance of students or employees recorded through electronic RFID based attendance system, when RFID card shown in front of reader it will save it in microcontroller memory.
- **Smart auto pump:** Smart auto pump is the Bluetooth controlled pump which will automatically start the pump when water level reaches below level and switch off when water level reaches full level of the tank, it will help to minimize water and electricity wastage.
- **Smart light:** Smart light is less power consuming LED light which can be managed through mobile phones with Bluetooth controller.
- **Sun grid:** Sun grid micro inverter systems which transfer less inverter design with dual mode power inversion technique and digital display.
- **Areca tree climber:** Areca tree climber is a remote-control robot which climb the areca tree and harvest the areca nut without any damage.
- **ECG heart meter:** ECG heart meter is a portable ECG meter which can be used for electrocardiography that records and displays the ECG waves using portable device mobile phone application.
- **Intra oral dental scanner:** Intra oral dental scanner is a comprehensive orthodontic rehabilitation package which is used for dental diagnosis with 3D intra oral scanner taking high quality images of lower and upper jaws of the person.
- **Dental vibrator:** Dental vibrator is a comprehensive orthodontic rehabilitation package which will help the speed of dental treatment both lower and upper jaws of the person.

(B) Services:

- **Software development:** Software designing consist of development, designing, maintaining, redesigning of personal computer applications like ERP and billing solutions and software as per the requirements of customers.
- **Mobile application development:** Mobile application development consists of developing, designing and solutions for mobile phone applications and software as per the requirements of customers.
- **Web development and hosting:** Web development consist of website development, web application development which the company designs, develops, maintains and redesigns asper the requirements of their customer.
- **PCB designing and fabrication:** The company undertakes single, double and multi-layer printed circuit board designing and fabrication as per product requirement and customer requirement.
- **E-commerce:** The company formed e- commerce website called electronickart.com to undertake sales of electronics and electrical products and also the companies' own products.
- **Technical and Project training and Development:** The company started by providing technical training and project development training for students and interested learning individuals who involves in research and development activities.
- **Incubation Centre:** Kakunje Software Private Limited started incubation center for students in various Mangalore based institutions like St. Josef College, NMAM Institute, AJ Institute etc., as a part their technical training and project development unit to train and provide knowledge and make them employable and develop entrepreneurial skills.
- **Microcontroller programming and embedded system solutions:** The company known for their providing microcontroller programming and all type of embedded system solutions which attracts and creates clients for their business through their software and hardware development and designing, detailed analysis, prototyping and efficient delivery.

6. SWOC ANALYSIS :

SWOC (Strength, Weakness, Opportunities, and Challenges) analysis is used frequently to analyze organizational internal capabilities [16-17]. Many company analysis scholarly articles use SWOC analysis for understanding internal analysis [18-22], ABCD analysis as Stakeholder analysis [23-25], and PESTLE analysis as external organizational analysis [26-27].

6.1 Internal Attributes:

Strength:

- Strong impact of Kakunje as brand name, Kakunje Polymers, Kakunje Plastipacks, Kakunje Foods are some of trusted brands in the market
- Innovativeness and patented products like Intra oral dental scanner, Areca tree climber attract more clients.
- Highly skilled and trained employees
- Low cost manufacturing techniques of the company
- Top clients like BASF chemicals, Campco, HAL, AquaSys

Weakness:

- Company has small market share
- Less number of workers, so that they cannot take more project at a time
- Less financial support

6.2 External Attributes:

Opportunities:

- Market share growth opportunities
- Digital India support from government
- Increasing market demand for digitalization
- Growing market for artificial intelligence and robotics
- Increasing demand for online facilities and mobile application facilities
- Increasing demand for innovative products and services

- Research and Development activities
- Future development and demand for e-commerce

Challenges:

- Increasing competition from competitors in market Kakunje Software Private Limited has well established infrastructure facilities, the functions of company are operated from Mangalore head office. The competitors of Kakunje Software Private Limited are in the both hardware and software solution providers situated in Mangalore region as follows:
 - (i) Robosoft technologies, Mangalore
 - (ii) Cognizant technology solutions, Mangalore
 - (iii) Invenger technologies, Mangalore
 - (iv) Winman software, Mangalore
- Research and Development activities to develop existing products
- Expanding manpower in order to intake more valuable projects and to improve quality work
- Explore social problems using engineering and innovative ideas
- Expanding E-commerce business through more electronics and electrical products
- Developing more innovative, unique products and patent available to the market
- Developing Human Resource & finance departments
- Reaching education institutions through incubation centers in nearby districts

7. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION :

Software companies and information system companies are mainly dealing with inventing, updating and developing software and hardware technologies. It involves hardware products, computer software designing, mobile application designing, web-designing, which the work involved, developing or creating these products or services for their business purpose and developing for customer requirements is called a project. In order to manage these projects, the concept of project management is required, it is shown in the following figure 1.

Fig. 1: Aspects of Software Development Project Management

- Projects have starting time and finishing time, project management is required to complete the project and complete each process with in scheduled time in the software development projects.
- Project management is required to fulfill the requirement and bring all process and team together to reach the objective and manage the scope of software development project.
- Project management also required to manage the quality of software which they develop, the organizing and controlling each process will result in increasing the performance of the team which will resulting in better quality.
- Projects have limited budget that is project management is required to manage the financial and cost aspects and complete the project with in the estimated budget and to utilize the resources at maximum possible way.

7.1 Project Management in Software Development Process:

Software development process will be applied on projects in a software company in order to develop a software based on the requirements. These large-scale companies appoint a project manager, whereas small and medium scale companies appoint chief technical officer and some companies assign to the department heads.

Software development, mobile application development and web development has a similar process in every company that the process involves analysis, designing, development, implementation, monitoring and evaluation and the project manager has to manage all requirements of these projects. The process is depicted in the following figure 2.

(A) Software Development Project Management in General Sense:

Fig. 2: Software development process in general sense

7.2 Analysis:

The project begins with the end user of that product and objectives include:

- Software invented or developed for company’s personal use
- Software invented or developed for target market
- Software invented or developed for customer requirement

While developing a project there will be a certain requirement it may be for company or for market or for customer. The marketing team will analyze the market and brings customer and presents customer requirements to the company.

7.3 Designing:

In designing stage project manager does the planning and organizing activities. If the project is with innovative concept they have to invest more on research and development activities and they need professional team to development or otherwise they can only invest more on development activities and they need regular employees. The designing team will be formed and communicated them regarding the requirements of the customer and their time schedule. Design of the project based on the requirement includes resources required and number of employees required, activity schedule user interface, programming language selection, tools and data base selection, etc.

7.4 Developing:

Project manager controls activities and communicate the objectives the teams and provides resources. It is important to provide the time frame to complete the work, here developer does user interface design in order to produce desired output and does programming or coding using different programming languages based on specifications of the software. The important programming languages and operating systems used in the market are as follows:

- SQL (Sequel)

- Java
- C programming
- C++
- PHP
- Ruby on Rails
- iOS
- Python

Here, primary testing and validation will be carried out.

7.5 Testing:

In this stage project manager will appoint software tester, who analyzes the performance and each function of the developed software and web applications by using selenium software test and the tester approves the software to hosting, if the further changes required by the failure of developing stage or further major changes required by customer has to be cleared before hosting stage.

7.6 Hosting:

After successful testing the software company should assure the server for hosting the software or web application with the server which is managed by server engineer. Here, project manager gets actual cost and can compare the budgeted cost by that he can know profitability of the project and he can utilize the same technique for their upcoming projects.

7.7 Maintenance:

The company have to maintain the software or web application and availability with server, customer can further ask for changes in any time for that company should provide services and charge separately which will be extra income for the company.

(B) Software Development Project Management in Kakunje Software Limited:

Kakunje Software Private Limited is a small-scale software company. It attracts projects from business, service lenders, online shopping, companies and government clients. As the company deal with small software projects with the time period of one to five months, they do not appoint separate project manager in order to manage the project activities but CEO, CFO and CTO all together acts as project manager.

The software development project management process depicted in the figure 3 below.

Fig. 3: Software development process in Kakunje Software Limited

The company not only deals with software development projects but also web development projects, mobile application development projects and also hardware product development projects but software development is the core business of this company and major part of revenue is generated from this business.

1. Software and web application development project:
 - Designing and developing computer software based on customer requirement
 - Time period is one to five months
2. Mobile application development project:
 - Designing and developing mobile application and access to web application
 - Time period is one to five months
3. Hardware product development project:
 - Company research and development activities to solve social problems & develop existing technology, time period is based on research completion.

7.8 Business Analysis:

The company gets clients through CEO and he lists the customer requirements, analyzes the possibility of performance, suggest the changes and availability of services to the customer and prepares business documentation. Then CFO analyses and prepares budgeted cost and fixes the primary price to the project and collects the advance payment, the CTO of the company makes necessary resource arrangements and plan for user interface selection, programming, tools and data base to perform the project. Once the customer accepts the company requirement to perform the project, company signs an agreement with them begins the developing work.

7.9 Developing:

The developer designs the software project as customer requirement, the developing team is managed by CTO. Once the designing is completed then they divide the work within the team, developing process includes user interface design, programming or coding using programming languages, then for safety measures the does primary testing and validation process once it gets passed then communicate to the customer and makes necessary changes required.

7.10 Testing:

In testing process the developer test the web application using selenium software test to check whether the software and its functions works properly or not? then final changes are to be done the product will get approved by CTO. The company rent the server service from GoDaddy as they do not own server and does the hosting or publishes the product to customer use, the CEO issues safety and security certificate to the customer. The CFO analyzes the budgeted cost and actual cost then generates the invoice and collect the final payments. If, the customer requires further changes company charges separately as hourly work rate but the server maintenance charges are included in project cost.

7.11 Levels of Software Project Management:

Levels of software project management is the measurement of work complexity involved in the project based on this the software development process will be decided and changes in general development process are to be made. The Requisite organization and stratified system theory by Dr. Elliot Jaques explain about classification of project based on project complexity, time schedule and output of the project to manage project work, resource plan, project tasks and process. The levels of project are as follows:

Level 1:

Time frame is within three months and work is repetitive in nature, improvement in completed medium project are involved in this level

Level 2:

Time frame is three months to one year and work is repetitive and semi- repetitive in nature, small scale project development and improvement in medium and large project are involved in this level

Level 3:

Time frame is one to two years and work are semi- repetitive in nature, medium scale project development and improving completed big scale project are involved in this level

Level 4:

Time frame is 2 to 5 years and work are semi- repetitive and research and development in nature, medium scale and large-scale project development and improvement in functional system are involved

in this level

Level 5:

Time frame is 5 to 10 years and work are research and development, large scale project and improving group of functional systems are involved in this level

Level 6:

Time frame is 10 to 20 years and work are research and development, large scale projects, improving a value chain of the company are involved in this level

Level 7:

Time frame is 20 to 50 years and work are research and development, large scale projects, improving multiple value chain of the company are involved in this level.

7.12 Project Management Software

The digitalization era of project management is project management software, it is technological tool to estimation, planning, decision making, organizing and controlling of project activities used by project manager and project team.

The project management software comes with different types like personal, single user, computer software, mobile software, web based, multiple users and visual. It is helpful to maintain accuracy, control errors, less time consuming and also as evidence.

7.13 Functions of project management software:

- Cost budgeting, comparative analysis of budgeted cost with actual cost, cost control
- Project schedule estimation
- Project schedule division for each process and time management
- Project resource estimation
- Activity cost accounting
- Comparative analysis with historical data
- Project portfolio management

Project Management software:

Some common project management software as follows:

- Microsoft Project
- Atlassian JIRA
- CA Clarity
- Wrike
- Trello
- Liquid Planner

Table-1 below depicts a number table representor of required resource for managing the project, which is used for planning and allocating the technical staff based on schedule to the project.

Table 1: Resource allocating in general project management.

Month	1	2	3	4	5
Resource					
Designer	3	2	2	1	1
Developer	0	2	4	2	1
Tester	0	0	0	1	2
Total	3	4	6	4	4

Resource histogram is generated for the designer, developer and the tester is represented in a bar chart in the following figure 4.

Fig. 4: Resource allocation for managing general project.

- In software projects the human resource is allocated based on that company's software development process.
- The above resource histogram shows a five-month small project resource allocation in general as the company follows general software development process.
- Apart from these employees there will be project manager or management team and also some non-technical employees.

The following Table 2 represents resource allocation in Kakunje software development project.

Table 2: Resource allocation at Kakunje for 5 months project.

Month	1	2	3	4	5
Analyst	3	0	0	0	0
Developer	0	2	3	3	1
Tester	0	0	0	1	2
Total	3	2	3	4	3

Resource allocation histogram chart for five months project at Kakunje shown in the below figure 5.

Fig. 5: Resource allotment for five months project at Kakunje

The above histogram shows the 5-months resource histogram of Kakunje Software Private Limited based on their software development process.

- The company need Analyst as there is no project manager but there is project management team and

they act as analysts.

- There is no requirement of separate designer because the developer himself acts as designer and the number of requirements for designer is more but most of the companies prefer to hire a designer but when you see it from employee cost the Kakunje Software is doing good.
- Here the analysts are from project management team, developers and testers are from executive team but as it is seen in general resource allocation, designers, developers and testers all are from executive team only. The below depicted table-3 lists required resources.

Table 3: Resource utilization for one month project.

Weeks	1	2	3	4
Resource				
Analyst	1	0	0	0
Developer	0	1	1	2
Tester	0	0	0	1
Total	1	1	1	3

- The projects like small scale functioning software development like ERP software for small shops and upgradation of any research and development project.
- Research and development projects in large scale companies takes long time schedule like 10 months to two years. Table-4 below shows the statistics of resource histogram for R&D projects of 10 months, it generally requires more skilled employees and non-repetitive job.

Table 4: Project resource management for R&D software development projects

Month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Resource										
R&D	3	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Analyst	2	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Designer	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0
Developer	0	0	0	0	5	5	5	3	3	0
Tester	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	3
Total	5	5	4	3	6	5	5	4	4	3

- Here in addition to designer, developer, tester the research and development team and analysts are also given high importance as it involves huge resource management and high employee cost.

7.14 Software Development Project Schedule Management:

The project management major objective is to manage project schedule that will be from the time of acceptance to hosting the software project by managing and completing individual activities and bringing together to complete the project within the scheduled time period. The main two techniques apart from project management software are Project evaluation and review technique and Critical path method and these methods are mainly supported with variance analysis of project schedule and Gantt chart and how it changes based on the software development process is given in the figure-6 below.

Month	1	2	3	4	5
Activities					
1. Analysis					
2. Design					
3. Development					
4. Testing					
5. Hosting					

Fig 6: Gantt Chart for Software Development Project Schedule of 5 Months

- The figure shows that for a five-month schedule project how a company can divide their total time

in to individual activity schedules and the management team allocates minimum and maximum time that an individual activity can use that will impact on their project completion time period, PERT and CPM also depends on this schedule.

- Figure-7 below represents the Gantt chart of Software development 1-month project at Kakunje Software Private Limited and also this can be followed by all companies for small scale software development projects which does not involves research activity.

Month	1	2	3	4
Activities				
1. Analysis				
2. Design				
3. Development				
4. Testing				
5. Hosting				

Fig 7: Gantt Chart for Software Development Project Schedule of 5 Month

- These projects will help to fill the extra time which they were getting while developing the 5-month scheduled projects and helps to provide daily work and improve the skills of their employees
- This type of projects generally does not require project management software support and it can manage manually as the work complexity is very less and the designing and testing work will be very less and it involves more analysis and development activity
- There will be less work in the begging of the project schedule and increase at the end of the project as shown in below figure-8, which should be highly monitored by the project management team.

Fig. 8: Monitoring Project Management

7.15 Testing:

- Activity 1 represents the software development project acceptance and analysis according to the development process, from activity 1 to activity 2 it takes maximum 1 month.
- Activity 2 represents the designing process of software development process and after 1-month activity 3 begins and after 3 month activity 4 begins and these are closely interconnected activities.
- Activity 3 represents developing stage which is done along with activity 4 and after 2 months it is ready for activity 5.
- Activity 4 represents testing stage which the quality of activity 3 is to be measured and after 1 month it is ready for activity 5.
- Activity 5 represents the hosting stage and it is the completion of software development process.
- 1 to 2= 1 month
- 2 to 3= 1 month
- 2 to 4= 3 month
- 3 to 5= 2 month

- 4 to 5= 1 month
- This will help to know critical path to complete the project shortest way and we can say that 1-2-3-5 is shortest than 1-2-4-5. So, 1-2-3-5 is the critical path of this software development project. This is shown in the following table-5.

Table 5: Estimation of project duration and its relationship

Task Name	Duration in months			Relationship
	Optimistic	Most Likely	Pessimistic	
1	0.5	1	1.5	Start, 1 month
2	0.5	1	1.5	after task 1, 1 month
3	1	2	3	after task 2, 2 months
4	0.25	0.5	1	after task 3, 0.5 month
5	0.25	0.5	1	After task 4, End, 0.5 month

- Variance= ((Pessimistic Time- Optimistic Time)/6)².
- The optimistic time, most likely time and pessimistic time are derived from Gantt chart and PERT and CPM together and the task represents each stage in the software development process.
- The variance calculation mainly required for risk management in project schedule management, that is CPM will help to identify shortest way to complete the project effectively and variance help to identify the variability in project duration, by this a project manager can identify the schedule risk and take preventive measures in designing project schedule.
- The project manager estimates the optimistic time, most likely time and pessimistic time in order to manage the overall time by managing individuals time taken for a task, so that he can prevent the delay in completing the project is depicted below in table-6.

Table 6: Expected task duration and its variance

Task Name	Duration in months			Expected task duration	Variance
	Optimistic	Most Likely	Pessimistic		
1	0.5	1	1.5	1	0.029
2	0.5	1	1.5	1	0.029
3	1	2	3	2	0.11
4	0.25	0.5	1	0.5	0.016
5	0.25	0.5	1	0.5	0.016

7.16 Software Development Project Cost Management:

Cost management is one of the major objectives of software development project management and it is the major responsibility of project manager or project management team. The cost management concept includes cost estimation and budgeting, cost control, cost reduction, pricing decision, profitability management, cost risk management, cost recording.

7.17 Methods of Software Development Project Cost Management:

- The general software development project cost budgeting in small scale and medium scale companies are made on historical cost basis, only special projects which involves more research and development activities are done through zero based cost budgeting.
- The COCOMO model or constructive cost model is developed mainly for software development project management using regression formula which requires historical cost data, it is most preferable cost budgeting model in the industry.

7.18 Estimated Cost Data for a Software Development Project:

Table-7 showing estimated cost and income records for medium scale project in a small company (5-month work with worth INR Rs. 10 Lakhs).

Table 7: Estimated cost in completing a project

Particulars	Amount in INR Lakhs
TOTAL PROJECT WORTH	10.00
(LESS) EXPENSES:	
Employee Cost	04.50
Telephone and Internet Charges	0.10
Electricity Charges	0.10
Server Charges	0.05
Maintenance Charges	0.75
Transportation Charges	0.05
Stationary Charges	0.05
System Maintenance Charges	0.25
Miscellaneous Expenses	0.25
Marketing Expenses	0.10
PROJECT INCOME	3.80

- If a small company take up a five-month work with INR Rs. 10 lakh worth project which is generally a semi-repetitive work project without any research and development activity they can make INR Rs. 3.80 lakh income excluding office maintenance expenses, interest, taxes which they can get overall 35% as net profit.
- The above data estimated on historical data of the small-scale software development company same as Kakunje Software Private Limited software development projects are repetitive and semi-repetitive projects.
- The biggest cost for every software development company is employee cost and high attrition rates which could maximize the overall employee cost per year, outsourcing and automation will be the solution for this problem.
- The 1-month schedule project cost and income vary based on their functions it might be only 30,000 INR Rupees if it involves only upgradation and maintenance work but also company can get up to 2.00 INR Lakhs Rupees if it is a full-fledged project involving more work.
- This type of project will help to generate more income along with medium scale projects as it requires less resources the developing cost will be less and company can earn more by taking more small projects.
- It helps the company to manage their fixed cost and for this type projects there will be time and work basis payment system which the salary payment for the employees will be on hourly basis and some companies follow commission on number of small projects they complete within a month.
- When it compared with 5-month scheduled project and research and development project it will cost very less and earn more as the company can complete more projects.

8. FINDINGS :

8.1 Methods of software development projects:

The software development project management is the key functioning area of any software development company, the management style of software development projects differs with the small scale and large-scale companies and the size of the project and target customers. The software development projects in large scale companies are generally involves huge investment, high research and development activities, long term time period and large resources and it involves more of non-repetitive jobs. The software development projects in small scale and medium scale companies involves small investments, small term time period, less resources, minimum research and development activities and it involves more repetitive jobs. All new software development projects are accepted only after doing the feasibility test which is also called as business analysis or evaluation of possibility of performance which involves financial feasibility, resource feasibility, cost feasibility, time feasibility and market feasibility. The project management methodologies are the basis for managing the projects and the project management structure is designed on the basis of the underlying methodology.

8.2 Software development project manager

- There is no compulsion to appoint a project manager, in small scale companies' departmental heads all together acts as project manager and works in a team but it works only because they are getting less projects or small projects compared to large scale companies, in large scale companies there should be a project manager in order to reduce the complexity in project management
- The importance of project manager in big project management is too high that, he should manage all the functioning areas of project and he have to be connected with all key persons of the project, activities like project team management, project cost management, project schedule management, project report recording, customer requirement management, project communication management, project risk management

8.3 Project complexity management:

- Project complexity arises due to risks in the project management like inflation or cost risk, employee risk, project completion or schedule risk, resource risk, communication risk, market and competitor risk, these should be analyzed and managed by project manager or management team
- Present days most of the companies uses project management software which is easy to access and includes most of all functioning areas of project management like budgeting, cost management, finance planning, schedule management, PERT, CPM, internal communication which will reduce the complexity of the project management team.

Table-8 displaying the comparative cost and income records for medium scale project in a small company (5-month schedule small project):

Table 8: Cost analysis of a small company

Particulars	Amount in INR Lakhs	Amount in INR Lakhs	Amount in INR Lakhs
TOTAL PROJECT WORTH	10.00	15.00	20.00
(LESS) EXPENSES:			
Employee Cost	4.50	4.50	4.50
Telephone and Internet Charges	0.10	0.15	0.20
Electricity Charges	0.10	0.15	0.20
Server Charges	0.05	0.05	0.05
Maintenance Charges	0.75	1.50	2.25
Transportation Charges	0.05	0.10	0.15
Stationary Charges	0.05	0.10	0.15
System Maintenance Charges	0.25	0.50	1.00
Miscellaneous Expenses	0.25	0.50	1.00
Marketing Expenses	0.10	0.20	0.30
PROJECT INCOME	3.80	7.25	14.70

- The above comparative cost- income statement shows how a small-scale software company plans to maximize their income and profitability of the business by increasing the number of project intake there by increasing the sales.
- This method will help the company to design the target and effective utilization of resources and provide the service for better price to the customer.
- The challenge is employee cost which fixed per month in order to overcome this and make huge profit the company should increase their sales and taking more projects also requires time each project should be completed within a time frame and sometimes it needs over time work and extra payment.

9. SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION :

The company develops their business by implementing the concept of project management and project manager supported with modern project management software support, which will help the company to

better result of managing time, resource, cost, performance, quality altogether a good value to the customer.

(1) Appointing a Project Manager:

- Software development companies who do not appoint a project manager will divide the same work with all departmental heads by thinking it might increase overall employee cost
- If the company can appoint a project manager who handles all process and multiple projects, the departmental heads can concentrate more on their departmental activities which will automatically increase the performance of the business and help to manage multiple projects, quality of each project, business portfolio management, better communication with all department employees and to maintain good relation with customers and to run the business in a systematical way

(2) Utilizing the Project Management Software:

- The software development companies can utilize the project management software in order to manage the multiple projects and manage individual projects efficiently
- Plan the activities of project in a systematical way will increase the performance and quality of the work
- Design the schedule and resources in each stage of development and record employee cost will help to time and employee management
- Small companies can get better results even though they do not appoint project manager

The analysis, interpretation and findings of this study convey that by adopting project management system the software development company can manage the business in efficient and profitable manner. As the history of project management reminds that most of the industries started to implement this concept by observing the success of mega engineering projects because of the effective utilization of project management concept.

The project management will help to finish the project within time by managing time schedule, run the business profitably by managing cost effectiveness of the project, increase the performance by maintaining good communication flow within the company and with customer and best utilization of resources to get good quality product, to manage overall internal and external risks of the project of any type of software development projects.

The large-scale software development companies care efficiently using the project management concept and it helps them to manage mega projects and multiple projects. In medium scale and small-scale software development companies all departmental heads together work as project manager but it will lead conflicts between departments and there will be less effective communication which will lead to decrease in the overall performance. In unstructured small-scale software development companies who are getting small and less projects they do not go for project management but they do only cost and time management and that will affect the quality of the product.

Hence, in the modern days the companies want to reduce the number of employees and they also want to reduce the human efforts and human errors by adopting robotics and artificial intelligence technology. Project management software actually reduces the project manager's efforts and human errors to manage multiple projects currently large-scale companies are utilizing this technology but in medium and small-scale software companies it removes the presence of project manager where the employees themselves utilize the technology and manage the project as they were getting less number and small projects compared to large scale companies.

REFERENCES :

- [1] Das, K., & Sagara, H. (2017). State and the IT Industry in India. *Economic & Political Weekly*, 52(41), 57-64.
- [2] Gökçöz, F., & Güvercin, M. T. (2018). Investigating the total factor productivity changes in the top ICT companies worldwide. *Electronic Commerce Research*, 18(4), 791-811.
- [3] Jiang, J. J., Klein, G., & Fernandez, W. D. (2018). From project management to program management: an invitation to investigate programs where IT plays a significant role. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 19(1), 1-9.

- [4] Demirkesen, S., & Ozorhon, B. (2017). Impact of integration management on construction project management performance. *International Journal of Project Management*, 35(8), 1639-1654.
- [5] Taks, Marijke, Kesenne, Stefan, Chalip, Laurence, & Green, B. Christine. (2011). Economic Impact Analysis Versus Cost Benefit Analysis: The Case of a Medium-Sized Sport Event. *International Journal of Sport Finance*, 6(3), 187-203.
- [6] Hochdörffer, J., Buegin, J., Vlachou, E., Zogopoulos, V., Lanza, G., & Mourtzis, D. (2018). Holistic approach for integrating customers in the design, planning, and control of global production networks. *CIRP Journal of Manufacturing Science and Technology*, 23(1), 98-107.
- [7] Gonovski, V. (2017). Risk Management in Project Management–Basics. *Knowledge International Journal*, 16(3), 995-1000.
- [8] Cotterell, M., & Hughes, B. (1995). Software project management, *International Thomson Computer Press*.
- [9] Aanbari, F. T., & Young Hoon Kwak, P. F. T. A. (2008). Impact on Project Management of Allied Disciplines: *Trends and Future of Project Management Practices and Research*, 5(2), 324-331.
- [10] Almaamari, G., Williams, N., & Atkinson, R. (2017). Stakeholders' trust and power dynamic in tourism resort projects in a developing country, *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, 8(4), 77-89.
- [11] Korte, R., Smith, K. A., & Li, C. Q. (2018). The Role of Empathy in Entrepreneurship: A Core Competency of the Entrepreneurial Mindset. *Advances in Engineering Education*, 7(1), 1-7.
- [12] Sanz-Llopis, J., & Ostermann, M. (2020). Innovation in project management through framing and challenge redefinition. *International journal of managing projects in business*, 5(1), 234-239.
- [13] Petersen, K. W. (2020). Project Management Office Performance Variables that Influence Project Success: A Correlational Study, *Dissertation of Capella University*, 121-135.
- [14] Arashpour, M., Abbasi, B., Arashpour, M., Hosseini, M. R., & Yang, R. (2017). Integrated management of on-site, coordination and off-site uncertainty: Theorizing risk analysis within a hybrid project setting. *International Journal of Project Management*, 35(4), 647-655.
- [15] Korte, R., Smith, K. A., & Li, C. Q. (2018). The Role of Empathy in Entrepreneurship: A Core Competency of the Entrepreneurial Mindset. *Advances in Engineering Education*, 7(1), 1-12.
- [16] Holla, R. (2017). A Study on SWOC Analysis of Reliance Ijo. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 2(1), 42-47.
- [17] Aithal, P. S., & Kumar, P. M. (2015). Applying SWOC analysis to an institution of higher education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 5(7), 231-247.
- [18] Vijayakumar, S., & Nethravathi, P. S. (2021). The Mega Conglomerate of India-Success Story of Growth of Reliance Industries: A Case Study. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 5(1), 143-154.
- [19] Puneeth, B. R., & Nethravathi, P. S. (2021). Paytm's Journey Towards Digital Payment in India–A Case Study. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 5(2), 125-141.
- [20] Puneeth, B. R., & Nethravathi, P. S. (2021). Bicycle Industry in India and its Challenges–A Case Study. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 5(2), 62-74.
- [21] Murthy, A., & Nethravathi, P. S. (2021). The Evolution of the E-Vehicle Industry and its Path Towards Setting up Dominance in Automobile Industry-A Case Study. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 5(2), 38-49.
- [22] Vijayakumar, S., & Nethravathi, P. S. (2021). The Growth of IT & BPM Industry Services and its Journey towards 'Make in India' –A Case Study. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 5(1), 232-243.

- [23] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V., & Kumar, P. M. (2015). A new ABCD technique to analyze business models & concepts. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 5(4), 409-423.
- [24] Aithal, P. S. (2016). Study on ABCD analysis technique for business models, business strategies, operating concepts & business systems. *International Journal in Management and Social Science*, 4(1), 95-115.
- [25] Aithal, P. S. (2017). ABCD Analysis as Research Methodology in Company Case Studies. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 2(2), 40-54.
- [26] Team, F. M. E. (2013). PESTLE analysis. *Strategy Skills*. www.free-management-ebooks.com.
- [27] Aithal, P. S. (2017). An effective method of developing business case studies based on company analysis. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 2(1), 16-27.

A Study on Optimization and Allocation of Requirements during the Software Development Life Cycle in Digital Align Private Limited

Nethravathi P. S.¹, Vaikunta Pai T.², Shwetha Bhat³ & P. S. Aithal⁴

¹ Professor, Institute of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India.

ORCIDID: 0000-0001-5447-8673; Email: nethrakumar590@gmail.com

² Faculty, Institute of Computer Science & Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India.

ORCID: 0000-0001-6100-9023; Email: vaikunthpai@gmail.com

³ RPA Developer, Digital Align, Mangalore, India; Email: shwethabhat012@gmail.com

⁴ Professor, Institute of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India.

ORCIDID: 0000-0002-4691-8736; Email: psaithal@gmail.com

Area of the Paper: Computer Science.

Type of the Paper: Research Analysis.

Type of Review: Peer Reviewed as per [\[C/O/P/E\]](#) guidance.

Indexed In: OpenAIRE.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6656441>

Google Scholar Citation: [IJCSBE](#)

How to Cite this Paper:

Nethravathi, P. S., Vaikunta Pai, T., Bhat, Shwetha, & Aithal, P. S., (2022). A Study on Optimization and Allocation of Requirements during the Software Development Life Cycle in Digital Align Private Limited. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE)*, 6(1), 451-469. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6656441>

International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)

A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India.

Crossref DOI : <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJCSBE.2581.6942.0174>

Paper Submission: 09/04/2022

Paper Publication: 15/06/2022

© With Authors.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution Non-Commercial 4.0 International License](#) subject to proper citation to the publication source of the work.

Disclaimer: The scholarly papers as reviewed and published by the Srinivas Publications (S.P.), India are the views and opinions of their respective authors and are not the views or opinions of the S.P. The S.P. disclaims of any harm or loss caused due to the published content to any party.

A Study on Optimization and Allocation of Requirements during the Software Development Life Cycle in Digital Align Private Limited

Nethravathi P. S.¹, Vaikunta Pai T.², Shwetha Bhat³ & P. S. Aithal⁴

¹ Professor, Institute of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India.

ORCIDID: 0000-0001-5447-8673; Email: nethrakumar590@gmail.com

² Faculty, Institute of Computer Science & Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India.

ORCID: 0000-0001-6100-9023; Email: vaikunthpai@gmail.com

³ RPA Developer, Digital Align, Mangalore., India; Email: shwethabhat012@gmail.com

⁴ Professor, Institute of Computer and Information Sciences, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India.

ORCIDID: 0000-0002-4691-8736; Email: psaithal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Purpose: In order to face the challenge of optimization and allocation of necessary requirements to complete a project with in the allocated time period, the project manager must be efficient in applying different technical skills and managerial strategies to the project management process. In order to develop a software and RPA product, a company schedules different process as per the specified order and unique requirements. As the history of project management reminds that most of the industries started to implement this concept by observing the success of mega engineering projects because of the effective utilization of project management concept.

Objective: This work is carried to understand the concepts of project management in software firms. To investigate the implementation and importance of these concepts and to know the role of project manager in managing the process in software development.

Methodology: Digital Align Private Limited, Mangalore, provides excellent and state-of-the-art customized software and hardware solutions as per the necessities of customers. In order to manage the project activities CEO, CFO and CTO all together acts as project manager. The software development project management process starts by identifying needs and recommending solutions, which can be delivered to value its stakeholders. At the second phase the actual development will begin and the developed software will be tested according to customer requirements.

Findings/Results: Budgeting, cost management, finance planning etc., represented by CPM and PERT charts by using Microsoft Project and Atlassian JIRA project management software. The project resources, which are used to manage the project and allocation of technical staff are represented by histogram. With the help of Gantt Chart software development project schedule of 5 month are shown.

Conclusion: To manage Digital Align business in an effective and gainful manner, the company managed overall internal and external risks of the project. By using the project management software, the company condensed the project manager's efforts and human errors to manage multiple projects.

Paper Type: Case study-based Research Analysis

Keywords: Project Management, Software Development Life Cycle, Process, Software Company, Requirement Specification.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Software Industry or Information Technology Industry deals with software and hardware development [1]. Maintaining business includes trading, manufacturing, servicing activities. The software industry started since 1953 and first software provider is computer Usage Company in 1955, IBM and UNIVAC are the commercial computer dears in 1960s. In 1959 computer sciences corporation was founded and helped to develop advanced computer technology and automatic processing technology. Now the world-wide size of software industry estimated as USD\$ 429.9 billion [2]. The Project Management is the management activities of initiating, planning, organizing, controlling and closing the assigned project work by satisfying the requirements and manage cost benefit of the project within assigned time period [3]. The word Project is any activity undertaken which involves research design and proper planning with set of interrelated activities to be executed by an individual or by a team to achieve particular purpose over a fixed cost and time frame, the activities of Project Management is managed by the Project Manager. The Project Manager is a key person who manages the project and overall responsibilities of the success of project by effectively managing the project management activities. It includes project initiation to project closure, technical and non-technical skills to manage a project. The duties of project manager are decision making, developing schedules, project cost management, risk management, project team management, documentation and reporting, contacting with vendors, quality control, etc. [4].

Project Cost Management is the activity which does cost-benefit analysis of the project [5]. It is the method to manage the overall cost of project which helps to generate profit, this activity deals with cost budgeting using historical data and complete the project within budgeted cost, which will include project development cost, labor cost, material costs and to manage risk of the project like inflation, natural disasters, unexpected costs. Project management process is which the general development stages of a project [6].

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

- (1) To study and understand the project management concept in software development companies.
- (2) To analyze the implementation and importance of project management concept in software development companies.
- (3) To analyze the role and importance project manager in order to manage the software development process.
- (4) To evaluate the impacts and challenges involved in project management to software development companies.

3. METHODOLOGY:

The study is based on data collected from primary sources and secondary sources as shown below:

- The primary sources of data are collected by direct interviewing the CEO and Managing Director, departmental heads, and employees of Digital Align Private Limited.
- The secondary sources of data are collected by referring few textbooks related to project management concepts, articles, websites, and literature reviews related to project management and software project management concepts, referring to finance and cost data of Digital Align Private Limited.

4. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Project Management regarded as a high priority as all organizations involved in implementing new undertakings, innovation and challenges. Project may be individually diverse, however over a time, some tools, management techniques and problem-solving techniques results in bringing project to a successful end (Gonovski, V. 2017) [7]. Software project management is a key idea about the planning, monitoring and control of software projects. Projects to produce software are worthwhile only if the satisfy real needs and examine how it can identify stakeholders in a project and their objectives (Cotterell, M., and Hughes, B. 1995) [8]. Project management is the combination of project scope management, project cost management, project time management, project quality management, project human resource management, project risk management, project communication management (Aanbari, F. T., and Kwak, Y. H. 2018) [9]. Project management deals with the pre-determined cost,

quality and pre-determined schedule of a project, and is managed by systematic way and the final result should be accepted by others is called success of a project (Almaamari, G., Williams, N., and Atkinson, R. 2017) [10].

There are differences in practicing project management concept with each industry, the maturity of repeated work project is low and the project involving research expansion activity is very high (Korte, R., Smith, K. A., and Li, C. Q. 2018) [11]. Project manager should aware of the project risk involved to complete the project successfully, to manage that he can predict and control the risks by taking reference from similar projects which will save the investment and time (Sanz-Llopis, J., and Ostermann, M. 2020) [12].

Project management office which headed by project manager is team which manages whole activities of project management and they are responsible for project failure, project success and that is the result of coordination between them and execution team (Petersen, K. W. 2020) [13]. Project risk management is the process of identification of risk factor, assessing the risk effects, developing strategic solutions, implementing solutions, control the risk factors, managing the crisis, recover from the crisis related to project management (Arashpour, M., Abbasi, B., Arashpour, M., Hosseini, M. R., and Yang, R. 2017) [14]. The Project will successful when there is coordination in the management team and executing team, the team coordination and communication should be there with each member to build a project towards the objective (Korte, R., Smith, K. A., and Li, C. Q. 2018) [15].

5. INDUSTRY OVERVIEW :

Digital Align Private Limited

Digital Align Private Limited is located in Mangalore, the company known for providing excellent and innovative customized software and hardware solutions as per the requirements of customers. The company deals with trading, manufacturing and services which they incorporated to provide e-commerce, technical and project training, website and Digital Assistant for customers using AlignXcel, software and hardware solutions, electronic and electrical product manufacturing.

The company was founded in the year 2015, by Rajesh Patil.

2021: Rajesh Patil Belgaum made the firm Digital Align as Digital Align India Pvt Ltd, a project development center and to provide technical training. The objective was to build a FinTech product and providing software development and automation services to banks in US.

2021: Digital Align registered and incorporated as a company, Digital Align Private Limited under government of India ministry of corporate affairs,.

2022: The company started evolving as a product based company initiative of AlignXcel. By the end of 2022 introduce digital assistants and software products such as GenieOCR, App and DASmartlog API.

Vision: Engineering Ideas

Mission: An Innovative Technology Company That Creates FinTech Products for local banks and credit union companies.

5.1 Organization Structure:

Digital Align Private Limited Company follows functional organizational structure with constructive management policy with democratic leadership style, where the organizational structure follows all tasks should be allocated by and reported to Managing Director, where management policy follows that the top management will consult each teams before taking any major decisions regarding the company, whereas leadership style allows all team members and employees to participate in decisionmaking and exchange their ideas. So, the organizational structure helps them to lead towards success by taking careful decisions, proper work allocation based on employee specialized area of operation and proper supervision for quality management.

- **Chairman, Director:** Rajesh Patil Belgaum is present Chairman and Director of Digital Align Software Private Limited, the company has two Directors, he is top management of the company who takes part in major decisions in Annual General Meetings.
- **Director:** Mahantesh Patil is present Director of Digital Align Private Limited and he is the top management of the company who takes part in major decisions of the company.
- **Vice President, Sales & Business Development:** Kevin Murphy is Vice President who manages

Sales and Business Development.

- **Managing Director:** Athul Kakathkar is present Managing Director of Digital Align Private Limited and he is the top management and manages middle level management, his activity consist decision making, coordination, strategic management, marketing and human resource management of the company.
- **Chief Finance Officer (CFO): Lakshmi Parameshwaran,** Chief Finance Officer manages the finance, accounting and banking related issues and helps to maintain proper books of accounts and guides to manage the fund and cost of the company.
- **Web Developing Engineer:** Web developers who develop the websites and web applications.
- **RPA and Software application Developing Engineer:** Software and App developers develops the personal computer and mobile applications.

5.2 Information about day-to-day organization activity:

- (1) Engineers who are in to Web, software and mobile application designers are works under the supervision of chief technological officer of the company.
- (2) The work allocation, salary payment and increments for employees being done on the basis of performance analysis report prepared by chief technological officer.
- (3) Employees also provides technical training and project development training for students and learning individuals and engaged with research and development activities.

5.3 Products and Services:

(A) Products:

- **Digital Assistants:** Fintech Assistants which helps staffs of various credit unions, local banks manual, mundane, boring, tedious work.
- **DASmartLogs:** Using Elastic search technology, to store daily status log files and to retrieve logs using DASmartLogs API. This API also helps in providing business insights, ROI for the company.
- **Genie OCR:** Intelligent OCR Application which involves Human in the loop where Data extracted from huge Pdf is displayed using Genie OCR App to verify and review the extracted information.
- **Appraisal App:** An Web Application which helps to manage Appraiser Process and supports Loan Officer to review the Appraisal Process.
- **AlignXcel Marketplace, Process Portal:** This is a marketplace where users can buy new digital assistant products, request for new products and view bot performance all in single app.
- **Web-app for On-demand Process:** An web application to trigger On Demand Process by providing some inputs required to run the process for the clients.

(B) Services:

- **Software development:** Software designing consist of development, designing, maintaining, redesigning of personal computer applications like Appraisal App and digital solutions and software as per the requirements of customers.
- **Web development and hosting:** Web development consist of website development, web application development which the company designs, develops, maintains and redesigns as per the requirements of their customer.

6. SWOC ANALYSIS :

SWOC (Strength, Weakness, Opportunities, and Challenges) analysis is used frequently to analyze organizational internal capabilities [16-19]. Here, the strength and weakness are analysed as internal attributes and Opportunities and challenges are analysed as external attributes:

6.1 Internal Attributes:

Strength:

- Strong impact of AlignXcel as brand name, DASmartLogs, GenieOCR Process Portal are some of trusted brands in the market.
- Innovativeness Digital Assistants like PIFCU Mortgage, Skyone , OCR Web, Web App
- Highly skilled and trained employees.
- Low cost manufacturing techniques of the company.

- Top clients like Toyota Financial Savings Bank, PIFCU Credit Union, SkyOne Credit Union, Gesa Credit Union Companies.

Weakness:

- Company has small market share
- Less number of workers, so that they cannot take more projects at a time
- Less financial support

6.2 External Attributes:

Opportunities:

- Market share growth opportunities
- Digital India support from government
- Increasing market demand for digitalization
- Growing market for artificial intelligence and robotics
- Increasing demand for online facilities and mobile application facilities
- Increasing demand for innovative products and services
- Research and Development activities
- Future development and demand for e-commerce

Challenges:

- Increasing competition from competitors in the market Digital Align Private Limited has well-established infrastructure facilities, the functions of company are operated from the Mangalore head office. The competitors of Digital Align Private Limited are in the software solution providers situated in Mangalore region as follows:
 - (i) Robosoft technologies, Mangalore
 - (ii) Cognizant technology solutions, Mangalore
 - (iii) Invenger technologies, Mangalore
 - (iv) Diya Systems, Mangalore
- Research and Development activities to develop existing products
- Expanding manpower in order to intake more valuable projects and to improve quality work
- Explore social problems using engineering and innovative ideas
- Expanding RPA and Salesforce business through more electronics and digital products
- Developing more innovative, unique products and patent available to the market
- Developing Human Resource & finance departments
- Reaching education institutions through incubation centers in nearby districts

7. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION :

Software companies and information system companies are mainly dealing with inventing, updating and developing software and hardware technologies. It involves hardware products, computersoftware designing, mobile application designing, web-designing, which the work involved, developing or creating these products or services for their business purpose and developing for customer requirements is called a project. In order to manage these projects, the concept of project management is required, it is shown in the following figure 1.

Fig. 1: Aspects of Software Development Project Management

- Projects have starting time and finishing time, project management is required to complete the project and complete each process with in scheduled time in the software development projects.
- Project management is required to fulfill the requirement and bring all process and team together to reach the objective and manage the scope of software development project.
- Project management also required to manage the quality of software which they develop, the organizing and controlling each process will result in increasing the performance of the team which will resulting in better quality.
- Projects have limited budget that is project management is required to manage the financial and cost aspects and complete the project with in the estimated budget and to utilize the resources at maximum possible way.

7.1 Project Management in Software Development Process:

Software development process will be applied on projects in a software company in order to develop a software based on the requirements. These large-scale companies appoint a project manager, whereas small and medium scale companies appoint chief technical officer and some companies assign to the department heads.

Software development, mobile application development and web development has a similar process in every company that the process involves analysis, designing, development, implementation, monitoring and evaluation and the project manager has to manage all requirements of these projects. The process is depicted in the following figure 2.

Software Development Project Management in General Sense:

Fig. 2: Software development process in general sense

7.2 Analysis:

The project begins with the end user of that product and objectives include:

- Software invented or developed for company's personal use
- Software invented or developed for target market
- Software invented or developed for customer requirement

While developing a project there will be a certain requirement it may be for company or for market or for customer. The marketing team will analyze the market and brings customer and presents customer requirements to the company.

7.3 Designing:

In designing stage project manager does the planning and organizing activities. If the project is with innovative concept they have to invest more on research and development activities and they need professional team to development or otherwise they can only invest more on development activities and they need regular employees. The designing team will be formed and communicated them regarding the requirements of the customer and their time schedule. Design of the project based on therequirement includes resources required and number of employees required, activity schedule user interface,

programming language selection, tools and data base selection, etc.

7.4 Developing:

Project manager controls activities and communicate the objectives the teams and provides resources. It is important to provide the time frame to complete the work, here developer does user interface design in order to produce desired output and does programming or coding using different programming languages based on specifications of the software. The important programming languages and operating systems used in the market are as follows:

- SQL (Sequel)
- Uipath
- C# programming
- Salesforce
- PHP
- VB
- iOS
- Python

Here, primary testing and validation will be carried out.

7.5 Testing:

In this stage project manager will appoint software tester, who analyzes the performance and each function of the developed software and web applications by using selenium software test and the tester approves the software to hosting, if the further changes required by the failure of developing stage or further major changes required by customer has to be cleared before hosting stage.

7.6 Hosting:

After successful testing the software company should assure the server for hosting the software or web application with the server which is managed by server engineer. Here, project manager gets actual cost and can compare the budgeted cost by that he can know profitability of the project and he can utilize the same technique for their upcoming projects.

7.7 Maintenance:

The company have to maintain the software or web application and availability with server, customer can further ask for changes in any time for that company should provide services and charge separately which will be extra income for the company.

Software Development Project Management in Digital Align Limited:

Digital Align Private Limited is a small-scale software company. It attracts projects from business, service lenders, online shopping, companies and government clients. As the company deal with small software projects with the time period of one to five months, they do not appoint separate project manager in order to manage the project activities but CEO, CFO and CTO all together acts as project manager. The software development project management process depicted in the figure 3.

The company not only deals with software development projects but also web development projects, mobile application development projects and also hardware product development projects but software development is the core business of this company and major part of revenue is generated from this business.

1. Software and web application development project:

- Designing and developing computer software based on customer requirement
- Time period is one to five months

2. Mobile application development project:

- Designing and developing mobile application and access to web application
- Time period is one to five months

3. Hardware product development project:

- Company research and development activities to solve social problems & develop existing technology, time period is based on research completion.

Fig. 3: Software development process in Digital Align Limited

7.8 Business Analysis:

The company gets clients through CEO and he lists the customer requirements, analyzes the possibility of performance, suggest the changes and availability of services to the customer and prepares business documentation. Then CFO analyses and prepares budgeted cost and fixes the primary price to the project and collects the advance payment, the CTO of the company makes necessary resource arrangements and plan for user interface selection, programming, tools and data base to perform the project. Once the customer accepts the company requirement to perform the project, company signs an agreement with them begins the developing work.

7.9 Developing:

The developer designs the software project as customer requirement, the developing team is managed by CTO. Once the designing is completed then they divide the work within the team, developing process includes user interface design, programming or coding using programming languages, then for safety measures the does primary testing and validation process once it gets passed then communicate to the customer and makes necessary changes required.

7.10 Testing:

In testing process the developer test the web application using selenium software test to check whether the software and its functions works properly or not? Then final changes are to be done the product will get approved by CTO. The company rent the server service from GoDaddy as they do not own server and does the hosting or publishes the product to customer use, the CEO issues safety and security certificate to the customer. The CFO analyzes the budgeted cost and actual cost then generates the invoice and collect the final payments. If, the customer requires further changes company charges separately as hourly work rate but the server maintenance charges are included in project cost.

7.11 Levels of Software Project Management:

Levels of software project management is the measurement of work complexity involved in the project based on this the software development process will be decided and changes in general development process are to be made. The Requisite organization and stratified system theory by Dr. Elliot Jaquez explain about classification of project based on project complexity, time schedule and output of the project to manage project work, resource plan, project tasks and process. The levels of project are as follows:

Level 1:

Time frame is within three months and work is repetitive in nature, improvement in completed medium project are involved in this level.

Level 2:

Time frame is three months to one year and work is repetitive and semi- repetitive in nature, small scale project development and improvement in medium and large project are involved in this level.

Level 3:

Time frame is one to two years and work are semi- repetitive in nature, medium scale project development and improving completed big scale project are involved in this level.

Level 4:

Time frame is 2 to 5 years and work are semi- repetitive and research and development in nature, medium scale and large-scale project development and improvement in functional system are involved in this level.

Level 5:

Time frame is 5 to 10 years and work are research and development, large scale project and improving group of functional systems are involved in this level.

Level 6:

Time frame is 10 to 20 years and work are research and development, large scale projects, improving a value chain of the company are involved in this level.

Level 7:

Time frame is 20 to 50 years and work are research and development, large scale projects, improving multiple value chain of the company are involved in this level.

7.12 Project Management Software:

The digitalization era of project management is project management software, it is technological tool to estimation, planning, decision making, organizing and controlling of project activities used by project manager and project team.

The project management software comes with different types like personal, single user, computer software, mobile software, web based, multiple users and visual. It is helpful to maintain accuracy, control errors, less time consuming and also as evidence.

7.13 Functions of project management software:

- Cost budgeting, comparative analysis of budgeted cost with actual cost, cost control
- Project schedule estimation
- Project schedule division for each process and time management
- Project resource estimation
- Activity cost accounting
- Comparative analysis with historical data
- Project portfolio management Project Management software:

Some common project management software as follows:

- Microsoft Project
- Atlassian JIRA
- Confluence
- Wrike
- Trello
- Liquid Planner

Table-1 below depicts a number table represent or of required resource for managing the project, which is used for planning and allocating the technical staff based on schedule to the project.

Table 1: Resource allocating in general project management.

Month	1	2	3	4	5
Resource					
Designer	3	2	2	1	1
Developer	0	2	4	2	1

Tester	0	0	0	1	2
Total	3	4	6	4	4

Resource histogram is generated for the designer, developer and the tester is represented in a bar chart in figure 4.

Fig. 4: Resource allocation for managing general project

In software projects the human resource is allocated based on that company's software development process.

The above resource histogram shows a five-month small project resource allocation in general as the company follows general software development process.

Apart from these employees there will be project manager or management team and also some non-technical employees.

The following Table 2 represents resource allocation in Digital Align development project.

Table 2: Resource allocation at Digital Align for 5 months project.

Month	1	2	3	4	5
Analyst	3	0	0	0	0
Developer	0	2	3	3	1
Tester	0	0	0	1	2
Total	3	2	3	4	3

The histogram shows the 5-months resource histogram of Digital Align Private Limited based on their software development process.

- The company need Analyst as there is no project manager but there is project management team and they act as analysts.
- There is no requirement of separate designer because the developer himself act as designer and the number of requirements for designer is more but most of the companies prefer to hire a designer but when you see it from employee cost the Digital Align is doing good.
- Here the analysts are from project management team, developers and testers are from executive team but as it is seen in general resource allocation, designers, developers and testers all are from executive team only. The below depicted table-3 lists required resources.

Resource allocation histogram chart for five months project at Digital Align shown in figure 5.

Fig. 5: Resource allotment for five months project at Digital Align

Table 3: Resource utilization for one month project.

Weeks	1	2	3	4
Resource				
Analyst	1	0	0	0
Developer	0	1	1	2
Tester	0	0	0	1
Total	1	1	1	3

- The projects like small scale functioning software development like ERP software for small shops and upgradation of any research and development project.
- Research and development projects in large scale companies takes long time schedule like 10 months to two years. Table-4 below shows the statistics of resource histogram for R&D projects of 10 months, it generally requires more skilled employees and non-repetitive job.

Table 4: Project resource management for R&D software development projects

Month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Resource										
R&D	3	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Analyst	2	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Designer	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0
Developer	0	0	0	0	5	5	5	3	3	0
Tester	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	3
Total	5	5	4	3	5	5	5	4	4	3

- Here in addition to designer, developer, and tester the research and development team and analysts are also given high importance as it involves huge resource management and high employee cost.

7.14 Software Development Project Schedule Management:

The project management major objective is to manage project schedule that will be from the time of acceptance to hosting the software project by managing and completing individual activities and bringing together to complete the project with in the scheduled time period. The main two techniques apart from project management software are Project evaluation and review technique and Critical path method and these methods are mainly supported with variance analysis of project schedule and Gantt

chart and how it changes based on the software development process is given in the figure-6 below.

Month	1	2	3	4	5
Activities					
1. Analysis					
2. Design					
3. Development					
4. Testing					
5. Hosting					

Fig 6: Gantt Chart for Software Development Project Schedule of 5 Months

- The figure shows that for a five-month schedule project how a company can divide their total time in to individual activity schedules and the management team allocates minimum and maximum time that an individual activity can use that will impact on their project completion time period, PERT and CPM also depends on this schedule.
- Figure-7 below represents the Gantt chart of Software development 1-month project at Digital Align Private Limited and also this can be followed by all companies for small scale software development projects which does not involves research activity.

Month	1	2	3	4
Activities				
1. Analysis				
2. Design				
3. Development				
4. Testing				
5. Hosting				

Fig 7: Gantt Chart for Software Development Project Schedule of 5 Month

- These projects will help to fill the extra time which they were getting while developing the 5- month scheduled projects and helps to provide daily work and improve the skills of their employees.
- This type of projects generally does not require project management software support and it can manage manually as the work complexity is very less and the designing and testing work will be very less and it involves more analysis and development activity.
- There will be less work in the begging of the project schedule and increase at the end of the projectas shown in below figure-8, which should be highly monitored by the project management team.

Fig. 8: Monitoring Project Management

7.15 Testing:

- Activity 1 represents the software development project acceptance and analysis as according to the development process, from activity 1 to activity 2 it takes maximum 1 month.

- Activity 2 represents the designing process of software development process and after 1-month activity 3 begins and after 3 moth activity 4 begins and these are closely interconnected activities.
- Activity 3 represents developing stage which is done along with activity 4 and after 2 months it is ready for activity 5.
- Activity 4 represents testing stage which the quality of activity 3 is to be measured and after 1 month it is ready for activity 5.
- Activity 5 represents the hosting stage and it is the completion of software development process.
- 1 to 2= 1 month
- 2 to 3= 1 month
- 2 to 4= 3 month
- 3 to 5= 2 month
- 4 to 5= 1 month
- This will help to know critical path to complete the project shortest way and we can say that 1-2-3-5is shortest than 1-2-4-5. So, 1-2-3-5 is the critical path of this software development project. This is shown in the following table-5.

Table 5: Estimation of project duration and its relationship

Task Name	Duration in months			Relationship
	Optimistic	Most Likely	Pessimistic	
1	0.5	1	1.5	Start, 1 month
2	0.5	1	1.5	after task 1, 1 month
3	1	2	3	after task 2, 2 months
4	0.25	0.5	1	after task 3, 0.5 month
5	0.25	0.5	1	After task 4, End, 0.5 month

- Variance= ((Pessimistic Time- Optimistic Time)/6)².
- The optimistic time, most likely time and pessimistic time are derived from Gantt chart and PERT and CPM together and the task represents each stage in the software development process.
- The variance calculation mainly required for risk management in project schedule management, that is CPM will help to identify shortest way to complete the project effectively and variance help to identify the variability in project duration, by this a project manager can identify the schedule risk and take preventive measures in designing project schedule.
- The project manager estimates the optimistic time, most likely time and pessimistic time in order to manage the overall time by managing individuals time taken for a task, so that he can prevent the delay in completing the project is depicted below in table-6.

Table 6: Expected task duration and its variance

TaskName	Duration in months			Expected task duration	Variance
	Optimistic	Most Likely	Pessimistic		
1	0.5	1	1.5	1	0.029
2	0.5	1	1.5	1	0.029
3	1	2	3	2	0.11
4	0.25	0.5	1	0.5	0.016
5	0.25	0.5	1	0.5	0.016

7.16 Software Development Project Cost Management:

Cost management is one of the major objectives of software development project management and it is the major responsibility of project manager or project management team. The cost management concept

includes cost estimation and budgeting, cost control, cost reduction, pricing decision, profitability management, cost risk management, cost recording.

7.17 Methods of Software Development Project Cost Management:

- The general software development project cost budgeting in small scale and medium scale companies are made on historical cost basis, only special projects which involves more research and development activities are done through zero based cost budgeting.
- The COCOMO model or constructive cost model is developed mainly for software development project management using regression formula which requires historical cost data, it is most preferable cost budgeting model in the industry.

7.18 Estimated Cost Data for a Software Development Project:

Table-7 showing estimated cost and income records for medium scale project in a small company (5-month work with worth INR Rs. 10 Lakhs).

Table 7: Estimated cost in completing a project

Particulars	Amount in INR Lakhs
TOTAL PROJECT WORTH	10.00
(LESS) EXPENSES:	
Employee Cost	04.50
Telephone and Internet Charges	0.10
Electricity Charges	0.10
Server Charges	0.05
Maintenance Charges	0.75
Transportation Charges	0.05
Stationary Charges	0.05
System Maintenance Charges	0.25
Miscellaneous Expenses	0.25
Marketing Expenses	0.10
PROJECT INCOME	3.80

- If a small company take up a five-month work with INR Rs. 10 lakh worth project which is generally a semi-repetitive work project without any research and development activity they can make INR Rs. 3.80 lakh income excluding office maintenance expenses, interest, taxes which they can get overall 35% as net profit.
- The above data estimated on historical data of the small-scale software development company same as Digital Align Private Limited software development projects are repetitive and semi-repetitive projects.
- The biggest cost for every software development company is employee cost and high attrition rates which could maximize the overall employee cost per year, outsourcing and automation will be the solution for this problem.
- The 1-month schedule project cost and income vary based on their functions it might be only 30,000 INR Rupees if it involves only upgradation and maintenance work but also company can get up to 2.00 INR Lakhs Rupees if it is a full-fledged project involving more work.
- This type of project will help to generate more income along with medium scale projects as it requires less resources the developing cost will be less and company can earn more by taking more small projects.
- It helps the company to manage their fixed cost and for this type projects there will be time and work basis payment system which the salary payment for the employees will be on hourly basis and some companies follows commission on number of small projects they complete within a month.
- When it compared with 5-month scheduled project and research and development project it will cost very less and earn more as the company can complete more projects.

8. FINDINGS :

8.1 Methods of software development projects:

The software development project management is the key functioning area of any software development company, the management style of software development projects differs with the small scale and large-scale companies and the size of the project and target customers. The software development projects in large scale companies are generally involve huge investment, high research and development activities, long term time period and large resources and it involves more of non-repetitive jobs. The software development projects in small scale and medium scale companies involve small investments, small term time period, less resources, minimum research and development activities and it involves more repetitive jobs. All new software development projects are accepted only after doing the feasibility test which is also called as business analysis or evaluation of possibility of the performance which involves financial feasibility, resource feasibility, cost feasibility, time feasibility and market feasibility. The project management methodologies are the basis for managing the projects and the project management structure is designed on the basis of the underlying methodology.

8.2 Software development project manager:

- There is no compulsion to appoint a project manager, in small scale companies' departmental heads all together acts as project manager and works in a team but it works only because they are getting less projects or small projects compared to large scale companies, in large scale companies there should be a project manager in order to reduce the complexity in project management.
- The importance of project manager in big project management is too high that, he should manage all the functioning areas of project and he have to be connected with all key persons of the project, activities like project team management, project cost management, project schedule management, project report recording, customer requirement management, project communication management, project risk management.

8.3 Project complexity management:

- Project complexity arises due to risks in the project management like inflation or cost risk, employee risk, project completion or schedule risk, resource risk, communication risk, market, and competitor risk, these should be analyzed and managed by project manager or management team.
- Present days most of the companies uses project management software which is easy to access and includes most of all functioning areas of project management like budgeting, cost management, finance planning, schedule management, PERT, CPM, internal communication which will reduce the complexity of the project management team.

Table-8 displaying the comparative cost and income records for medium scale project in a small company (5 month schedule small project):

Table 8: Cost analysis of a small company

Particulars	Amount in INR Lakhs	Amount in INR Lakhs	Amount in INR Lakhs
TOTAL PROJECT WORTH	10.00	15.00	20.00
(LESS) EXPENSES:			
Employee Cost	4.50	4.50	4.50
Telephone and Internet Charges	0.10	0.15	0.20
Electricity Charges	0.10	0.15	0.20
Server Charges	0.05	0.05	0.05
Maintenance Charges	0.75	1.50	2.25
Transportation Charges	0.05	0.10	0.15
Stationary Charges	0.05	0.10	0.15
System Maintenance Charges	0.25	0.50	1.00
Miscellaneous Expenses	0.25	0.50	1.00
Marketing Expenses	0.10	0.20	0.30
PROJECT INCOME	3.80	7.25	14.70

- The above comparative cost-income statement shows how a small-scale software company plan to maximize their income and profitability of the business by increasing the number of project intake there by increasing the sales.
- This method will help the company to design the target and effective utilization of resources and provide the service for better price to the customer.
- The challenge is employee cost which fixed per month in order to overcome this and make huge profit the company should increase their sales and taking more projects also requires time each project should be completed within a time frame and sometimes it needs overtime work and extra payment.

9. SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION :

The company develops its business by implementing the concept of project management and project manager supported with modern project management software support, which will help the company to better result of managing time, resource, cost, performance, quality altogether a good value to the customer.

(1) Appointing a Project Manager:

- Software development companies who do not appoint a project manager will divide the samework with all departmental heads by thinking it might increase overall employee cost
- If the company can appoint a project manager who handles all process and multiple projects, the departmental heads can concentrate more on their departmental activities which will automatically increases the performance of the business and help to manage multiple projects, quality of each project, business portfolio management, better communication with all department employees and to maintain good relation with customers and to run the business in a systematical way.

(2) Utilizing the Project Management Software:

- The software development companies can utilize the project management software in order to manage the multiple projects and manage individual projects efficiently.
- Plan the activities of project in systematical way will increases the performance and quality of the work.
- Design the schedule and resources in each stage of development and record employee cost will help to time and employee management.
- Small companies can get better results even though they do not appoint project manager.

The analysis, interpretation and findings of this study convey that by adopting project management system the software development company can manage the business in an efficient and profitable manner. As the history of project management reminds that most of the industries started to implement this concept by observing the success of mega engineering projects because of the effective utilization of project management concepts.

The project management will help to finish the project within time by managing time schedule, run the business profitably by managing cost effectiveness of the project, increase the performance by maintaining good communication flow within the company and with customer and best utilization of resources to get good quality product, to manage overall internal and external risks of the project of any type of software development projects.

The large-scale software development companies care efficiently using the project management concept and it helps them to manage mega projects and multiple projects. In medium scale and small-scale software development companies all departmental heads together work as project manager but it will lead conflicts between departments and there will be less effective communication which will lead to decrease in the overall performance. In unstructured small-scale software development companies who are getting small and less projects they do not go for project management but they do only cost and time management and that will affect the quality of the product.

Hence, in the modern days, the companies want to reduce the number of employees and they also want to reduce the human efforts and human errors by adopting robotics and artificial intelligence technology. Project management software actually reduces the project manager's efforts and human errors to manage multiple projects currently large-scale companies are utilizing this technology but in medium and small-scale software companies it removes the presence of project managers where the

employees themselves utilize the technology and manage the project as they were getting less number and small projects compared to large scale companies.

REFERENCES :

- [1] Das, K., & Sagara, H. (2017). State and the IT Industry in India. *Economic & Political Weekly*, 52(41), 57-64. [Google Scholar](#)
- [2] Gökgöz, F., & Güvercin, M. T. (2018). Investigating the total factor productivity changes in the top ICT companies worldwide. *Electronic Commerce Research*, 18(4), 791-811. [Google Scholar](#)
- [3] Jiang, J. J., Klein, G., & Fernandez, W. D. (2018). From project management to program management: an invitation to investigate programs where IT plays a significant role. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 19(1), 1-9. [Google Scholar](#)
- [4] Demirkesen, S., & Ozorhon, B. (2017). Impact of integration management on construction project management performance. *International Journal of Project Management*, 35(8), 1639-1654. [Google Scholar](#)
- [5] Taks, Marijke, Kesenne, Stefan, Chalip, Laurence, & Green, B. Christine. (2011). Economic Impact Analysis versus Cost Benefit Analysis: The Case of a Medium-Sized Sport Event. *International Journal of Sport Finance*, 6(3), 187-203. [Google Scholar](#)
- [6] Hochdörffer, J., Buergin, J., Vlachou, E., Zogopoulos, V., Lanza, G., & Mourtzis, D. (2018). Holistic approach for integrating customers in the design, planning, and control of global production networks. *CIRP Journal of Manufacturing Science and Technology*, 23(1), 98-107. [Google Scholar](#)
- [7] Gonovski, V. (2017). Risk Management in Project Management–Basics. *Knowledge International Journal*, 16(3), 995-1000. [Google Scholar](#)
- [8] Cotterell, M., & Hughes, B. (1995). Software project management, *International Thomson Computer Press*. 1-293. [Google Scholar](#)
- [9] Aanbari, F. T., & Young Hoon Kwak, P. F. T. A. (2008). Impact on Project Management of Allied Disciplines: *Trends and Future of Project Management Practices and Research*, 5(2), 324-331. [Google Scholar](#)
- [10] Almaamari, G., Williams, N., & Atkinson, R. (2017). Stakeholders' trust and power dynamic in tourism resort projects in a developing country, *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, 8(4), 77-89. [Google Scholar](#)
- [11] Korte, R., Smith, K. A., & Li, C. Q. (2018). The Role of Empathy in Entrepreneurship: A Core Competency of the Entrepreneurial Mindset. *Advances in Engineering Education*, 7(1), 1-7. [Google Scholar](#)
- [12] Sanz-Llopis, J., & Ostermann, M. (2020). Innovation in project management through framing and challenge redefinition. *International journal of managing projects in business*, 5(1), 234-239. [Google Scholar](#)
- [13] Petersen, K. W. (2020). Project Management Office Performance Variables that Influence Project Success: A Correlational Study, *Dissertation of Capella University*, 121-135. [Google Scholar](#)
- [14] Arashpour, M., Abbasi, B., Arashpour, M., Hosseini, M. R., & Yang, R. (2017). Integrated management of on-site, coordination and off-site uncertainty: Theorizing risk analysis within a hybrid project setting. *International Journal of Project Management*, 35(4), 647-655. [Google Scholar](#)
- [15] Korte, R., Smith, K. A., & Li, C. Q. (2018). The Role of Empathy in Entrepreneurship: A Core Competency of the Entrepreneurial Mindset. *Advances in Engineering Education*, 7(1), 1-12. [Google Scholar](#)
- [16] Holla, R. (2017). A Study on SWOC Analysis of Reliance Jio. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 2(1), 42-47. [Google Scholar](#)

- [17] Aithal, P. S., & Kumar, P. M. (2015). Applying SWOC analysis to an institution of higher education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 5(7), 231-247. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [18] Vijayakumar, S., & Nethravathi, P. S. (2021). The Mega Conglomerate of India-Success Story of Growth of Reliance Industries: A Case Study. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 5(1), 143-154. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [19] Puneeth, B. R., & Nethravathi, P. S. (2021). Paytm's Journey towards Digital Payment in India—A Case Study. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 5(2), 125-141. [Google Scholar↗](#)

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

Australian Government

IP Australia

CERTIFICATE OF GRANT INNOVATION PATENT

Patent number: 2021103335

The Commissioner of Patents has granted the above patent on 16 March 2022, and certifies that the below particulars have been registered in the Register of Patents.

Name and address of patentee(s):

Nethravathi P. S. of Professor, College of Computer & Information Science Srinivas University, Mangalore Karnataka 575001 India

P. S. Aithal of Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University Mangalore Karnataka 575001 India

Suhan Mendon of Associate Professor, Manipal Institute of Management Manipal Academy of Higher Education Manipal, Karnataka 576104 India

Ananth Prabhu G. of Professor, Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering Sahyadri College of Engg. & Management Mangalore, Karnataka 575007 India

Anush Bekal of Associate Professor, Dept of Electronics & Comm. Engineering Sahyadri College of Engg. and Management Mangalore, Karnataka 575007 India

Taramol K. G. of Assistant Professor, School of Business, Manipal Academy of Higher Education Dubai 345050 United Arab Emirates

Soofi Anwar of Director Academics, University of Stirling RAK 41222 United Arab Emirates

Ganga Bhavani of Assistant Professor, Amity University Dubai Dubai International Academic City (DIAC) Dubai 345019 United Arab Emirates

Bhawana Rudra of Assistant Professor, Flat no:101, S.M.R Sterling, Bapuji Nagar, Bowenpally Secunderabad Telangana 500011 India

Sonia V. Soans of Lecturer, Information Technology, University of Tech. & Applied Sciences Muscat 611 Oman

Harish Neermarga of CEO, Accolade Tech Solutions Mangalore Karnataka 575001 India

Title of invention:

SYSTEM FOR PRODUCTIVITY DETERMINATION USING MACHINE LEARNING BASED FACE RECOGNITION

Name of inventor(s):

P. S., Nethravathi; Aithal, P. S.; Mendon, Suhan; G., Ananth Prabhu; Bekal, Anush; K. G., Taramol; Anwar, Soofi; Bhavani, Ganga; Rudra, Bhawana; Soans, Sonia V. and Neermarga, Harish

Term of Patent:

Eight years from 14 June 2021

NOTE: This Innovation Patent cannot be enforced unless and until it has been examined by the Commissioner of Patents and a Certificate of Examination has been issued. See sections 120(1A) and 129A of the Patents Act 1990, set out on the reverse of this document.

Dated this 16th day of March 2022

Commissioner of Patents

PATENTS ACT 1990

The Australian Patents Register is the official record and should be referred to for the full details pertaining to this IP Right.

Australian Government
IP Australia

CERTIFICATE OF GRANT
INNOVATION PATENT

Patent number: 2021103335

Dated this 16th day of March 2022

Commissioner of Patents

PATENTS ACT 1990

The Australian Patents Register is the official record and should be referred to for the full details pertaining to this IP Right.

**SYSTEM FOR PRODUCTIVITY DETERMINATION USING
MACHINE LEARNING BASED FACE RECOGNITION**

ABSTRACT

The present invention is related to a system for productivity determination using machine learning based face recognition. The objective of present invention is to solve the anomalies presented in the prior art techniques related to employee; productivity analysis using advance face recognition technologies.

SYSTEM FOR PRODUCTIVITY DETERMINATION USING MACHINE LEARNING BASED FACE RECOGNITION

FIELD OF INVENTION

- [001]. The present invention relates to the technical field of biometric and machine learning.
- [002]. The present invention related to the technical field of emotion
- [003]. More particularly, the present invention is related to a system for productivity determination using machine learning based face recognition.

BACKGROUND & PRIOR ART

- [004]. Face recognition technology is currently a hot spot in biometric technology. It has important applications in security, attendance, and robot applications. It is recognized as the least intrusive and most convenient biometric technology. In view of this, the purpose of the present invention is to provide a face recognition method and system, which can improve the face recognition rate under the condition that the illumination changes greatly and the face posture is random.
- [005]. Facial emotion recognition (FER) is a major concern in the fields of computer vision and artificial intelligence owing to its significant academic and commercial potential.
- [006]. Some of the prior work is listed herewith:
- [007]. CN108764047A Group emotion behavior analysis method and apparatus, electronic device, medium and product Embodiments of the invention disclose a group emotion behavior analysis method and apparatus, an electronic device, a medium and a product. The method comprises the steps of carrying out image acquisition on a group comprising at least one person to obtain at least one group image; executing human face recognition on the at least one group image to obtain at least one human face image, and/or executing human body recognition on the at least one group image to obtain at least one human body image.

[008]. CN109472212A An emotion analysis check-in interaction system based on human face recognition The invention discloses an emotion analysis check-in interaction system based on human face recognition, the invention can achieve the purpose of check-in by the way of face recognition or the combination of fingerprint and face recognition, avoiding the problem of inaccurate check-in information in common check-in mode, Moreover, since the check-in method of face recognition can collect the image information of the sign-in person, so that the emotion analysis module can analyze the mood of the sign-in personnel on the day according to the image, and then sends the motivator's discourse through the motivating interaction module, Emotions, songs, or music to the check-in person's cell phone, encourage and encourage the sign-in personnel, When it is used in the company, it is helpful for the manager to analyze the character of the employee, so as to arrange the working tasks more reasonably. In addition, it is also helpful for the manager to grasp the working state of the employee in real time.

[009]. CN107833018A Face recognition technology-based enterprise management system The present invention discloses a face recognition technology-based enterprise management system which relates to the enterprise management technology field, and comprises a work attendance management sub-system, an employee motivation sub-system and a warehouse management sub-system. The attendance management sub-system can check on the work attendance of the employees automatically, thereby improving the work attendance management efficiency. The employee motivation sub-system recognizes the face expressions of the employees to reflect the emotion states of the employees and carry out the psychological motivation on the employees, thereby improving the working enthusiasms. The warehouse management sub-system can effectively avoid the people without fixed duties entering a warehouse to steal the public goods and materials, thereby saving the enterprise cost. The face recognition technology-based enterprise management system fully utilizes the face image data of the employees, and enables the enterprise management efficiency to be improved effectively.

[0010]. CN112382051A Smart residence security system based on block chain The invention discloses a smart residence security system based on a block chain, and

the system is characterized in that the system comprises a sound positioning module which is used for judging whether there is an abnormal sound or not, and achieving the positioning of the abnormal sound; a face recognition module used for recognizing a face and judging whether the face is a house owner or not; a police emotion sensing module used for monitoring whether a dangerous case occurs in the house; a networking alarm module used for sending alarm information to residents and security personnel when an alarm situation occurs, and providing abnormal position information; a block chain database used for storing face information of residents and workers in a community; and a sound positioning module which comprises a microphone array module, a sound acquisition module, a sound preprocessing module and an abnormal sound positioning module. The residence security system is more stable in operation and safer in operation.

[0011]. AU2020103514A4 IFER- Student Behavior Identification: INTELLIGENT STUDENT BEHAVIOUR IDENTIFICATION USING FER ABSTRACT Our Invention\ " IFER- Student Behavior Identification\ " is a human Face expression Recognition is one of the most powerful and challenging tasks in the world. The social communication. Generally, face expressions are natural and direct means for human Beings to communicate their emotions and intentions. Face expressions are the key Characteristics of non-verbal communication and this describes the survey of Face Expression Recognition (FER) techniques which include the three major stages such as Pre-processing, feature extraction and classification. The invented technology also includes the survey explains the various types of FER techniques with its major contributions. The performance of various FER techniques Is compared based on the number of expressions recognized and complexity of algorithms. The IFER- student behavior identification is a method for teaching social behavior to students comprises the steps of identifying rules of conduct, establishing positive consequences for obeying the rules of conduct and establishing negative consequences for disobeying the rules of conduct, teaching the students the rules of conduct.

[0012]. US20190311188A1 Face emotion recognition method based on dual-stream convolutional neural network A face emotion recognition method based on dual-

stream convolutional neural network uses a multi-scale face expression recognition network to single frame face images and face sequences to perform learning classification. The method includes constructing a multi-scale face expression recognition network which includes a channel network with a resolution of 224×224 and a channel network with a resolution of 336×336 , extracting facial expression characteristics at different resolutions through the recognition network, effectively combining static characteristics of images and dynamic characteristics of expression sequence to perform training and learning, fusing the two channel models, testing and obtaining a classification effect of facial expressions. The present invention fully utilizes the advantages of deep learning, effectively avoids the problems of manual extraction of feature deviations and long time, and makes the method provided by the present invention more adaptable. Moreover, the present invention improves the accuracy and productivity of expression recognition.

[0013]. US11010600B2 Face emotion recognition method based on dual-stream convolutional neural network A face emotion recognition method based on dual-stream convolutional neural network uses a multi-scale face expression recognition network to single frame face images and face sequences to perform learning classification. The method includes constructing a multi-scale face expression recognition network which includes a channel network with a resolution of 224×224 and a channel network with a resolution of 336×336 , extracting facial expression characteristics at different resolutions through the recognition network, effectively combining static characteristics of images and dynamic characteristics of expression sequence to perform training and learning, fusing the two channel models, testing and obtaining a classification effect of facial expressions. The present invention fully utilizes the advantages of deep learning, effectively avoids the problems of manual extraction of feature deviations and long time, and makes the method provided by the present invention more adaptable. Moreover, the present invention improves the accuracy and productivity of expression recognition.

[0014]. CN109558535A Personalized article pushing method and system based on face

recognition The invention provides a personalized article pushing method and system based on face recognition, and the method comprises the steps of obtaining a face image in a video image, recognizing the face image, and building a user file according to a recognition result; analyzing the face image based on the demographic information to obtain user attribute information, and storing the user attribute information to a user file; calculating similarity among the users, performing clustering analysis on the user archives to extract behavior characteristics of the users, and converting the behavior characteristics of the users to generate a neighbor set related to the users; and generating a user feature vector by combining the neighbor set and the user attribute information, and constructing a feature matrix between the user feature vector and the article from the article set to form an initial pushing result of the article.

[0015]. CN207960434U Safety device of family based on people's face facial expression recognition and behavior analysis The utility model relates to a safety device of family based on people's face facial expression recognition and behavior analysis. It including install stealthy anti -theft net on the balcony, slip driving mechanism and with slip driving mechanism signal connection's processing controls ware, still including be used for gathering and people's face facial expression recognition device of analyst's the expression information of face with be used for gathering and the behavior analysis device of analyst's action information, this people's face facial expression recognition device and behavior analysis device all with processing controls ware signal connection. The utility model discloses combine people's face facial expression recognition device and behavior analysis device on using the basis of stealthy anti -theft net, possess the advantage of stealthy anti -theft net outside, obtain assay people's emotional state with the expression of the face through the monitoring people with action through people's face facial expression recognition device.

[0016]. CN112370037A Safe driving method and system based on emotion recognition The invention relates to the technical field of intelligent aided driving, and provides a safe driving method and system based on emotion recognition. A master control module, an image acquisition module, a vehicle state collection module, a heart

rate collection device, a voice module and a vehicle braking module are taken as components to establish a safe driving mechanism, wherein the image acquisition module, the vehicle state collection module, the heart rate collection device, the voice module and the vehicle braking module are connected with the master control module; the personality information of a driver is collected in advance to obtain a personality value, the heart rate and the face image of the driver are collected in real time, a corresponding heart rate change rate is obtained through calculation, and the emotion of the driver is determined through face expression recognition; through multi-pronged approaches, accuracy for driver emotion recognition can be improved, and before the driver emits a dangerous driving behavior, a voice prompt is given to pacify the emotion of the driver.

[0017]. CN109558535B Method and system for individually pushing articles based on face recognition. The invention provides a personalized article pushing method and system based on face recognition, and the method comprises the steps of obtaining a face image in a video image, recognizing the face image, and building a user file according to a recognition result; analyzing the face image based on the demographic information to obtain user attribute information, and storing the user attribute information to a user file; calculating similarity among the users, performing clustering analysis on the user archives to extract behavior characteristics of the users, and converting the behavior characteristics of the users to generate a neighbor set related to the users; and generating a user feature vector by combining the neighbor set and the user attribute information, and constructing a feature matrix between the user feature vector and the article from the article set to form an initial pushing result of the article. According to the present invention, the data information, such as the gender, the age and the emotion of the user and the like is obtained by analyzing the face image of the user,

[0018]. US8873813B2 Application of Z-webs and Z-factors to analytics, search engine, learning, recognition, natural language, and other utilities Here, we introduce Z-webs, including Z-factors and Z-nodes, for the understanding of relationships between objects, subjects, abstract ideas, concepts, or the like, including face, car, images, people, emotions, mood, text, natural language, voice, music, video,

locations, formulas, facts, historical data, landmarks, personalities, ownership, family, friends, love, happiness, social behavior, voting behavior, and the like, to be used for many applications in our life, including on the search engine, analytics, Big Data processing, natural language processing, economy forecasting, face recognition, dealing with reliability and certainty, medical diagnosis, pattern recognition, object recognition, biometrics, security analysis, risk analysis, fraud detection, satellite image analysis, machine generated data analysis, machine learning, training samples, extracting data or patterns (from the video, images, and the like), editing video or images, and the like. Z-factors include reliability factor, confidence factor, expertise factor, bias factor, and the like, which is associated with each Z-node in the Z-web.

[0019].

[0020]. Groupings of alternative elements or embodiments of the invention disclosed herein are not to be construed as limitations. Each group member can be referred to and claimed individually or in any combination with other members of the group or other elements found herein. One or more members of a group can be included in, or deleted from, a group for reasons of convenience and/or patentability. When any such inclusion or deletion occurs, the specification is herein deemed to contain the group as modified thus fulfilling the written description of all Markush groups used in the appended claims.

[0021]. As used in the description herein and throughout the claims that follow, the meaning of “a,” “an,” and “the” includes plural reference unless the context clearly dictates otherwise. Also, as used in the description here in, the meaning of “in” and “on” unless the context clearly dictates otherwise.

[0022]. The recitation of ranges of values herein is merely intended to serve as a shorthand method of referring individually to each separate value falling within the range. Unless otherwise indicated herein, each individual value is incorporated into the specification as if it were individually recited herein. All methods described herein can be performed in any suitable order unless otherwise indicated herein or

otherwise clearly contradicted by context.

[0023]. The use of any and all examples, or exemplary language (e.g. “such as”) provided with respect to certain embodiments herein is intended merely to better illuminate the invention and does not pose a limitation on the scope of the invention otherwise claimed. No language in the specification should be construed as indicating any non-claimed element essential to the practice of the invention.

[0024]. The above information disclosed in this Background section is only for enhancement of understanding of the background of the invention and therefore it may contain information that does not form the prior art that is already known in this country to a person of ordinary skill in the art.

SUMMARY

[0025]. The present invention mainly cures and solves the technical problems existing in the prior art. In response to these problems, the present invention provides a system for productivity determination using machine learning based face recognition.

[0026]. The present invention discloses a system for productivity determination using machine learning based face recognition, wherein the system comprises at least one computing device and at least one camera, wherein the computing device processes the information received from the camera through a computer implemented method wherein the computer implemented method of recording emotional stability of a worker is characterized by:

[0027]. starting the method with worker information data; Activating an emotional stability unit on a mobile computing device with worker information data to open the application; Determining the navigation information by a navigation unit; activating the camera unit; Determining the face image;

[0028]. Activating the face scanner unit; Determining the face recognition; matching the information through machine learning based matching unit and marking the emotional stability on a successful match and ending the method; wherein: on failing

to detect availability of worker information data after starting;

[0029]. logging into emotional stability unit on a mobile computing device with Wireless communication; Determining the Navigation information by navigation unit; Activating the camera unit; Determining the face image; activating the face scanner unit;

[0030]. Determining the face recognition & transferring the data through local wireless communication unit and perform mothering the information through machine learning based computing unit and marking the emotional stability on successful match and ending the method.

OBJECTIVE OF THE INVENTION

[0031]. The principle objective of the present invention is to provide a system for productivity determination using machine learning based face recognition.

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF DRAWINGS

[0032]. Further clarify various aspects of some example embodiments of the present invention, a more particular description of the invention will be rendered by reference to specific embodiments thereof which are illustrated in the appended drawings. It is appreciated that these drawings depict only illustrated embodiments of the invention and are therefore not to be considered limiting of its scope. The invention will be described and explained with additional specificity and detail through the use of the accompanying drawings.

[0033]. In order that the advantages of the present invention will be easily understood, a detailed description of the invention is discussed below in conjunction with the appended drawings, which, however, should not be considered to limit the scope of the invention to the accompanying drawings, in which:

[0034]. Figure 1 shows an exemplary representation of a system for productivity determination using machine learning based face recognition, according to the present invention.

DETAILS DESCRIPTION

[0035]. The present invention discloses a system for productivity determination using machine learning based face recognition.

[0036]. Figure 1 shows the exemplary representation of a system for productivity determination using machine learning based face recognition, according to the present invention.

[0037]. Although the present disclosure has been described with the purpose of to a system for productivity determination using machine learning based face recognition, it should be appreciated that the same has been done merely to illustrate the invention in an exemplary manner and to highlight any other purpose or function for which explained structures or configurations could be used and is covered within the scope of the present disclosure.

[0038]. The present invention discloses a system for productivity determination using machine learning based face recognition, wherein system comprises at least one computing device and at least one camera, wherein the computing device process the information received from the camera through a computer implemented method wherein computer implemented method of recording emotional stability of a worker characterized by:

[0039]. starting the method with worker information data; Activating on emotional stability unit on a mobile computing device with worker information data to open the application; Determining the Navigation information by navigation unit; activating the camera unit; Determining the face image;

[0040]. Activating the face scanner unit; Determining the face recognition; mothering the information through machine learning based mothering unit and marking the emotional stability on successful match and ending the method; wherein: on failing to detect availability of worker information data after starting;

[0041]. logging into emotional stability unit on a mobile computing device with Wireless

communication; Determining the Navigation information by navigation unit; Activating the camera unit; Determining the face image; activating the face scanner unit;

[0042]. Determining the face recognition & transferring the data through local wireless communication unit and perform mothering the information through machine learning based computing unit and marking the emotional stability on successful match and ending the method.

[0043]. The figures and the foregoing description give examples of embodiments. Those skilled in the art will appreciate that one or more of the described elements may well be combined into a single functional element. Alternatively, certain elements may be split into multiple functional elements. Elements from one embodiment may be added to another embodiment. For example, order of processes described herein may be changed and are not limited to the manner described herein. Moreover, the actions of any block diagram need not be implemented in the order shown; nor do all of the acts need to be necessarily performed. Also, those acts that are not dependent on other acts may be performed in parallel with the other acts. The scope of embodiments is by no means limited by these specific examples.

[0044]. Although implementations of the invention have been described in a language specific to structural features and/or methods, it is to be understood that the appended claims are not necessarily limited to the specific features or methods described. Rather, the specific features and methods are disclosed as examples of implementations of the invention.

DRAWINGS

FIGURE 1

Urkunde

über die Eintragung des
Gebrauchsmusters Nr. 20 2021 106 820

Bezeichnung:

Verbesserung der Mitarbeiterbindung und des Feedbacksystems in der
Industrie durch maschinelles Lernen

IPC:

G06Q 10/06

Inhaber/inhaberin:

Hawaladar, Iqbal Thonse, Manama, BH
Mendon, Suhan, Dr., Mangalore, Karnataka, IN
Sathyanarayana, Nethravathi Periyapattana, Dr., Mangalore, Karnataka, IN

Tag der Anmeldung:

15.12.2021

Tag der Eintragung:

05.01.2022

Die Präsidentin des Deutschen Patent- und Markenamts

Cornelia Rudloff-Schäffer

München, 05.01.2022

Die Voraussetzungen der Schutzfähigkeit werden bei der Eintragung eines Gebrauchsmusters nicht geprüft.
Den aktuellen Rechtsstand und Schutzzumfang entnehmen Sie bitte dem DPMAregister unter www.dpma.de.

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

Diese Darstellung dient der visuellen Prüfung der Inhalte einer XML-Datei, das Layout ist nicht verbindlich. Das verbindliche Original ist die XML-Datei.
Der Antrag kann nicht über Fax oder Post eingereicht werden.

**Deutsches
Patent- und Markenamt**

DPMAdirekt G6053 e Seite 1

An das
Deutsches Patent- und Markenamt
80297 München

<p>(1) Sendungen des Deutschen Patent- und Markenamts sind zu richten an:</p> <p>Name, Vorname / Firma <input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="Hohendorf Kierdorf Patentanwälte PartGmbB"/> <input style="width: 90%;" type="text"/> <input style="width: 90%;" type="text"/></p> <p>Straße, Hausnummer / ggf. Postfach <input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="Hohenzollererring 79-83"/></p> <p>Postleitzahl Ort <input style="width: 20%;" type="text" value="50672"/> <input style="width: 70%;" type="text" value="Köln, DE"/></p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Elektronisches Postfach</p>	Antrag auf Eintragung eines Gebrauchsmusters	2
<p>Datum <input style="width: 20px;" type="text" value="14"/> <input style="width: 20px;" type="text" value="12"/> <input style="width: 20px;" type="text" value="2021"/></p>		
<p>(2) Zeichen des Anmelders/Vertreters (max. 20 Stellen) <input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="G11235DE"/></p> <p>Telefon des Anmelders/Vertreters <input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="+49 221 42357744"/></p>		
<p>(3) Der Empfänger in Feld (1) ist der</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Anmelder <input type="checkbox"/> Zustellungsbevollmächtigte <input type="checkbox"/> Vertreter </p> <p style="text-align: right; font-size: small;">ggf. Nr. der Allgemeinen Vollmacht <input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/></p>		
<p>(4) Anmelder (1) <small>nur auszufüllen, wenn abweichend von Feld (1) Handelsregisternummer nur bei Firmen anzugeben</small></p> <p>Name, Vorname / Firma lt. Handelsregister <input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="Hawaladar, Iqbal Thonse"/></p> <p><input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="Professor, Department of Accounting & Finance"/></p> <p><input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="College of Business Administration, Kingdom University, Bahrain"/></p> <p>Straße, Hausnummer (kein Postfach) <input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="Flat 15, Building 18, Road 801, Block 308, Gudaibiya"/></p> <p>Postleitzahl Ort Land <input style="width: 20%;" type="text" value="122001"/> <input style="width: 50%;" type="text" value="Manama"/> <input style="width: 30%;" type="text" value="BH"/></p> <p>Telefon Fax E-Mail <input style="width: 30%;" type="text"/> <input style="width: 30%;" type="text"/> <input style="width: 40%;" type="text"/></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Der Anmelder ist eingetragen im Handelsregister Nr. <input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/> beim Amtsgericht <input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/></p>		
<p>Anmelder (2)</p> <p>Name, Vorname / Firma lt. Handelsregister <input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="Dr. Mendon, Suhan"/></p> <p><input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="Associate Professor, Manipal institute of Management"/></p> <p><input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="Manipal Academy of Higher Education(MAHE)"/></p> <p>Straße, Hausnummer (kein Postfach) <input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="House no. 5-10-1013/2 , Near Alake Bridge, Kudroll"/></p> <p>Postleitzahl Ort Land <input style="width: 20%;" type="text" value="575003"/> <input style="width: 50%;" type="text" value="Mangalore, Karnataka"/> <input style="width: 30%;" type="text" value="IN"/></p> <p>Telefon Fax E-Mail <input style="width: 30%;" type="text"/> <input style="width: 30%;" type="text"/> <input style="width: 40%;" type="text"/></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Der Anmelder ist eingetragen im Handelsregister Nr. <input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/> beim Amtsgericht <input style="width: 100%;" type="text"/></p>		
<p>Anmelder (3)</p> <p>Name, Vorname / Firma lt. Handelsregister <input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="Dr. Sathyanarayana, Nethravathi Periyapattana"/></p> <p><input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="Professor , Department of Computer & Information Science"/></p>		

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

Diese Darstellung dient der visuellen Prüfung der Inhalte einer XML-Datei, das Layout ist nicht verbindlich. Das verbindliche Original ist die XML-Datei.
Informationen zum Schutz des Erfinders (unverbindlich)

DPMA Direkt G6003 e Seite 2

College of Computer & Information Sciences, Birla Institute of Technology
 Straße, Hausnummer (kein Postfach) Sreepada, 4-197/12, Kalyana Nagar, Marakada

Postleitzahl 575015 Ort Mangalore, Karnataka Land IN

Telefon _____ Fax _____ E-Mail _____

Der Anmelder ist eingetragen im Handelsregister Nr. _____ beim Amtsgericht _____

Vertreter (1)
 Name, Vorname / Firma Hohendorf Kierdorf Patentanwälte PartGmbB

Straße, Hausnummer / ggf. Postfach Hohenzollernring 79-83

Postleitzahl 50672 Ort Köln Land DE

Telefon +49 221 42357744 Fax +49 221 42357745 E-Mail office@hohendorf-kierdorf.com

(6) soweit bekannt Anmelder-Nr. _____ Vertreter-Nr. _____
 Zustelladressen-Nr. 108972623

(6) Vorschlag ist unbedingt anzugeben, sofern bekannt
Bezeichnung der Erfindung _____
IPC-Vorschlag des Anmelders
 VERBESSERUNG DER MITARBEITERBINDUNG UND DES FEEDBACKSYSTEMS IN DER INDUSTRIE DURCH MASCHINELLES LERNEN

(7) **Sonstige Anträge**
 Aussetzung der Eintragung und Bekanntmachung auf __ Monate (Max. 15 Mon. ab Anmelde- oder Prioritätstag)
 Rechercheantrag - Ermittlung der öffentlichen Druckschriften (§ 7 Gebrauchsmustergesetz)

(8) **Erklärungen** Aktenzeichen Anmelde tag
 Teilung/Ausscheidung aus der Gebrauchsmusteranmeldung
 Abzweigung aus der Patentanmeldung/dem Patent
 Der Anmelder ist an **Lizenzvergabe** interessiert (unverbindlich)

(9) Inländische Priorität (Datum, Aktenzeichen der Voranmeldung) _____
 Ausländische Priorität (Datum, Land, Aktenz. der Voranmeldung) _____
 Ausstellungspriorität (Datum der erstmaligen Zurschaustellung, Ausstellung) _____

(10) **Gebühreuzahlung** in Höhe von 30,00 EUR
 SEPA-Mandatsverwendung elektr. Formular ist beigelegt. Überweisung (nach Erhalt der Empfangsbescheinigung)
Wird die Anmeldegebühr nicht innerhalb 3 Monaten nach dem Tag des Eingangs der Anmeldung gezahlt, so gilt die Anmeldung als zurückgenommen!

(11) **Anlagen**
 1. 14 Seite(n) Beschreibung
 2. 2 Seite(n) Schutzansprüche
5 Anzahl Schutzansprüche

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

Diese Darstellung dient der visuellen Prüfung der Inhalte einer XML-Datei, das Layout ist nicht verbindlich. Das verbindliche Original ist die XML-Datei.
Der Antrag kann nicht über Fax oder Post eingereicht werden.

	3. <input type="text"/> Anzahl Figuren	DPMAdirekt G6003 e Seite 3
	4. <input type="text"/> Abschrift(e) der Voranmeldung(en) bei Priorität	
	5. <input type="text"/> Abschrift der Voranmeldung bei Abzweigung	
	6. <input type="text"/> Vertretervollmacht	
	7. <input type="text"/> Übersetzung(en)	
	8. <input type="text"/> Sonstiges	
G6003e 1.08		Bearbeiter (1) <input type="text"/> Unterschrift <input type="text"/> Funktion des Bearbeiters

ADVANCE EMPLOYEE RETENTION AND FEEDBACK SYSTEM IN INDUSTRY USING MACHINE LEARNING

FIELD OF INVENTION

The present invention relates to the field of relates to a computer implemented system of identifying, retaining and motivating employees through a management and reward system.

More particularly, the present invention is related to advance employee retention and feedback system in industry using machine learning.

BACKGROUND OF THE INVENTION

The subject matter discussed in the background section should not be assumed to be prior art merely as a result of its mention in the background section. Similarly, a problem mentioned in the background section or associated with the subject matter of the background section should not be assumed to have been previously recognized in the prior art. The subject matter in the background section merely represents different approaches, which in-and-of-themselves may also be inventions.

Some of the prior work listed herewith:

IN202141028831A STUDY OF EMPLOYEE RETENTION STRATEGIES IN IT INDUSTRY - RANKING OF EMPLOYEE RETENTION STRATEGIES BASED ON DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES GENDER, AGE AND EXPERIENCE AT PRESENT ORGANIZATION Employee retention plays an important role in an organization because it affects employee performance. The purpose of this study is to examine the effect of employee retention strategies namely employee reward programs, flexible working environment, timely promotions, career developmental programs, better compensation and performance-based bonus on employee retention and employee performance. The study results revealed that employee retention strategies have positive effect on employee retention as well as employee performance. The study would also helpful for researchers and academicians to understand

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

the role of employee retention in an organization. The major purpose of this study is to identify and analyze the major determinant strategies that affect employee retention. This research closely looked at the following broad strategies: Job Security and Good working environment, Better Compensation System, Effective Training and developmental Programmed, Rewards and Recognition, Employees Participation in management activities, Welfare measures, Promotion opportunities, Challenging Work assignments, Scope for Career growth and development, Fair evaluation system. A total of 615 self-administrative questionnaires data is received and the data was analyzed with the help of SPSS_v20 software. The results demonstrated that employee retention strategies have a significant role in employee retention as well as outstanding enterprise performance. The outcomes of this study will help organizations understand the importance of employee retention strategies in achieving superior organizational overall performance and in retaining competent employees.

US20110282662CUSTOMER SERVICE DATA RECORDING DEVICE, CUSTOMER SERVICE DATA RECORDING METHOD, AND RECORDING MEDIUM To enable determining the correlation between customer satisfaction and employee satisfaction, a speech acquisition unit 102 acquires conversations between employees and customers; an emotion recognition unit 155 recognizes employee and customer emotions based on employee and customer speech in the conversation; a satisfaction calculator 156, 157 calculates employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction based on the emotion recognition output from the emotion recognition unit 155; and a customer service data recording unit 159 relates and records employee satisfaction data denoting employee satisfaction and customer satisfaction data denoting customer satisfaction as customer service data in a management server database DB.

CA2666264ATTRITION WARNING AND CONTROL SYSTEM An attrition warning and control system informs an employer as to the risk of attrition for an employee. The employee is assigned a discrete attrition category. The discrete attrition category is determined from an employee satisfaction behavior. The employee satisfaction behavior may be categorized according to its behavior type. Portal logic executed by the attrition warning and control system generates employee team attrition risk reports for employee teams. The portal logic also builds project team attrition risk reports from the employee team attrition risk reports. Reporting logic executed by the attrition warning and control system delivers the discrete attrition category, employee satisfaction behavior, the employee team attrition risk reports, and the project team attrition risk reports through an authorized connection via a

communication interface.

IN202141023567A NOVEL SYSTEM FOR CONTROLLING EMPLOYEES' ATTRITION RATE Title of Invention: A Novel System for Controlling Employees Attrition Rate Field of Invention: Management using Computer Application ABSTRACT An attrition alarm and control system warns an employer when an employee is about to leave. The employee is assigned to a specific turnover group. The discrete turnover group is determined by employee satisfaction activities. Employee satisfaction behavior can be characterized according to its type. Portal logic run by the attrition alarm and control system generates employee team attrition risk reports. The gateway logic generates project team attrition risk reports from employee team attrition risk reports. The attrition alert and control system's reporting logic send separate attrition group, employee satisfaction behavior, employee team attrition risk reports, and project team attrition risk reports over an approved link over a communication interface.

AU2009202262ATTRITION WARNING AND CONTROL SYSTEM An attrition warning and control system informs an employer as to the risk of attrition for an employee. The employee is assigned a discrete attrition category. The discrete attrition category is determined from an employee satisfaction behavior. The employee satisfaction behavior may be categorized according to its behavior type. Portal logic executed by the attrition warning and control system generates employee team attrition risk reports for employee teams. The portal logic also builds project team attrition risk reports from the employee team attrition risk reports. Reporting logic executed by the attrition warning and control system delivers the discrete attrition category, employee satisfaction behavior, the employee team attrition risk reports, and the project team attrition risk reports through an authorized connection via a communication interface. 06/06/09,cI.17%9.specification as filed.6-jie-09,2

US20020120494METHOD AND SYSTEM FOR GATHERING EMPLOYEE FEEDBACK A computer implemented method for collecting employee feedback, wherein the method includes the steps of: identifying a plurality of categories related to the work conditions at an employer, gathering employee feedback, organizing the employee feedback by the categories into a rating report, and allowing employers and other entities access to the rating report.

US0090307025ATTRITION WARNING AND CONTROL SYSTEM An attrition warning and control system informs an employer as to the risk of attrition for an employee. The employee is assigned a discrete attrition category. The discrete attrition category is determined

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

from an employee satisfaction behavior. The employee satisfaction behavior may be categorized according to its behavior type. Portal logic executed by the attrition warning and control system generates employee team attrition risk reports for employee teams. The portal logic also builds project team attrition risk reports from the employee team attrition risk reports. Reporting logic executed by the attrition warning and control system delivers the discrete attrition category, employee satisfaction behavior, the employee team attrition risk reports, and the project team attrition risk reports through an authorized connection via a communication interface.

IN201941038236SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR DEVELOPMENT OF A WORKFORCE PLANNING MODEL TO IDENTIFY EMPLOYEE RETENTION A system for development of a workforce planning model to identify employee retention is disclosed. The system includes a workforce data collection subsystem configured to collect demographics data associated with at least one employee of an organization from a survey process; a workforce planning model generation subsystem to identify a plurality of employee retention factors corresponding to the at least one employee in the organization based on collected demographics data, to analyse a plurality of determined employee retention factors using a univariate statistical analysis technique and a multivariate structural equation modelling (SEM) technique; to compute an unstandardized regression weight (URW) value, a standardized regression weight (SRW) value, a standard error (SE) value, a t-value and a R2 value for a plurality of analyzed employee retention factors and to generate the workforce planning model to identify the retention of the at least one employee in the organization. 1

US20040049413APPARATUS, METHOD, AND COMPUTER PROGRAM FOR RESERVATION OF ACCOMMODATION A feedback collecting section obtains from an employee feedback on a hotel based on his or her previous personal experience about the hotel, a favorites processing section provides information relating to the employee's favorite hotels, a recommendation processing section provides information relating to recommended hotels selected based on the employee feedback, and a room availability inquiring section provides a list of available rooms that is created by a travel agent website by adding to it the employee feedback.

JP2009237636HUMAN RESOURCE MATCHING SYSTEM PROBLEM TO BE SOLVED: To provide a human resource matching system for achieving appropriate staff assignment by properly selecting employees, and assigning jobs to them according to the skill level of each

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

employee. SOLUTION: Whether there is any employee satisfying request carrier information input from a portable terminal 2 is checked. When an employee satisfying the request carrier is found, the information on the employee is transmitted to a task terminal 2. When no employee satisfying the request carrier is found, whether there is any employee satisfying quasi-request carrier leading to the request carrier is checked. When an employee satisfying the quasi-request carrier is found as the result, skill conditions necessary for the request carrier are acquired from a skill decision condition database 14. An insufficient skill is predetermined. A developing method adapted to the predetermined insufficient skill and information relevant thereto are acquired from an employee development dictionary database 15, and the information is transmitted to the task terminal.

Groupings of alternative elements or embodiments of the invention disclosed herein are not to be construed as limitations. Each group member can be referred to and claimed individually or in any combination with other members of the group or other elements found herein. One or more members of a group can be included in, or deleted from, a group for reasons of convenience and/or patentability. When any such inclusion or deletion occurs, the specification is herein deemed to contain the group as modified, thus fulfilling the written description of all Markus groups used in the appended claims.

As used in the description herein and throughout the claims that follow, the meaning of “a,” “an,” and “the” includes plural reference unless the context clearly dictates otherwise. Also, as used in the description herein, the meaning of “in” includes “in” and “on” unless the context clearly dictates otherwise.

The recitation of ranges of values herein is merely intended to serve as a shorthand method of referring individually to each separate value falling within the range. Unless otherwise indicated herein, each individual value is incorporated into the specification as if it were individually recited herein. All methods described herein can be performed in any suitable order unless otherwise indicated herein or otherwise clearly contradicted by context.

The use of any and all examples, or exemplary language (e.g. “Such as”) provided with respect to certain embodiments herein is intended merely to better illuminate the invention and does not pose a limitation on the scope of the invention otherwise claimed. No language in the specification should be construed as indicating any non-claimed element essential to the practice of the invention.

The above information disclosed in this Background section is only for the enhancement of understanding of the background of the invention and therefore it may contain information that does not form the prior art that is already known in this country to a person of ordinary skill in the art.

SUMMARY

Before the present systems and methods, are described, it is to be understood that this application is not limited to the particular systems, and methodologies described, as there can be multiple possible embodiments which are not expressly illustrated in the present disclosure. It is also to be understood that the terminology used in the description is for the purpose of describing the particular versions or embodiments only and is not intended to limit the scope of the present application.

The present invention mainly cures and solves the technical problems existing in the prior art. In response to these problems, the present invention discloses Advance employee retention and feedback system in industry using machine learning.

As one aspect of the present invention is to presents “A advance employee retention and feedback system in industry using machine learning, wherein the system is processed by at least one computing unit, wherein the system comprising:

A Employee feedback module, used to get the feedback from the employee of the organization , wherein in the employee feedback module comprises a number of questions related to the working of the organization, the employee satisfaction about the working and demands of the employee towards the employer, wherein the employee feedback module assign a secret code to each employee , provide hidden profile to the employer, wherein the employee feedback module comprises a database of the employee with their past history of working to the organization and current feedback from the manager of the employee; and An employee profile management unit , wherein the employment profile management unit comprises profile of the Employees with an employee satisfaction index calculated through a machine learning model, , wherein the employee satisfaction index is calculated according to the employees feedback in an employee feedback module with a profile feedback from the colleagues or the manager of the employee , wherein employee profile management unit sent a lower employee satisfaction data to the management to the organization and to associated manager, , wherein

employee profile management unit provide facilitation to the higher management to visually monitor the different employee satisfaction index in an employer graphical user interface.. ”

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF DRAWINGS

To clarify various aspects of some example embodiments of the present invention, a more particular description of the invention will be rendered by reference to specific embodiments thereof which are illustrated in the appended drawings. It is appreciated that these drawings depict only illustrated embodiments of the invention and are therefore not to be considered limiting of its scope. The invention will be described and explained with additional specificity and detail through the use of the accompanying drawings.

In order that the advantages of the present invention will be easily understood, a detailed description of the invention is discussed below in conjunction with the appended drawings, which, however, should not be considered to limit the scope of the invention to the accompanying drawings, in which:

Figure 1 shows block diagram representation of Advance employee retention and feedback system in industry using machine learning.

DETAIL DESCRIPTION

The present invention is related to Advance employee retention and feedback system in industry using machine learning.

Figure 1 shows block diagram representation of Advance employee retention and feedback system (10) in industry using machine learning.

Although the present disclosure has been described with the purpose of Advance employee retention and feedback system in industry using machine learning, it should be appreciated that the same has been done merely to illustrate the invention in an exemplary manner and to highlight any other purpose or function for which explained structures or configurations could be used and is covered within the scope of the present disclosure.

The advance employee retention and feedback system (10) in industry using machine learning

is disclosed in this disclosure.

The system (10) is processed by at least one computing unit (1).

The system (10) comprises a Employee feedback module (2) and an employee profile management unit (5).

The Employee feedback module (2) is used to get the feedback from the employee (3) of the organization.

The employee feedback module (2) comprises a number of questions related to the working of the organization, the employee satisfaction about the working and demands of the employee towards the employer.

The employee feedback module (2) assigns a secret code to each employee, provide hidden profile to the employer.

The employee feedback module (2) comprises a database (4) of the employee with their past history of working to the organization and current feedback from the manager of the employee.

The employee profile management unit (5) comprises profile of the Employees (3) with an employee satisfaction index calculated through a machine learning model.

The employee satisfaction index is calculated according to the employees' feedback in an employee feedback module (2) with a profile feedback from the colleagues or the manager of the employee.

The employee profile management unit sent a lower employee satisfaction data to a higher management (6) to the organization and to associated manager.

The employee profile management unit (5) provide facilitation to the higher management (6) to visually monitor the different employee satisfaction index in an employer graphical user interface.

The Mobile computing unit is used to assess Employee feedback module (2). The Employee feedback module (2) has question appears in the form of objective questions.

The computing unit (1) is processor based computing unit.

The employee satisfaction index is calculated using large data analysis of employees through

the same in industry using training sets and classification models.

Those skilled in the art will appreciate that one or more of the described elements may well be combined into a single functional element. Alternatively, certain elements may be split into multiple functional elements. Elements from one embodiment may be added to another embodiment. For example, order of processes described herein may be changed and are not limited to the manner described herein. Moreover, the actions of any block diagram need not be implemented in the order shown; nor do all of the acts need to be necessarily performed. Also, those acts that are not dependent on other acts may be performed in parallel with the other acts. The scope of embodiments is by no means limited by these specific examples.

Although implementations of the invention have been described in a language specific to structural features and/or methods, it is to be understood that the appended claims are not necessarily limited to the specific features or methods described. Rather, the specific features and methods are disclosed as examples of implementations of the invention.

CLAIMS

We claim:

1. A advance employee retention and feedback system (10) in industry using machine learning, wherein the system is processed by at least one computing unit (1), wherein the system (10) comprising:

A Employee feedback module (2), used to get the feedback from the employee (3) of the organization , wherein in the employee feedback module (2) comprises a number of questions related to the working of the organization, the employee satisfaction about the working and demands of the employee towards the employer, wherein the employee feedback module (2) assign a secret code to each employee , provide hidden profile to the employer, wherein the employee feedback module (2) comprises a database (4) of the employee with their past history of working to the organization and current feedback from the manager of the employee; and A employee profile management unit (5) , wherein the employment profile management unit (5) comprises profile of the Employees (3) with an employee satisfaction index calculated through a machine learning model, , wherein the employee satisfaction index is calculated according to the employees feedback in an employee feedback module (2) with

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

a profile feedback from the colleagues or the manager of the employee , wherein employee profile management unit (5) sent a lower employee satisfaction data to a higher management (6) to the organization and to associated manager, , wherein employee profile management unit (5) provide facilitation to the higher management (6) to visually monitor the different employee satisfaction index in an employer graphical user interface.

2. The advance employee retention and feedback system (10) in industry using machine learning as claimed in claim 1, the Mobile computing unit is used to assess Employee feedback module (2) .

3. The advance employee retention and feedback system (10) in industry using machine learning as claimed in claim 1, The Employee feedback module (2) has question appears in the form of objective questions.

4. The advance employee retention and feedback system (10) in industry using machine learning as claimed in claim 1, The computing unit (1) is processor based computing unit.

5. The advance employee retention and feedback system (10) in industry using machine learning as claimed in claim 1, The employee satisfaction index is calculated using large data analysis of employees through the same in industry using training sets and classification models...

ADVANCE EMPLOYEE RETENTION AND FEEDBACK SYSTEM IN INDUSTRY USING MACHINE LEARNING

ABSTRACT

The present invention relates to Advance employee retention and feedback system in industry using machine learning. The objective of the present invention is to solve the problems in the prior art technologies related to computer based identifying, retaining and motivating employees through a management system.

DIAGRAM

Fig. 1

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

5/11/2021

PATENT eFiling

Sr.No.	Name	Nationality	Address	Country	State
1	Dr. Ananth Prabhu G	India	Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Sahyadri College of Engineering and Management, Mangalore, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
2	Dr.Karuna Pandit	India	Professor, Department of Information Science and Engineering, NMAM Institute of Technology, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
3	Dr. Mustafa Basthikodi	India	Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Sahyadri College of Engineering and Management, Mangalore, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
4	Dr. Nethravathi P.S	India	Professor, College of Computer and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
5	Dr Manjula Sanjay Koti	India	Professor & Head, Department of MCA, Sir M Visvesvaraya Institute of Technology, Hinsamarenahalli, Bangalore, Karnataka India	India	Karnataka
6	Dr. Anush Bekal	India	Associate Professor, Department of Electronics and	India	Karnataka

<https://pindiaonline.gov.in/epatentfiling/DraftedForm/ListofDraftedForm>

1/5

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

5/11/2021

PATENT eFiling

			Communications Engineering, Sahyadri College of Engineering and Management, Mangalore, Karnataka, India		
7	Shilpashree S	India	Research Scholar, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, SJC Institute of Technology, Chickballapur, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
8	Rohan Don Salins	India	Assistant Professor, Computer Science and Engineering, St. Joseph Engineering College, Vamanjur, Mangalore, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
9	Sonia V. Soans	India	Lecturer, Department of Information Technology, University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Muscat, Oman	Oman	Not Applicable
10	Vaishak N L	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Sahyadri College of Engineering and Management, Mangalore, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka

2. INVENTOR(S):

Sr.No.	Name	Nationality	Address	Country	State
1	Dr. Ananth Prabhu G	India	Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Sahyadri College of Engineering and Management, Mangalore, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
2	Dr.Karuna Pandit	India	Professor, Department of Information Science and Engineering, NMAM Institute of Technology, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
3	Dr. Mustafa Basthikodi	India	Professor, Department of Computer Science	India	Karnataka

<https://ipindiaonline.gov.in/epatentfiling/DraftedForm/ListofDraftedForm>

2/5

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

5/11/2021

PATENT eFiling

			and Engineering, Sahyadri College of Engineering and Management, Mangalore, Karnataka, India		
4	Dr. Nethravathi P.S	India	Professor, College of Computer and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
5	Dr Manjula Sanjay Koti	India	Professor & Head, Department of MCA, Sir M Visvesvaraya Institute of Technology, Hinsamarenahalli, Bangalore, Karnataka India	India	Karnataka
6	Dr. Anush Bekal	India	Associate Professor, Department of Electronics and Communications Engineering, Sahyadri College of Engineering and Management, Mangalore, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
7	Shilpashree S	India	Research Scholar, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, SJC Institute of Technology, Chickballapur, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
8	Rohan Don Salins	India	Assistant Professor, Computer Science and Engineering, St. Joseph Engineering College, Vamanjur, Mangalore, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
9	Sonia V. Soans	India	Lecturer, Department of Information Technology, University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Muscat, Oman	Oman	Not Applicable
10	Vaishak N L	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Sahyadri College of Engineering and Management,	India	Karnataka

<https://ipindiaonline.gov.in/epatentfiling/DraftedForm/ListofDraftedForm>

3/5

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

5/11/2021

PATENT eFiling

Mangalore,
Karnataka, India

3. TITLE OF THE INVENTION: SYSTEM FOR MANAGEMENT OF VENTILATORS FOR COVID PATIENTS IN HOSPITAL USING BLOCK CHAIN

4. ADDRESS FOR CORRESPONDENCE OF APPLICANT / Telephone No.:
AUTHORISED PATENT AGENT IN INDIA: Fax No.:
Dr. Nethravathi P.S, Professor, College of Computer and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India Mobile No:
E-mail: 1990uditmamodiya@gmail.com

5. PRIORITY PARTICULARS OF THE APPLICATION(S) FILED IN CONVENTION COUNTRY:

Sr.No.	Country	Application Number	Filing Date	Name of the Applicant	Title of the Invention
--------	---------	--------------------	-------------	-----------------------	------------------------

6. PARTICULARS FOR FILING PATENT COOPERATION TREATY (PCT) NATIONAL PHASE APPLICATION:

International Application Number	International Filing Date as Allotted by the Receiving Office
PCT//	

7. PARTICULARS FOR FILING DIVISIONAL APPLICATION

Original (first) Application Number	Date of Filing of Original (first) Application
-------------------------------------	--

8. PARTICULARS FOR FILING PATENT OF ADDITION:

Main Application / Patent Number:	Date of Filing of Main Application
-----------------------------------	------------------------------------

9. DECLARATIONS:

(i) Declaration by the inventor(s)

I/We ,Dr. Ananth Prabhu G,Dr.Karuna Pandit,Dr. Mustafa Basthikodi,Dr. Nethravathi P.S,Dr Manjula Sanjay Koti,Dr. Anush Bekal,Shilpashree S,Rohan Don Salins,Sonia V. Soans,Vaishak N L, is/are the true & first inventor(s) for this invention and declare that the applicant(s) herein is/are my/our assignee or legal representative.

(a) Date: ----

(b) Signature(s) of the inventor(s):

(c) Name(s): Dr. Ananth Prabhu G,Dr.Karuna Pandit,Dr. Mustafa Basthikodi,Dr. Nethravathi P.S,Dr

<https://ipindiaonline.gov.in/epatentfiling/DraftedForm/ListofDraftedForm>

4/5

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

5/11/2021

PATENT eFiling

Manjula Sanjay Koti,Dr. Anush Bekal,Shilpashree S,Rohan Don Salins,Sonia V. Soans,Vaishak N L

(ii) Declaration by the applicant(s) in the convention country

I/We, the applicant(s) in the convention country declare that the applicant(s) herein is/are my/our assignee or legal representative.

(a) Date: -----

(b) Signature(s) :

(c) Name(s) of the singnatory: Dr. Ananth Prabhu G,Dr.Karuna Pandit,Dr. Mustafa Basthikodi,Dr. Nethravathi P.S,Dr Manjula Sanjay Koti,Dr. Anush Bekal,Shilpashree S,Rohan Don Salins,Sonia V. Soans,Vaishak N L

(iii) Declaration by the applicant(s)

- The Complete specification relating to the invention is filed with this application.
- I am/We are, in the possession of the above mentioned invention.
- There is no lawful ground of objection to the grant of the Patent to me/us.

10. FOLLOWING ARE THE ATTACHMENTS WITH THE APPLICATION:

Sr.	Document Description	FileName
1	REQUEST FOR EARLY PUBLICATION(FORM-9)	form 9.pdf
2	COMPLETE SPECIFICATION	FORM 2.pdf
3	DRAWINGS	Drawing.pdf
4	STATEMENT OF UNDERTAKING (FORM 3)	Form 3.pdf
5	DECLARATION OF INVENTORSHIP (FORM 5)	Form 5.pdf

I/We hereby declare that to the best of my/our knowledge, information and belief the fact and matters stated hereing are correct and I/We request that a patent may be granted to me/us for the said invention.

Dated this(Final Payment Date):

Signature:

Name: Balram Singh Yadav

To The Controller of Patents

The Patent office at CHENNAI

This form is electronically generated.

Print

FORM 2

THE PATENTS ACT, 1970
(39 of 1970) &
THE PATENTS RULES, 2003
COMPLETE SPECIFICATION
(See section 10, rule 13)

1. TITLE OF THE INVENTION:

**SYSTEM FOR MANAGEMENT OF
VENTILATORS FOR COVID PATIENTS IN
HOSPITAL USING BLOCK CHAIN**

2. APPLICANTS

Sr.No.	Name	Nationality	Address
1	Dr. Ananth Prabhu G	India	Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Sahyadri College of Engineering and Management, Mangalore, Karnataka, India
2	Dr.Karuna Pandit	India	Professor, Department of Information Science and Engineering, NMAM Institute of Technology, Karnataka, India
3	Dr. Mustafa Basthikodi	India	Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Sahyadri College of Engineering and Management, Mangalore, Karnataka, India
4	Dr. Nethravathi P.S	India	Professor, College of Computer and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India
5	Dr Manjula Sanjay Koti	India	Professor & Head, Department of MCA, Sir M Visvesvaraya Institute of Technology, Hinsamarenahalli, Bangalore, Karnataka India

6	Dr. Anush Bekal	India	Associate Professor, Department of Electronics and Communications Engineering, Sahyadri College of Engineering and Management, Mangalore, Karnataka, India
7	Shilpashree S	India	Research Scholar, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, SJC Institute of Technology, Chickballapur, Karnataka, India
8	Rohan Don Salins	India	Assistant Professor, Computer Science and Engineering, St. Joseph Engineering College, Vamanjur, Mangalore, Karnataka, India
9	Sonia V. Soans	India	Lecturer, Department of Information Technology, University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Muscat, Oman
10	Vaishak NL	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Sahyadri College of Engineering and Management, Mangalore, Karnataka, India

3. PREAMBLE TO THE DESCRIPTION

COMPLETE SPECIFICATION

The following specification particularly describes the invention and the manner in which it is to be performed.

SYSTEM FOR MANAGEMENT OF VENTILATORS FOR COVID PATIENTS IN HOSPITAL USING BLOCK CHAIN

FIELD OF INVENTION

The present invention relates to the technical field of medical data processing, in particular to a hospital resource consumption management and control system.

The present invention relates to field of hospital management system and system is provided to, specifically hospital resource planning through hospital resource management system.

The present invention is also related to field system for management of ventilator resources in a hospital, particularly related to a computer-based system for managing ventilators and ICU in a hospital.

More particularly, the present invention is related to system for management of ventilators for covid patients in hospital using block chain.

BACKGROUND & PRIOR ART

The subject matter discussed in the background section should not be assumed to be prior art merely as a result of its mention in the background section. Similarly, a problem mentioned in the background section or associated with the subject matter of the background section should not be assumed to have been previously recognized in the prior art. The subject matter in the background section merely represents different approaches, which in-and-of-themselves may also be inventions.

Some of the prior related works as follows:

CN112599227A Hospital resource consumption management and control method System and corresponding device and storage medium presents “a hospital resource consumption

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

management and control method, system and corresponding equipment and storage medium, wherein the method comprises the following steps: determining one or more influencing factors influencing the total cost on the basis of collected disease first page data and corresponding medical record charge detail data. All the cases are grouped according to the determined influential factors and the pre-set packet characteristics. Based on the usage data of each charging item, different usage control intervals of different charging items corresponding to each group of cases are determined for managing and controlling hospital resource consumption. The method enables the usage amount of the charging items to be determined automatically and accurately, and is used for hospitals. A doctor regulates the consumption of the corresponding medical resource.”

KR1020160016317A System for Hospital Resource Managing and Method thereof presents “a system and a method for managing small and medium-sized hospitals. The system for managing resources of a hospital group including a plurality of individually operated hospitals comprises: an inventory management module to manage an article order list for each hospital ward and department that requested articles, and manage a requested quantity by an approval by a manager on article order; a release management module to manage the current release for receipt and delivery of all departments in the hospital including a requested release by a request of department and a general release for adjusting the inventory quantity”

EP2063373A1 Method and system for management of operatingroom resources presents “ computer-implemented method for managing operating-room resources in a hospital includes the steps of receiving at least one surgery request, identifying the resources required for surgery associated with the surgery request, capturing initial data on availability of the resources, capturing initial patient data, and establishing a pre-scheduled operating-room plan based on an initial optimization, and the further steps of capturing current data on availability of the resources, capturing current patient data and establishing a current operating-room plan based on a current optimization.”

EP2060986B1 System and method for management of processes in a hospital and/or in an operating room presents “ a computer-implemented method for managing operating-room resources in a hospital includes the steps of receiving at least one surgery request, identifying

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

the resources required for surgery associated with the surgery request, capturing initial data on availability of the resources, capturing initial patient data, and establishing a pre-scheduled operating-room plan based on an initial optimization, and the further steps of capturing current data on availability of the resources, capturing current patient data and establishing a current operating-room plan based on a current optimization”

JP2018506801A - In hospitals and health care consultant for optimal human resources manager hospital helps plan is determined, based on a simulation system and method presents “plurality of patient parameter comprises at least [...] human resources personnel and volume parameters received parameter based temporary personal resources plan to yield, The fluctuation of the parameter as variables representing parameters of the pseudo-random distribution of the temporary manpower plan represents a plan of human resources, based on the data received parameter variation, calculated from the temporary manpower and plunger, The purpose of the simulated human resources of the medical facility personnel to optimize the objective function represents a plan of the random variables, The simulated human resources personnel in plan showing the optimized parameters is determined from the optimization of the random variables, the human resources personnel and plunger for outputting [...] The electronic processor is programmed to execute a method for planning a human resource A human resources planning system.”

CN2643405Y - Patient diagnosis and treatment data statistics monitor presents “patient diagnosis data statistics and monitoring device, mainly for doctor diagnosis and patient data collection, processing and output. The utility model includes a diagnosis bed, a data processor and a display screen, a weight sensor is arranged below a bearing surface or a bearing foot of the diagnosis bed. An output end of the diagnosis bed weight sensor is connected with an input end of the data processor; the output end of the data processor is connected with the input end of the display screen. The output end of the data processor can also be connected with a printer or a computer management center of the hospital. The utility model strengthens the understanding on patient data mastered by the doctor for the hospital, monitors the operation of the diagnosis equipment, provides basis for reasonable arrangement of hospital resources and improves the management level of the hospital.”

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

CN202394308U Hospital touch screen automatic toll collector presents “a hospital touch screen automation toll collector, which is programmed by employing an SQL database C/S architecture, and is provided with a vertical cabinet structure, wherein a main control machine is a G31 industrial personal computer. The hospital touch screen automation toll collector comprises a touch screen liquid crystal display, a currency receiving machine, a currency changing machine, a printer and a reader and writer, etc. The automatic toll collector employs a serial port connection mode, is in cooperation with the network technology and can automatically receive paper currencies of 5-100 Yuan and changes currencies of 20 Yuan, 10 Yuan and 1 Yuan. The hospital touch screen automatic toll collector performs toll collection through finger touch, is unmanned, is automatic in toll collection and billing, is a novel modern mechatronics product, and can self-manages and saves labor service expenditure, thereby reducing operational cost and increasing the whole image of enterprises. The hospital touch screen automation toll collector is provided with a function of counterfeit money identification, can make a voice alarm signal and is operated through finger touch.”

US20120203564A1 Method and System for Real-Time Automatic Optimization of Emergency Room Resources Management presents “a computer implemented method and system for real-time optimal management of hospital's Emergency Room resources. The system provides optimal work plan for crewmembers and equipment, taking into consideration relevant variables. It uses multivariable optimization techniques to optimize the defined cost functions, which represent overall patient treatment waiting time and cost. Real-time information is provided to both patients and crewmembers. The work plan is continuously updated according to occurring events.”

NL2023043A CIVIL HOSPITAL MOBILIZATION SYSTEM AND METHOD THEREOF presents “provides a civil hospital mobilization system and method thereof, and the system includes a civil hospital mobilization model configured to simulate mobilization organization and management of a civil hospital resource, to obtain a corresponding mobilization result. The civil hospital mobilization model 5 includes an organization management module configured to generate a mobilization policy for the civil hospital resource; a mobilization execution module configured to mobilize the civil hospital resource according to the mobilization policy, and output a mobilization result. “

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

CN2643405Y Patient diagnosis and treatment data statistics monitor presents “to patient diagnosis data statistics and monitoring device, mainly for doctor diagnosis and patient data collection, processing and output. The utility model includes a diagnosis bed, a data processor and a display screen, a weight sensor is arranged below a bearing surface or a bearing foot of the diagnosis bed. An output end of the diagnosis bed weight sensor is connected with an input end of the data processor; the output end of the data processor is connected with the input end of the display screen. The output end of the data processor can also be connected with a printer or a computer management center of the hospital. The utility model strengthens the understanding on patient data mastered by the doctor for the hospital, monitors the operation of the diagnosis equipment, provides basis for reasonable arrangement of hospital resources and improves the management level of the hospital.”

CN106788477A Intelligent mobile medical terminal presents “an intelligent mobile medical terminal. The terminal comprises a database module, a position recognition module, a cloud data receiving module, a communication module, a power module, a management module, a display module, an operation module and a server. Wherein, the management module is used for classifying and managing immediate data and original data in the database; the management module 10 comprises an infusion management module, a room check management module, a calling module, a drug taking management module and an information inquiry module. The infusion management module, room check management module, calling module, drug taking management module and the information inquiry module of the management module share a processing module. “

CN206239403U Cardiac surgery postoperative care monitoring appearance presents “ a cardiac surgery postoperative care monitoring appearance, including infrared video camera, support frame, detection subsidies, power and display, the input of detection room on duty is connected to infrared video camera 's output electricity, detect the input that the output electricity that pastes was connected with detecting system, detecting system includes the blood pressure check appearance, breathes detector, heart rate detection appearance and body temperature detector, 5 detecting system's output electricity is connected with the input of information collection module, and detecting system's output still the electricity be connected with information contrast module's input. This cardiac surgery postoperative care monitoring appearance, it need not waste the time that the nursing staff detected to possess the patient's

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

condition that detects by oneself, be favorable to the advantage of hospital's medical treatment resource application, has solved monitoring that medical personnel cannot be at every moment to patient's vital sign, cannot be timely know the condition, cause patient emergency easily under, the problem of the phenomenon that the appearance cannot in time be salvage.”

CN209486817U Intelligent ward automatic storage and recovery cabinet presents “an intelligent automatic storage and recovery cabinet for an inpatient area in the technical field of medicine. Integrated cabinet, the device further comprises a recovery device, the integrated cabinet comprises a medical staff clothes distribution cabinet, a 20 hospital dress distribution cabinet and a selling cabinet. The medical staff clothes distribution cabinet, the hospital dress distribution cabinet and the selling cabinet are arranged side by side. The medical worker and staff clothes distribution cabinet comprises a doctor and staff clothes putting area. A nurse work clothes putting area and a nursing work clothes putting area, the doctor work clothes putting area, the nurse work clothes putting area and the nurse work clothes putting area are arranged side by side. Main display screens and object taking two-dimensional code scanners are fixedly arranged on the side walls of the medical personnel staff clothes distribution cabinet, the hospital clothes distribution cabinet and the selling cabinet body; according to the hospital straw hat room management system, cross contamination between straw hats is avoided, manpower and material resources are saved.

TWM599444U Medical information service device presents “medical service information platform module comprises a subscription service module, a system function management module, a hospital resource management module, a medical imaging management module, a medical imaging management module and a database.”.

Groupings of alternative elements or embodiments of the invention disclosed herein are not to be construed as limitations. Each group member can be referred to and claimed individually or in any combination with other members of the group or other elements found herein. One or more members of a group can be included in, or deleted from, a group for reasons of convenience and/or patentability. When any such inclusion or deletion occurs, the specification is herein deemed to contain the group as modified, thus fulfilling the written description of all Markus groups used in the appended claims.

As used in the description herein and throughout the claims that follow, the meaning of “a,” “an,” and “the” includes plural reference unless the context clearly dictates otherwise. Also, as used in the description herein, the meaning of “in” includes “in” and “on” unless the context clearly dictates otherwise.

The recitation of ranges of values herein is merely intended to serve as a shorthand method of referring individually to each separate value falling within the range. Unless otherwise indicated herein, each individual value is incorporated into the specification as if it were individually recited herein. All methods described herein can be performed in any suitable order unless otherwise indicated herein or otherwise clearly contradicted by context.

The use of any and all examples, or exemplary language (e.g. “Such as”) provided with respect to certain embodiments herein is intended merely to better illuminate the invention and does not pose a limitation on the scope of the invention otherwise claimed. No language in the specification should be construed as indicating any non-claimed element essential to the practice of the invention.

The above information disclosed in this Background section is only for the enhancement of understanding of the background of the invention and therefore it may contain information that does not form the prior art that is already known in this country to a person of ordinary skill in the art.

OBJECTIVE OF THE INVENTION

The principle objective of the present invention is to provide a system for management of ventilators for covid patients in hospital using block chain.

SUMMARY

Before the present systems and methods, are described, it is to be understood that this application is not limited to the particular systems, and methodologies described, as there can

be multiple possible embodiments which are not expressly illustrated in the present disclosure. It is also to be understood that the terminology used in the description is for the purpose of describing the particular versions or embodiments only and is not intended to limit the scope of the present application.

The present invention mainly cures and solves the technical problems existing in the prior art. In response to these problems, the present invention discloses system for management of ventilators for covid patients in hospital using block chain.

As one aspect of the present invention presents a system for management of ventilators for covid patients in hospital using block chain, wherein the system comprises: a wearable biomedical monitoring unit, wherein the wearable biomedical monitoring unit is configuring to monitor biomedical signals and physiological signals of patient, wherein the wearable biomedical monitoring unit comprises. an oximeter, used to measure oxygen level of patient, a pulse meter, used to measure pulse of the patients, a respiration rate measurement unit, used to measure the respiration rate of the patient, a communication unit used to communicate the signal; a healthcare resource management unit, wherein health healthcare resource management unit is used to manage and allot the ventilator and ice to the patient, wherein the healthcare resource management unit comprises a database, to store information about the available ventilators and ice unit in the hospital; and a central control unit , wherein the central control unit is connected to the all the wearable biomedical monitoring unit of all the patients available in the hospital, and connected to the healthcare resource management unit , wherein central control unit assign a priority index to 20 reach patients according to their biomedical signals and patient data using a block chain algorithm, and used to allot ice and ventilator to a patient according to priority index of the patient , wherein the priority index is calculated using the critical condition of the patient, biomedical and physical parameters of the patient , patient data and request of the patient.

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF DRAWINGS

To clarify various aspects of some example embodiments of the present invention, a more particular description of the invention will be rendered by reference to specific embodiments thereof which are illustrated in the appended drawings. It is appreciated that these drawings

depict only illustrated embodiments of the invention and are therefore not to be considered limiting of its scope. The invention will be described and explained with additional specificity and detail through the use of the accompanying drawings.

In order that the advantages of the present invention will be easily understood, a detailed description of the invention is discussed below in conjunction with the appended drawings, which, however, should not be considered to limit the scope of the invention to the accompanying drawings, in which:

Figure 1 shows detail block diagram representation of system for management of ventilators for covid patients in hospital using block chain.

DETAIL DESCRIPTION

The present invention is related to system for management of ventilators for covid patients in hospital using block chain. Figure 1 shows detail block diagram representation of system for management of ventilators for covid patients in hospital using block chain. Although the present disclosure has been described with the purpose of system for management of ventilators for covid patients in hospital using block chain, it should be appreciated that the same has been done merely to illustrate the invention in an exemplary manner and to highlight any other purpose or function for which explained structures or configurations could be used and is covered within the scope of the present disclosure.

The system for management of ventilators for covid patients in hospital using block chain is disclosed in this disclosure.

The system for management of ventilators for covid patients in hospital using block chain, wherein the system comprises a wearable 5 biomedical monitoring unit, a healthcare resource management unit, and a central control unit.

The wearable biomedical monitoring unit is configuring to monitor biomedical signals and physiological signals of patient.

The wearable biomedical monitoring unit comprises an oximeter, 10 a pulse meter and a respiration rate measurement unit.

The oximeter is used to measure oxygen level of patient. The pulse meter is used to measure pulse of the patients. The respiration rate measurement unit is used to measure the respiration rate of the patient, a communication unit used to communicate the signal.

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

The wearable biomedical monitoring unit is connected to the central control unit wireless communication unit.

The Healthcare resource management unit is used to manage and allot the ventilator and ICU to the patient.

The Healthcare resource management unit comprises a database, to store information about the available ventilators and ICU unit in the hospital.

The Central control unit is connected to the all the wearable biomedical monitoring unit of all the patients available in the hospital, and connected to the Healthcare resource management unit.

The central control unit assign a priority index to reach patients according to their biomedical signals and patient data using a block chain algorithm, and used to allot ICU and ventilator to a patient according to priority index of the patient.

The priority index is calculated using the critical condition of the patient, biomedical and physical parameters of the patient, patient data and request of the patient.

The biomedical monitoring unit is weired by the patient on each finger and on his hand.

The patient data comprises history of health of the patient, past critical illness of the patient and past medical and treatment data.

The figures and the foregoing description give examples of embodiments. Those skilled in the art will appreciate that one or more of the described elements may well be combined into a single functional element.

Alternatively, certain elements may be split into multiple functional elements. Elements from one embodiment may be added to another embodiment. For example, order of processes described herein may be changed and are not limited to the manner described herein. Moreover, the actions of any block diagram need not be implemented in the order shown; nor do all of the acts need to be necessarily performed. Also, those acts that are not dependent on other acts may be performed in parallel with the other acts. The scope of embodiments is by no means limited by these specific examples.

Although implementations of the invention have been described in a language specific to structural features and/or methods, it is to be understood that the appended claims are not necessarily limited to the specific features or methods described. Rather, the specific features and methods are disclosed as examples of implementations of the invention.

CLAIMS

We claim:

1. A system for management of ventilators for covid patients in hospital using block chain, wherein the system comprises: A wearable biomedical monitoring unit, wherein the wearable biomedical monitoring unit is configuring to monitor biomedical signals and physiological signals of patient, wherein the Wearable biomedical monitoring unit comprises, An oximeter, used to measure oxygen level of patient, A pulse meter, used to measure pulse of the patients, A respiration rate measurement unit, used to measure the respiration rate of the patient, a communication unit used to communicate the signal; A Healthcare resource management unit, wherein health Healthcare resource management unit is used to manage and allot the ventilator and ICU to the patient, wherein the Healthcare resource management unit comprises a database, to store information about the available ventilators and ICU unit in the hospital; and A Central control unit , wherein the central control unit is connected to the all the wearable biomedical monitoring unit of all the patients available in the hospital, and connected to the Healthcare resource management unit , wherein central control unit assign a priority index to reach patients according to their biomedical signals and patient data using a block chain algorithm, And used to allot ICU and ventilator to a patient according to priority index of the patient , , wherein the priority index is calculated using the critical condition of the patient, biomedical and physical parameters of the patient , patient data and request of the patient.

2. The system for management of ventilators for covid patients in hospital using block chain as claimed in 1, wherein in biomedical monitoring unit is weird by the patient on each finger and on his hand.

3. The system for management of ventilators for covid patients in hospital using block chain as claimed in 1, the patient data comprises history of health of the patient, past critical illness of the patient and past medical and treatment data.

4. The system for management of ventilators for covid patients in hospital using block chain as claimed in 1, the wearable biomedical monitoring unit is connected to the central control unit wireless communication unit.

SYSTEM FOR MANAGEMENT OF VENTILATORS FOR COVID PATIENTS IN HOSPITAL USING BLOCK CHAIN

ABSTRACT

The present invention relates to system for management of ventilators for covid patients in hospital using block chain. The objective of the present invention is to solve the problems in the prior art technologies 10 of hospital resource management.

DRAWINGS

Applicants Dr. Ananth Prabhu G & others

Sheet No. 1 of Total 1

FIGURE 1

Dated 11th Day of May, 2021

Australian Government
IP Australia

CERTIFICATE OF GRANT INNOVATION PATENT

Patent number: 2021104977

The Commissioner of Patents has granted the above patent on 13 April 2022, and certifies that the below particulars have been registered in the Register of Patents.

Name and address of patentee(s):

Pankaj Mudholkar of Assistant Professor, Dept. Master of Computer Applications (MCA), Thakur Institute of Management Studies, Career Development & Research Mumbai Maharashtra 400101 India

Megha Mudholkar of Assistant Professor, Dept. Master of Computer Applications (MCA), Thakur Institute of Management Studies, Career Development & Research Mumbai Maharashtra 400101 India

Kusum Yadav of Associate Professor, College of Computer Science and Engineering, University of Ha'il Ha'il 81141 Saudi Arabia

Mannava Yesubabu of Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Vardhaman College of Engineering, Shamshabad Hyderabad 501218 India

Amedapu Srinivas of Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Sreenidhi Institute of Science and Technology Hyderabad 501218 India

Gaurav Indra of Assistant Professor, Department of Information Technology, Indira Gandhi Delhi Technical University For Women, Kashmere Gate New Delhi 110006 India

Vishal Dattana of Moodle Administrator and Senior Lecturer, Department of Computing, Middle East College Muscat 124 Oman

Nethravathi P.S of Professor, College of Computer and Information Science, Srinivas University Mangalore Karnataka 575001 India

Sonia V. Soans of Lecturer, Department of Information Technology, University of Technology and Applied Sciences, Muscat State Muscat 611 Oman

Jyoti Dashora of Assistant Professor, Sangam University Bhillwara Rajasthan 311001 India

Ansuman Samal of Associate Professor, Faculty of Hospitality and Tourism Management, Siksha O Anusandhan Deemed to be University Bhubaneswar Odisha 751030 India

Karunesh Saxena. of Vice Chancellor, Sangam University Bhillwara Rajasthan 31100 India

Ravinder M of Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science & Engineering, Indira Gandhi Delhi Technical University for Women, Madrasa Road, Opposite St. James Church, Kashmere Gate Delhi 110006 India

Title of invention:

INTELLIGENT SYSTEM & METHOD TO PROTECT AND SECURE ENVIRONMENT OF PREMISES USING IOT NETWORK

Name of inventor(s):

Dated this 13th day of April 2022

Commissioner of Patents

PATENTS ACT 1990

The Australian Patents Register is the official record and should be referred to for the full details pertaining to this IP Right.

Australian Government

IP Australia

CERTIFICATE OF GRANT INNOVATION PATENT

Patent number: 2021104977

Mudholkar, Pankaj; Mudholkar, Megha; Yadav, Kusum; Yesubabu, Mannava; Srinivas, Amedapu; Indra, Gaurav; Dattana, Vishal; P. S., Nethravathi; Soans, Sonia V.; Dashora, Jyoti; Samal, Ansuman; Saxena., Karunesh and M., Ravinder

Term of Patent:

Eight years from 5 August 2021

NOTE: This Innovation Patent cannot be enforced unless and until it has been examined by the Commissioner of Patents and a Certificate of Examination has been issued. See sections 120(1A) and 129A of the Patents Act 1990, set out on the reverse of this document.

Dated this 13th day of April 2022

Commissioner of Patents

PATENTS ACT 1990

The Australian Patents Register is the official record and should be referred to for the full details pertaining to this IP Right.

**INTELLIGENT SYSTEM & METHOD TO PROTECT AND
SECURE ENVIRONMENT OF PREMISES USING IOT
NETWORK**

ABSTRACT

The present invention is related to intelligent system & method to protect and secure environment of premises using IOT network. The objective of present invention is to solve the abnormalities presented in the prior art techniques related to securing and protecting the premises using sensors.

CLAIMS

I/We claim:

1. An intelligent system to protect and secure environment of premises using IOT network, wherein the system comprising: A transducer module, wherein the transducer module comprises plurality of transducers comprises a metal oxide transducer, a proximity transducer, an electrochemical transducer, an optical transducer, an IR detection, wherein the plurality of the transducers is placed at an appropriate location of the large premises to sense particular threat object; A plurality of visual panel, configured with at least one processor unit to visual panel the parameters of the environment with the source of the threat and the level of the threat; and A Controlling Processor Module, the Controlling Processor Module comprises a communication unit, a storage unit and a computing unit, wherein the Controlling Processor Module is connected to the transducer module, the threat controlling module , to the visual panel of the premises and to an online environment information sharing portal wherein at least one processor unit of the Controlling Processor Module process the signal from the transducer module & the online environment information sharing portal , and control the operation of the threat controlling module to the visual panel of the premises.
2. The system for internal environment maintenance for the large premises as claimed in claim 1, the system is connected to plurality of mobile processor unit to visual panel the status of inside environment of the premises with the source of the threat and level of the threat.
3. The system for internal environment maintenance for the large premises as claimed in claim 1, the Controlling Processor Module performs the computing using a microprocessor based Computing.
4. The system for internal environment maintenance for the large premises as claimed in claim 1, the Controlling Processor Module comprises an adaptive algorithm stored in the storage of the central computing unit, adapt and processes based on the different parameters of transducer modules.

DRAWINGS

FIGURE 1

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

3/30/2021

PATENT eFiling

<p>FORM 1 THE PATENTS ACT, 1970 (39 of 1970) & THE PATENTS RULES, 2003 APPLICATION FOR GRANT OF PATENT [See sections 7,54 & 135 and rule 20(1)]</p>	<p>(FOR OFFICE USE ONLY)</p> <p>Application No.:</p> <p>Filing Date:</p> <p>Amount of Fee Paid:</p> <p>CBR No.:</p> <p>Signature:</p>
---	--

1. APPLICANT(S):

Sr.No.	Name	Nationality	Address	Country	State
1	Dr. Chinmaya Ranjan Pattanaik	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Ajay Binay Institute of Technology, Cuttack, Odisha, India	India	Orissa
2	Dr. K. E. Prakash	India	Director, Department of Civil Engineering, Shree Devi Institute of Technology, Mangalore, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
3	Vinayachandra	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science, St Philomena College, Puttur, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
4	Dr. Charu	India	Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science Engineering and IT, Jaypee Institute of Information Technology, Noida, India	India	Uttar Pradesh
5	Geetha Poornima K	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science, St Philomena College, Puttur, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
6	Rajeshwari M	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science, St Philomena College, Puttur, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
7	Dr. Krishna Prasad K	India	Associate Professor, Director-College Research Council, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas	India	Karnataka

<https://ipindiaonline.gov.in/epatentfiling/DraftedForm/ListofDraftedForm>

1/8

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

3/30/2021

PATENT eFiling

			University, Karnataka, India		
8	Dr. Nethravathi P. S.	India	Professor, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
9	Dr. Pavithra G.	India	Associate Professor, Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering (ECE), Dayananda Sagar College of Engineering (DSCE), Block No. 17, Room No. 17205, Kumaraswamy Layout, Shavigemalleshwara Hills, Bangalore- 560078, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
10	Dr. T.C.Manjunath	India	Professor & Head of the Dept., Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering (ECE), Dayananda Sagar College of Engineering (DSCE), Block No. 17, Kumaraswamy Layout, Shavigemalleshwara Hills, Bangalore-560078, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka

2. INVENTOR(S):

Sr.No.	Name	Nationality	Address	Country	State
1	Dr. Chinmaya Ranjan Pattanaik	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Ajay Binay Institute of Technology, Cuttack, Odisha, India	India	Orissa
2	Dr. K. E. Prakash	India	Director, Department of Civil Engineering, Shree Devi Institute of Technology, Mangalore, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
3	Vinayachandra	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science, St Philomena College,	India	Karnataka

<https://ipinfronline.gov.in/ePatentFiling/TraffedForm/1/ctrl/TraffedForm>

2/6

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

3/30/2021

PATENT eFiling

			Puttur, Karnataka, India		
4	Dr. Charu	India	Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science Engineering and IT, Jaypee Institute of Information Technology, Noida, India	India	Uttar Pradesh
5	Geetha Poornima K	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science, St Philomena College, Puttur, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
6	Rajeshwari M	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science, St Philomena College, Puttur, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
7	Dr. Krishna Prasad K	India	Associate Professor, Director-College Research Council, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
8	Dr. Nethravathi P. S.	India	Professor, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
9	Dr. Pavithra G.	India	Associate Professor, Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering (ECE), Dayananda Sagar College of Engineering (DSCE), Block No. 17, Room No. 17205, Kumaraswamy Layout, Shavigemalleshwara Hills, Bangalore-560078, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
10	Dr. T.C.Manjunath	India	Professor & Head of the Dept., Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering (ECE), Dayananda Sagar	India	Karnataka

<https://ipindiaonline.gov.in/epatentfiling/DraftedForm/ListofDraftedForm>

3/6

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

3/30/2021

PATENT eFiling

		College of Engineering (DSCE), Block No. 17, Kumaraswamy Layout, Shavigemalleshwara Hills, Bangalore- 560078, Karnataka, India		
--	--	--	--	--

3. TITLE OF THE INVENTION: SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR DETECTION OF FAULTS IN GAS METER USING COMPOUND INTERNET OF THINGS (IOT) SENSORS

4. ADDRESS FOR CORRESPONDENCE OF APPLICANT / Telephone No.:
AUTHORISED PATENT AGENT IN INDIA:
 Dr. Chinmaya Ranjan Pattanaik, Assistant Professor, Telephone No.:
 Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Ajay Fax No.:
 Binay Institute of Technology, Cuttack, Odisha, India Mobile No:
 E-mail: 1990uditmamodiya@gmail.com

5. PRIORITY PARTICULARS OF THE APPLICATION(S) FILED IN CONVENTION COUNTRY:

Sr.No.	Country	Application Number	Filing Date	Name of the Applicant	Titile of the Invention

6. PARTICULARS FOR FILING PATENT COOPERATION TREATY (PCT) NATIONAL PHASE APPLICATION:

International Application Number	International Filing Date as Allotted by the Receiving Office
PCT//	

7. PARTICULARS FOR FILING DIVISIONAL APPLICATION

Original (first) Application Number	Date of Filing of Original (first) Application

8. PARTICULARS FOR FILING PATENT OF ADDITION:

Main Application / Patent Number:	Date of Filing of Main Application

9. DECLARATIONS:

(i) Declaration by the inventor(s)

I/We ,Dr. Chinmaya Ranjan Pattanaik,Dr. K. E. Prakash,Vinayachandra,Dr. Charu,Geetha Poornima K.,Rajeshwari M,Dr. Krishna Prasad K,Dr. Nethravathi P. S.,Dr. Pavithra G.,Dr. T.C.Manjunath, is/are the true & first inventor(s) for this invention and declare that the applicant(s) herein is/are my/our assignee or legal representative.

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

3/30/2021

PATENT eFiling

(a) Date: ----

(b) Signature(s) of the inventor(s):

(c) Name(s): Dr. Chinmaya Ranjan Pattanaik, Dr. K. E. Prakash, Vinayachandra, Dr. Charu, Geetha Poornima K, Rajeshwari M, Dr. Krishna Prasad K, Dr. Nethravathi P. S., Dr. Pavithra G., Dr. T.C. Manjunath

(ii) Declaration by the applicant(s) in the convention country

I/We, the applicant(s) in the convention country declare that the applicant(s) herein is/are my/our assignee or legal representative.

(a) Date: ----

(b) Signature(s) :

(c) Name(s) of the signatory: Dr. Chinmaya Ranjan Pattanaik, Dr. K. E. Prakash, Vinayachandra, Dr. Charu, Geetha Poornima K, Rajeshwari M, Dr. Krishna Prasad K, Dr. Nethravathi P. S., Dr. Pavithra G., Dr. T.C. Manjunath

(iii) Declaration by the applicant(s)

- The Complete specification relating to the invention is filed with this application.
- I am/We are, in the possession of the above mentioned invention.
- There is no lawful ground of objection to the grant of the Patent to me/us.

10. FOLLOWING ARE THE ATTACHMENTS WITH THE APPLICATION:

Sr.	Document Description	FileName
1	REQUEST FOR EARLY PUBLICATION(FORM-9)	Form 9.pdf
2	COMPLETE SPECIFICATION	FORM 2.pdf
3	DRAWINGS	Drawing.pdf
4	STATEMENT OF UNDERTAKING (FORM 3)	Form 3.pdf
5	DECLARATION OF INVENTORSHIP (FORM 5)	Form 5.pdf

I/We hereby declare that to the best of my/our knowledge, information and belief the fact and matters stated hereing are correct and I/We request that a patent may be granted to me/us for the said invention.

Dated this(Final Payment Date):

Signature:

Name: Balram Singh Yadav

To The Controller of Patents

The Patent office at KOLKATA

This form is electronically generated.

<https://ipindiaonline.gov.in/epatentfiling/DraftedForm/ListofDraftedForm>

5/6

FORM 2

THE PATENTS ACT, 1970
(39 of 1970) &
THE PATENTS RULES, 2003
COMPLETE SPECIFICATION
(See section 10, rule 13)

1. TITLE OF THE INVENTION:

**SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR DETECTION OF
FAULTS IN GAS METER USING COMPOUND
INTERNET OF THINGS (IOT) SENSORS**

2. APPLICANTS

Sr.No.	Name	Nationality	Address
1	Dr. Chinmaya Ranjan Pattanaik	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Ajay Binay Institute of Technology, Cuttack, Odisha, India
2	Dr. K. E. Prakash	India	Director, Department of Civil Engineering, Shree Devi Institute of Technology, Mangalore, Karnataka, India
3	Vinayachandra	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science, St Philomena College, Puttur, Karnataka, India
4	Dr. Charu	India	Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science Engineering and IT, Jaypee Institute of Information Technology, Noida, India
5	Geetha Poornima K	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science, St Philomena College, Puttur, Karnataka, India

6	Rajeshwari M	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science, St Philomena College, Puttur, Karnataka, India
7	Dr. Krishna Prasad K	India	Associate Professor, Director-College Research Council, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India
8	Dr. Nethravathi P. S.	India	Professor, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India
9	Dr. Pavithra G.	India	Associate Professor, Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering (ECE), Dayananda Sagar College of Engineering (DSCE), Block No. 17, Room No. 17205, Kumaraswamy Layout, Shavigemalleshwara Hills, Bangalore- 560078, Karnataka, India
10	Dr. T.C.Manjunath	India	Professor & Head of the Dept., Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering (ECE), Dayananda Sagar College of Engineering (DSCE), Block No. 17, Kumaraswamy Layout, Shavigemalleshwara Hills, Bangalore-560078, Karnataka, India

3. PREAMBLE TO THE DESCRIPTION

COMPLETE SPECIFICATION

The following specification particularly describes the invention and the manner in which it is to be performed.

SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR DETECTION OF FAULTS IN GAS METER USING COMPOUND INTERNET OF THINGS (IOT) SENSORS

FIELD OF INVENTION

The present invention relates to the technical field of an intelligent gas meter including detecting abnormal operation. The present invention relates to field of a fault diagnosis apparatus for a gas meter and a gas meter using the same, and more particularly, to an apparatus and method for diagnosing a failure of a gas meter through pressure detection and a gas meter using the same. The present invention relates to the technical field of a gas flow path of a gas meter which detects a failure of the operation, valve, flow on the gas meter fault detection method. More particularly, the present invention is related to system and method for detection of faults in gas meter using compound internet of things (IoT) sensors.

BACKGROUND & PRIOR ART

The subject matter discussed in the background section should not be assumed to be prior art merely as a result of its mention in the background section. Similarly, a problem mentioned in the background section or associated with the subject matter of the background section should not be assumed to have been previously recognized in the prior art. The subject matter in the background section merely represents different approaches, which in-and-of-themselves may also be inventions. A fuel for daily cooking of people has been transformed from a conventional energy with serious resource waste and serious pollution, such as firewood and coal, into a clean energy such as natural gas, coal gas or even electricity. However, concerning the use of fuel gas, a fault may occur in a gas meter due to reasons such as external magnetic interference and insufficient battery capacity. For a user without repair experience, when some simple faults occur, he/she still needs to make a call to invite a maintainer of a gas company to the site for repair. As a result, a lot of labor costs and time costs are wasted, and the efficiency is low.

Some of the prior related works as follows:

JP2010014584A - GAS METER HAVING REPORTING FUNCTION presents “Gas is supplied to the combustion device and supply the supply gas flow rate and metering of the gas

pressure, the gas combustion device which cuts off the supply of gas to the gas shut-off valve and, the metering part of the feed gas and the feed gas pressure flow measurement value based on the measurement value, the measuring section of the gas combustion appliance via a gas supply system leading to the occurrence of an abnormality and an abnormality detecting portion, which is detected by the abnormality detecting portion is abnormal, the abnormality of the predetermined object when the gas shut-off, the gas shut-off valve and a gas shut-off valve control portion, at every lapse of a fixed period of time, the predetermined period by the gas shut-off valve is shut off in the case, a predetermined \"without interrupting the gas\" report destination and transmits to the reporting section has a gas meter with and reporting functions”

JP5394017B2 - Reporting function with a gas meter presents “The gas meter 15, having a reporting function in a system 3 at a gas use side of a gas use situation supervisory system, has a metering section having a flow sensor and a pressure sensor, thus detecting the presence or absence of a fault at a fault detection section of a control section, based on them. When a fault of which gas should be shut off is detected, a gas shut-off valve is 7 forcibly shut off. When a fault of which a fault alarm should be given is detected, a fault alarm is displayed. A reporting section transmits a shut-off report and a fault alarm report, to a centralized supervisory center device 2 and transmits a gas shut-off report for a fixed period for the respective fixed period, and transmits a \"no gas shut-off\" report and a \"no fault alarm\" report to the centralized supervisory center device”

JP2009186300A - GAS METER DIAGNOSING DEVICE, GAS METER EQUIPPED WITH THIS DEVICE, AND GAS METER DIAGNOSING METHOD presents “a gas meter diagnosing device which is capable of determining abnormality (fault) of a flow sensor of a gas meter by utilizing a phenomenon that gas pressure changes when a gas flow rate changes, and to provide the gas meter equipped with the device and a gas meter diagnosing method. SOLUTION: A meter reading value being a cumulative value of a flow rate value of gas measured by a flow rate measuring means for measuring a passing gas flow rate, and a pressure value of the gas measured by a pressure measuring means, are made a set and read out at every prescribed time interval, and the presence or absence of a change in the pressure value is determined by a pressure value change determining means. In the case when there is the change in the pressure value, it is determined by a meter reading value change determining means whether the value changes or not,”

CN106643987A - Fault diagnosis and compensation method for multi-channel ultrasonic gas flow meter presents “a fault diagnosis and compensation method for multi-channel ultrasonic gas flow meter. The method is based on a four channel ultrasonic gas flow measuring device. The measuring device comprises a four channel ultrasonic sensor tube section, a sensor front-end processing module, a data acquisition control module and a computer. According to the method, firstly a position of an abnormal sound channel is determined by online sound velocity measurement, then, the measured data of the abnormal sound channels are discarded, finally, the weight coefficients corresponding to other normal operating sound channels are adjusted, the flow velocity and flow of the gas in the pipeline are calculated by using the measured data of the normal working sound channel to compensate the deviation of the flow measurement after the sound channel has faults, thus making the multi-channel ultrasonic gas flow meter guarantee a high measuring accuracy in the period after the sound channel fault occurs and before the fault is eliminated. The fault diagnosis and compensation method for multi-channel ultrasonic gas flow meter provides a solution thought for the online fault diagnosis and compensation of the multi-channel ultrasonic gas flow meter, and the proposed compensation method can obviously reduce the flow measuring deviation caused by sound channel fault.”

CN203260162U - Combustion gas alarm closing valve device presents “a combustion gas alarm closing valve device. With utilization of the device, problems that the existing combustion gas alarm device has low accuracy and reliability, the voltage output that is changed with changes of gas concentration is not stable, and the existing device is not suitable for all control stop valve types can be solved. The provided device comprises a power supply circuit that is connected with a controller; a fault detection circuit, a signal amplification processing circuit, an alarm and a pulse output control interface are connected to the controller; the fault detection circuit and the signal amplification processing circuit are connected in parallel to a sensor that is a catalysis principle-based sensor; a testing circuit is connected between the signal amplification processing circuit and the controller; and the pulse output control interface is connected to a solenoid valve control circuit. A control external output terminal of the solenoid valve control circuit is connected with an external solenoid valve; and a built-in output terminal of the solenoid valve control circuit is connected with a built-in solenoid valve of a gas meter. The provided combustion gas alarm closing valve device has the advantages of convenient usage, precise measurement, and high reliability.”

JP2010169461A - SYSTEM FOR DETECTING GAS LEAK presents “gas is made to flow to a master-and-slave type differential pressure regulator from a propane gas cylinder 10 through a main regulator A master regulator of the master-and-slave type differential regulator supplies the gas to the apartment house 40 side from the gas supply pipe A slave regulators connected to a bypass gas passage continuous to the gas supply pipe bypassing the master regulator. A microcomputer gas meter is provided for the bypass gas passage. The gas pressure is sampled at a high speed by a pressure sensor of the microcomputer gas meter 3 so as to detect a state of the use of a gas appliance. A flow rate of the gas is detected by the flow sensor of the microcomputer gas meter. When the gas appliance 50 is in the state of the use and a flow rate cannot be detected for a prescribed time, fault alarm processing is performed and the call is given to the processing center.”

CN107809459A - Intelligent meter maintenance payment method based on complex Internet of Things and Internet of Things system presents “an intelligent meter maintenance payment method based on the complex Internet of Things and an Internet of Things system. The Internet of Things system comprises multiple user sub-platforms, multiple service subplatforms, multiple management sub-platforms, a sensor network platform and multiple object sub-platforms, wherein the multiple management sub-platforms comprise multiple management servers of an energy supply company, each of the multiple object sub-platforms comprises intelligent 11 meters, and the intelligent meters comprise at least two of a gas meter, a water meter, an electric meter and a heat meter. According to the intelligent meter maintenance payment method based on the complex Internet of Things, maintenance payment of pipelines, lines and the intelligent meters can be completed in a network payment mode, the management subplatforms can send detection instructions to the intelligent meters during payment and collect the maintenance amount after the intelligent meters detect that faults are removed, and the problem that payment of users is inconvenient is solved.”

JP5203922B2 - A shut-off valve and a gas meter fault detection method presents “A gas flow path of a gas meter disposed in the gas passage at the time of the occurrence of the abnormal event a shut off valve failure detecting method for detecting failure of the shut off valve, The shutoff valve to shut off the gas flow passage between, the gas flow path of the gas flowing in the gas flow, when the gas flow rate is less than a predetermined amount, and the shutoff valve is opened, after imparting vibration to the shutoff valve, the shutoff valve in a state by the gas

flow, and the gas flow rate is detected when the detecting a failure of the shut-off valve The method is characterized in that the failure detection and a shut-off valve.”

CN210376509U - Intelligent gas meter power consumption and voltage detection tool presents “a power consumption and voltage detection tool for an intelligent gas meter. The power consumption and voltage detection tool comprises an ampere meter and a voltmeter, wherein the ampere meter is arranged on a shell and used for testing static power consumption of the gas meter; the left side surface of the shell is provided with a power supply changeover switch used for adjusting a power supply voltage value required by the tested gas meter; an ammeter button used for displaying an ammeter test value, a voltmeter button used for supplying power to a voltmeter, an upper wire clamp jack used for inserting an upper wire clamp and a probe jack used for inserting a voltage detection probe are arranged on the right side face of the shell, the ammeter button is connected with the ammeter in parallel, and the voltmeter button is connected with the voltmeter in series. The gas meter fault detection device is simple in structure and convenient to operate, can independently detect meters with abnormal power consumption in the production process, can perform voltage detection on the meters with abnormal power consumption, can rapidly detect faulty components, and brings great convenience to gas meter fault maintenance personnel to analyze fault problems.”

KR102046035B1 - Apparatus for diagnosing fault of gas meter and gas meter using the same presents “an apparatus for diagnosing a fault of a 13 gas meter comprises: an inlet unit provided with an inlet port into which gas flows and an inlet passage connected to the inlet port; and an outlet unit provided with an outlet port through which gas is discharged and an outlet passage connected to the outlet port. The apparatus comprises a differential pressure detector connected between a first through hole formed in the inlet unit to be connected to the inlet passage and a second through hole formed in the outlet unit to be connected to the outlet passage to detect differential pressure with respect to gas pressure around the inlet passage and the outlet passage. Moreover, through a differential pressure result detected in the differential pressure detector, a fault of a gas meter can be diagnosed”

Groupings of alternative elements or embodiments of the invention disclosed herein are not to be construed as limitations. Each group member can be referred to and claimed individually or in any combination with other members of the group or other elements found herein. One or more members of a group can be included in, or deleted from, a group for reasons of

convenience and/or patentability. When any such inclusion or deletion occurs, the specification is herein deemed to contain the group as modified, thus fulfilling the written description of all Markus groups used in the appended claims.

As used in the description herein and throughout the claims that follow, the meaning of “a,” “an,” and “the” includes plural reference unless the context clearly dictates otherwise. Also, as used in the description herein, the meaning of “in” includes “in” and “on” unless the context clearly dictates otherwise.

The recitation of ranges of values herein is merely intended to serve as a shorthand method of referring individually to each separate value falling within the range. Unless otherwise indicated herein, each individual value is incorporated into the specification as if it were individually recited herein. All methods described herein can be performed in any suitable order unless otherwise indicated herein or otherwise clearly contradicted by context.

The use of any and all examples, or exemplary language (e.g. “Such as”) provided with respect to certain embodiments herein is intended merely to better illuminate the invention and does not pose a limitation on the scope of the invention otherwise claimed. No language in the specification should be construed as indicating any non-claimed element essential to the practice of the invention.

The above information disclosed in this Background section is only for the enhancement of understanding of the background of the invention and therefore it may contain information that does not form the prior art that is already known in this country to a person of ordinary skill in the art.

SUMMARY

Before the present systems and methods, are described, it is to be understood that this application is not limited to the particular systems, and methodologies described, as there can be multiple possible embodiments which are not expressly illustrated in the present disclosure. It is also to be understood that the terminology used in the description is for the purpose of describing the particular versions or embodiments only and is not intended to limit the scope of the present application.

The present invention mainly cures and solves the technical problems existing in the prior art. In response to these problems, the present invention discloses system and method for detection of faults in gas meter using compound internet of things (IoT) sensors.

As one aspect of the present invention presents a system for detection of faults in gas meter using compound internet of things (IoT) 15 sensors, wherein the system characterized in that: An magnetic gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor, the magnetic gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor is electrically conductive gas in the pipeline when the flow of the gas occurred, wherein the internet of things (IoT) sensor is connected to the two electrodes of a signal amplifying unit, wherein the signal 20 amplifying unit 's the output is connected to a signal processing unit, the signal processing unit have a positive and a negative threshold of current excitation of induction potential with the flow of the gas; A vibro-acoustic internet of things (IoT) sensor connectable to a gas path of a pipeline and a center monitoring system, the internet of things (IoT) sensor being operable to measure one or more predetermined vibro-acoustic properties of the gas and/or gas path and communicate data on said measurements to the center monitoring system; and An gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor fault simulation detecting joint, its mounting between the internet of things (IoT) sensor and the connection plug, wherein characterized in that includes: a shell, and the shell about the end of the two ends are respectively provided with an internet of things (IoT) sensor, a connecting plug inserted on the interface, the left end of the said shell at the end of the interface is of a solid structure, wherein the system detect the fault using a the magnetic gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor and the air gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor using method comprising steps of Entering in to operation mode when a period of time is ended or whether the pre-set time period is completed ; Identifying whether or not the measured value of the pressure, temperature & flow rate by internet of things (IoT) sensors exceeds the preset thresholds; and Sending an indicative signal to a display when whether pressure, temperature & flow rate value of the parameters measured by the internet of things (IoT) sensor exceeds the preset threshold.

OBJECTIVE OF THE INVENTION

The principle objective of the present invention is to provide a system and method for detection of faults in gas meter using compound internet of things (IoT) sensors.

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF DRAWINGS

To clarify various aspects of some example embodiments of the present invention, a more particular description of the invention will be rendered by reference to specific embodiments thereof which are illustrated in the appended drawings. It is appreciated that these drawings depict only illustrated embodiments of the invention and are therefore not to be considered

limiting of its scope. The invention will be described and explained with additional specificity and detail through the use of the accompanying drawings.

In order that the advantages of the present invention will be easily understood, a detailed description of the invention is discussed below in conjunction with the appended drawings, which, however, should not be considered to limit the scope of the invention to the accompanying drawings, in which:

Figure 1 shows detail block diagram representation of system and method for detection of faults in gas meter using compound internet of things (IoT) sensors.

DETAIL DESCRIPTION

The present invention is related to system and method for detection of faults in gas meter using compound internet of things (IoT) sensors.

Figure 1 shows detail block diagram representation the system and method for detection of faults in gas meter using compound internet of things (IoT) sensors.

Although the present disclosure has been described with the purpose of system and method for detection of faults in gas meter using compound internet of things (IoT) sensors, it should be appreciated that the same has been done merely to illustrate the invention in an exemplary manner and to highlight any other purpose or function for which explained structures or configurations could be used and is covered within the scope of the present disclosure.

The system comprises a magnetic gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor, a vibro-acoustic internet of things (IoT) sensor and a gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor.

The magnetic gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor is electrically conductive gas in the pipeline when the flow of the gas occurred.

The internet of things (IoT) sensor is connected to the two electrodes of a signal amplifying unit.

The signal amplifying unit 's the output is connected to a signal processing unit, the signal processing unit have a positive and a negative threshold of current excitation of induction potential with the flow of the gas.

The vibro-acoustic internet of things (IoT) sensor is connectable to a gas path of a pipeline and a center monitoring system.

This internet of things (IoT) sensor is being operable to measure one or more predetermined vibro-acoustic properties of the gas and/or gas path and communicate data on said measurements to the center monitoring system.

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

The gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor fault simulation detecting joint is mounted between the internet of things (IoT) sensor and the connection plug.

The magnetic gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor, the vibroacoustic internet of things (IoT) sensor, air gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor in response to input signal and determining one or more faults in the form of internet of things (IoT) sensor and error orientation connection of sensors in one or both from one or more connection.

The system further comprises a float type gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor, peristaltic pump tube monitoring internet of things (IoT) sensor, sampling probe element internet of things (IoT) sensor and a temperature internet of things (IoT) sensor.

The gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor fault simulation detecting joint is characterized in that includes: a shell, and the shell about the end of the two ends are respectively provided with an internet of things (IoT) sensor, a connecting plug inserted on the interface, the left end of the said shell at the end of the interface is of a solid structure.

The gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor comprises a temperature sensor, a pressure sensor, a flow sensor, a current sensor, a voltage sensor and gas level sensor.

The center monitoring system is used to estimate the speed of gas flow propagating through the pipe in dependence on the received data from internet of things (IoT) sensor and on a measure of the pressure along the pipeline that is between the internet of things (IoT) sensor.

The system detects the fault using the magnetic gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor and the air gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor using a method, the method comprising steps of entering in to operation mode when a period of time is ended or whether the pre-set time period is completed, and Identifying whether or not the measured value of the pressure, temperature & flow rate by internet of things (IoT) sensors exceeds the preset thresholds.

An indicative signal is sent to a display when whether pressure, temperature & flow rate value of the parameters measured by the internet of things (IoT) sensor exceeds the preset threshold.

The system further comprises a piezoelectric internet of things (IoT) sensor with the double volume corrector is connected to the center monitoring unit of the system, the center monitoring unit is used to obtain the double-piezoelectric sensor and differential pressure sensor detection data of the gas flow meter fault detection.

The figures and the foregoing description give examples of embodiments. Those skilled in the art will appreciate that one or more of the described elements may well be combined into a single functional element. Alternatively, certain elements may be split into multiple functional elements. Elements from one embodiment may be added to another embodiment. For example, order of processes described herein may be changed and are not limited to the manner described

herein. Moreover, the actions of any flow diagram need not be implemented in the order shown; nor do all of the acts need to be necessarily performed. Also, those acts that are not dependent on other acts may be performed in parallel with the other acts. The scope of embodiments is by no means limited by these specific examples.

Although implementations of the invention have been described in a language specific to structural features and/or methods, it is to be understood that the appended claims are not necessarily limited to the specific features or methods described. Rather, the specific features and methods are disclosed as examples of implementations of the invention.

CLAIMS

We claim:

1. A system for detection of faults in gas meter using compound internet of things (IoT) sensors, wherein the system characterized in that: An magnetic gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor, the magnetic gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor is electrically conductive gas in the pipeline when the flow of the gas occurred, wherein the internet of things (IoT) sensor is connected to the two electrodes of a signal amplifying unit, wherein the signal amplifying unit 's the output is connected to a signal processing unit, the signal processing unit have a positive and a negative threshold of current excitation of induction potential with the flow of the gas;

A vibro-acoustic internet of things (IoT) sensor connectable to a gas path of a pipeline and a center monitoring system, the internet of things (IoT) sensor being operable to measure one or more predetermined vibro-acoustic properties of the gas and/or gas path and communicate data on said measurements to the center monitoring system; and

An gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor fault simulation detecting joint, its mounting between the internet of things (IoT) sensor and the connection plug, wherein characterized in that includes: a shell, and the shell about the end of the two ends are respectively provided with an internet of things (IoT) sensor, a connecting plug inserted on the interface, the left end of the said shell at the end of the interface is of a solid structure, wherein the system detect the fault using a the magnetic gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor and the air gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor using method comprising steps of :

Entering in to operation mode when a period of time is ended or whether the pre-set time period is completed; Identifying whether or not the measured value of the pressure, temperature & flow rate by internet of things (IoT) sensors exceeds the preset thresholds; and Sending an

indicative signal to a display when whether pressure, temperature & flow rate value of the parameters measured by the internet of things (IoT) sensor exceeds the preset threshold.

2. The system for detection of faults in gas meter using compound internet of things (IoT) sensors as claimed in claim 1, wherein the magnetic gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor, the vibroacoustic internet of things (IoT) sensor, air gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor in response to input signal and determining one or more faults in the form of internet of things (IoT) sensor and error orientation connection of sensors in one or both from one or more connection.

3. The system for detection of faults in gas meter using compound internet of things (IoT) sensors as claimed in claim 1, wherein the system further comprises a float type gas meter internet of things 26 (IoT) sensor, peristaltic pump tube monitoring internet of things (IoT) sensor, sampling probe element internet of things (IoT) sensor and a temperature internet of things (IoT) sensor.

4. The system for detection of faults in gas meter using compound internet of things (IoT) sensors as claimed in claim 1, wherein the center monitoring system is used to estimate the speed of gas flow propagating through the pipe in dependence on the received data from internet of things (IoT) sensor and on a measure of the pressure along the pipeline that is between the internet of things (IoT) sensor.

5. The system for detection of faults in gas meter using compound internet of things (IoT) sensors as claimed in claim 1, the system further comprises a piezoelectric internet of things (IoT) sensor with the double volume corrector is connected to the center monitoring unit of the system, the center monitoring unit is used to obtain the double-piezoelectric sensor and differential pressure sensor detection data of the gas flow meter fault detection.

6. The system for detection of faults in gas meter using compound internet of things (IoT) sensors as claimed in claim 1, wherein The gas meter internet of things (IoT) sensor comprises a temperature sensor, a pressure sensor, a flow sensor, a current sensor, a voltage sensor and gas level sensor.

**SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR DETECTION OF FAULTS IN
GAS METER USING COMPOUND INTERNET OF THINGS
(IOT) SENSORS**

ABSTRACT

The present invention relates to system and method for detection of faults in gas meter using compound internet of things (IoT) sensors. The objective of the present invention is to solve the problems in the prior art related to technologies of abnormality and fault detection of gas meter in high industrial operations.

DRAWINGS

Applicants: **Dr. Chinmaya Ranjan Pattanaik & others**

Sheet No. 1 of Total 1

FIGURE 1

Dated 30th Day of March, 2021

Australian Government

IP Australia

CERTIFICATE OF GRANT INNOVATION PATENT

Patent number: 2021102117

The Commissioner of Patents has granted the above patent on 26 May 2021, and certifies that the below particulars have been registered in the Register of Patents.

Name and address of patentee(s):

SK Dhakad of Associate Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, UIT - RGPV -Shivpuri Satarnwada, Madhya Pradesh, India

Mustafa Basthikodi of Professor, Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering, Sahyadri College of Eng. and Management Adyar, Mangalore, Karnataka, India

Vidya Bai G of Associate Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education Manipal, Karnataka, India

Pankaj Agarwal of Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Samrat Ashok Technological Institute Vidisha, Madhya Pradesh, India

Nethravathi P. S of Professor, Dept. of Computer & Information Science, Srinivas University Karnataka, India

Daniel Frank of Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education Manipal, Karnataka, India

Prakash Kumar Udupi of Professor, Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering, Sudeva, Bannanje, Udupi Karnataka, India

Sonia V. Soans of Lecturer, Department of Information Technology, University of Technology and Applied Sciences Muscat, Oman

Sachin Gupta of Professor, Dept. of Computer Science Engineering, School of Engineering and Technology MVN University, Palwal Haryana, India

Krishna Prasad K of Associate Professor, Dept. of Computer & Information Science, Srinivas University Karnataka, India

Bhoomi Gupta of Assistant Professor, Department of Information Technology, Maharaja Agrasen Institute of Technology Rohini, Delhi, India

Babita Yadav of Assistant Professor, Dept. of Computer Science Engineering, School of Engineering and Technology MVN University, Palwal Haryana, India

Pavithra G. of Associate Professor, Dept. of Electronics & Comm. Engineering, Dayananda Sagar College of Engineering Bangalore, Karnataka, India

T.C. Manjunath of Professor & Head of the Dept., Dept. of Electronics & Comm. Engineering, Dayananda Sagar College of Engineering Bangalore, Karnataka, India

Title of invention:

SYSTEM FOR SECURE AUTHENTICATION AND INTER-COMMUNICATION AMONG NETWORKED IOT DEVICES

Dated this 26th day of May 2021

Commissioner of Patents

PATENTS ACT 1990

The Australian Patents Register is the official record and should be referred to for the full details pertaining to the IP Right.

This data, for application number 2021102117, is current as of 2021-07-26 21:00 AEST

Australian Government
IP Australia

CERTIFICATE OF GRANT INNOVATION PATENT

Patent number: 2021102117

Name of inventor(s):

Dhakad, SK; Basthikodi, Mustafa; G, Vidya Bai; Agarwal, Pankaj; P. S, Nethravathi; Frank, Daniel; Udupi, Prakash Kumar; Soans, Sonia V.; Gupta, Sachin; Prasad K, Krishna; Gupta, Bhoomi; Yadav, Babita; G., Pavithra and Manjunath, T.C.

Term of Patent:

Eight years from 21 April 2021

NOTE: This Innovation Patent cannot be enforced unless and until it has been examined by the Commissioner of Patents and a Certificate of Examination has been issued. See sections 120(1A) and 129A of the Patents Act 1990, set out on the reverse of this document.

Dated this 26th day of May 2021

Commissioner of Patents

PATENTS ACT 1990

The Australian Patents Register is the official record and should be referred to for the full details pertaining to this IP Right.

Extracts from the Patents Act, 1990

- Sec 120(1A)** Infringement proceedings in respect of an innovation patent cannot be started unless the patent has been certified.
- Sec 128** **Application for relief from unjustified threats**
- (1) Where a person, by means of circulars, advertisements or otherwise, threatens a person with infringement proceedings or other similar proceedings a person aggrieved may apply to a prescribed court, or to another court having jurisdiction to hear and determine the application, for:
- (a) a declaration that the threats are unjustifiable; and
- (b) an injunction against the continuance of the threats; and
- (c) the recovery of any damages sustained by the applicant as a result of the threats.
- (2) Subsection (1) applies whether or not the person who made the threats is entitled to, or interested in, the patent or a patent application.
- Sec 129A** **Threats related to an innovation patent application or innovation patent and courts power to grant relief.**
- Certain threats of infringement proceedings are always unjustifiable.*
- (1) If:
- (a) a person:
- (i) has applied for an innovation patent, but the application has not been determined; or
- (ii) has an innovation patent that has not been certified; and
- (b) the person, by means of circulars, advertisements or otherwise, threatens a person with infringement proceedings or other similar proceedings in respect of the patent applied for, or the patent, as the case may be; then, for the purposes of an application for relief under section 128 by the person threatened, the threats are unjustifiable.
- Courts power to grant relief in respect of threats made by the applicant for an innovation patent or the patentee of an uncertified innovation patent*
- (2) If an application under section 128 for relief relates to threats made in respect of an innovation patent that has not been certified or an application for an innovation patent, the court may grant the application the relief applied for.
- Courts power to grant relief in respect of threats made by the patentee of certified innovation patent*
- (3) If an application under section 128 for relief relates to threats made in respect of a certified innovation patent, the court may grant the applicant the relief applied for unless the respondent satisfies the court that the acts about which the threats were made infringed, or would infringe, a claim that is not shown by the applicant to be invalid.
- Schedule 1** **Dictionary**
- certified**, in respect of an innovation patent other than in section 19, means a certificate of examination issued by the Commissioner under paragraph 101E(e) in respect of the patent

SYSTEM FOR SECURE AUTHENTICATION AND INTER-COMMUNICATION AMONG NETWORKED IOT DEVICES

ABSTRACT

The present invention relates to System for secure authentication and intercommunication among networked IOT devices. The objective of the present invention is to solve the problems in the prior art related to adequacies in technologies of secure interconnection of the internet of things device connected in a network.

SYSTEM FOR SECURE AUTHENTICATION AND INTER-COMMUNICATION AMONG NETWORKED IOT DEVICES

FIELD OF INVENTION

[001]. The present invention relates to the technical field of internet of things devices.

[002]. The present invention relates to the technical field of intercommunication of internet of things devices.

[003]. More particularly, the present invention is related to system for secure authentication and inter-communication among networked IOT devices.

BACKGROUND & PRIOR ART

[004]. The subject matter discussed in the background section should not be assumed to be prior art merely as a result of its mention in the background section. Similarly, a problem mentioned in the background section or associated with the subject matter of the background section should not be assumed to have been previously recognized in the prior art. The subject matter in the background section merely represents different approaches, which in-and-of-themselves may also be inventions.

[005]. Internet of Things (IoT) technology refers to a wide range of devices. Since IoT technology has nearly limitless applications that can be leveraged to form new and useful services, interest among service providers and developers in IoT technology continues to increase. However, service providers and developers are always mindful of security issues, and the access of an IoT device to a network, as well as its impact on network resources in the network.

[006]. IoT devices have become widespread and their uses have continued to expand. While the expansion of IoT devices offers various benefits, security issues are always present. For example, typically, an IoT device communicates with an access network (e.g., a base station or other type of wireless node) to initially establish a connection to a network device in a network. By way of further example, the IoT device transmits a radio resource control (RRC) request message, which carries an International Mobile Equipment Identity

(IMEI) or a Mobile Directory Number (MDN) of the IoT device, to the base station. The RRC request message is in a plain text format and subject to security vulnerabilities (e.g., spoofing, etc.). Also, the ability of the network to detect a security breach, which may occur subsequent to attachment, only occurs after a certain amount of data has been communicated by or to the IoT device.

[007]. Also, many IoT devices are “disposable devices,” which may not belong to its final users. For example, smart meters installed on residential properties are owned by the water company and not the owners of the residences. A user (e.g., a business user, etc.) may need to enable or dispatch a batch of IoT devices in a geographic area, which can require a change in core network elements (e.g., configuration, provisioning of subscription data, etc.). For example, there may be changes needed in a database (e.g., a home subscriber server (HSS), an equipment identity register (EIR), etc.) and other network elements (e.g., a mobility management entity (MME), a gateway device, etc.). However, the network service provider may not wish to grant the user access to these network elements because of the consequences (e.g., service down time, etc.) stemming from a mistake (e.g., a misconfiguration by the user, a data entry error, etc.) that may occur due to the access. Thus, the network service provider may be forced to allocate resources (e.g., personnel, network infrastructure, etc.) to configure the network elements on behalf of the user. Further, the network service provider may not wish to grant generic data access to the IoT devices.

[008]. . Some of the work listed herewith:

[009]. AU2020102441A4 - Secure communication among Iota Devices through IoT Coin Operation System Presents “A system for initiating a connection session, the system comprising: a sensor array; a gesture detection circuit communicatively coupled to the sensor array, the gesture detection circuit to: detect an air gesture performed by a user of the system based on data from the sensor array; and determine a classification of the air gesture; and a transceiver to transmit a signal to a receiver associated with a receiver device, to initiate a connection between the system and the receiver device, when the air gesture is recognized as a triggering gesture to initiate the connection”

[0010]. CN112019552A - Internet of Things secure communication method presents “method is characterized in that the Internet of Things system comprises an authentication cloud

platform. A plurality of business cloudplatforms and a plurality of equipment terminals, the business cloud platform remote connection the authentication cloud platform, the equipment terminal remote connection corresponds the business cloud platform, the safe communication method includes: the security communication method includes: Step S1: The authentication cloud platform generates first keys, the first key comprises first public keys andfirst private keys, and the authentication cloud platform transmits the firstpublic key to the equipment terminal through the service cloud platform. Step S2: The service cloud platform generates second keys, the second keys comprise second public keys and second private keys, and the service cloud platform sends the second public keys to the authentication cloud platform”

[0011]. CN111669407A - Internet of Things point-to-point secure communication implementation method based on cloud security authentication present “an internet of things point-to-point safe communication realization method based on cloud security authentication,which is characterized by comprising the following steps. The invention discloses a security communication hardware module which comprises a cloud communication module, a data processing module and a near field communication module. The cloud communication module is directly connected with a communication module of the internet through the cloudcommunication module. The data processing module is provided with a data processing and control cloud communication module capability module, and is used for controlling the cloud communication module to transmit and receive data and processing the received data. The near-field communication module is a short-distance transmission communication module to realize short-distance communication between the Internet of things terminal.”

[0012]. CN110430171A - Secure Internet of things communication protocol presents a secure internet of things communication protocol. The secure Internet of Things communication protocol comprises an information receiving unit, an equipment management center, an equipment connection center and a main body permission management system. The output end of the information receiving unit is connected with the input end of the equipment management center. The output end of the equipment management center is connected with the input end of the equipment connection center. The output end of the equipment connection center is connected with the input end of the main permission management system,and the input end of the information receiving unit is connected with the output

end of the HTTPS server. The invention discloses a secure Internet of Things communication protocol. According to the technical scheme, the safety of the Internet of Things communication protocol during working can be ensured. The safety degree of the Internet of Things communication protocol is greatly improved. The protection performance is good. The loss of a user caused by potential safety hazards of the Internet of Things communication protocol is avoided. The normal use of the user is ensured. The practicability is high, and the comprehensive information support can be provided.”

[0013]. US20210006583A1 - SYSTEM AND METHOD OF SECURE COMMUNICATION WITH INTERNET OF THINGS DEVICES presents Systems and methods of vulnerability detection for at least one internet of things (IoT) device in a computer network, including monitoring communication in the computer network to detect at least one IoT device, determining type and behavior of the detected at least one IoT device, checking in at least one vulnerability database in communication with the computer network, for a device profile corresponding to the type of the detected at least one IoT device, and blocking communication between the at least one IoT device and the computer network if the determined behavior of the at least one IoT device violates at least one predetermined rule for the corresponding device profile.

[0014]. US10153908B2 - Secure communication of IOT devices for vehicles presents “Method for establishing secure communication between a plurality of IoT devices in one or more vehicles include: provisioning the plurality of IoT devices by providing a unique identification, a digital identity token and a cryptographic key to each of the plurality of IoT devices; establishing a secure communication line between the plurality of IoT devices by authenticating respective communication lines between respective IoT devices and issuing a digital certificate to the respective communication lines; grouping the plurality of IoT devices into different groups based on a predetermined criteria; and including a group membership for a group of the different groups in an attribute certificate indicating group characterization.”.

[0015]. Groupings of alternative elements or embodiments of the invention disclosed herein are not to be construed as limitations. Each group member can be referred to and claimed individually or in any combination with other members of the group or other elements found herein. One or more members of a group can be included in, or deleted from, a group for

reasons of convenience and/or patentability. When any such inclusion or deletion occurs, the specification is herein deemed to contain the group as modified, thus fulfilling the written description of all Markus groups used in the appended claims.

[0016]. As used in the description herein and throughout the claims that follow, the meaning of “a,” “an,” and “the” includes plural reference unless the context clearly dictates otherwise. Also, as used in the description herein, the meaning of “in” includes “in” and “onTM unless the context clear dictates otherwise.

[0017]. The recitation of ranges of values herein is merely intended to serve as a shorthand method of referring individually to each separate value falling within the range. Unless otherwise indicated herein, each individual value is incorporated into the specification as if it were individually recited herein. All methods described herein can be performed in any suitable order unless otherwise indicated herein or otherwise clearly contradicted by context.

[0018]. The use of any and all examples, or exemplary language (e.g. “as”) provided with respect to certain embodiments herein is intended merely to better illuminate the invention and does not pose a limitation on the scope of the invention otherwise claimed. No language in the specification should be construed as indicating any non-claimed element essential to the practice of the invention.

[0019]. The above information disclosed in this Background section is only for the enhancement of understanding of the background of the invention and therefore it may contain information that does not form the prior art that is already known in this country to a person of ordinary skill in the art.

SUMMARY

[0020]. Before the present systems and methods, are described, it is to be understood that this application is not limited to the particular systems, and methodologies described, as there can be multiple possible embodiments which are not expressly illustrated in the present disclosure. It is also to be understood that the terminology used in the description is for the purpose of describing the particular versions or embodiments only and is not intended to limit the scope of the present application.

[0021]. The present invention mainly cures and solves the technical problems existing in the prior art. In response to these problems, the present invention discloses a System for secure authentication and inter-communication among networked IOT devices.

[0022]. As an aspect of the present invention, it presents a system for secure authentication and inter-communication among networked IOT devices, wherein system perform a method, wherein the method comprising: storing, by an Internet of Things (IoT) device, a hardware identifier that uniquely identifies the IoT device; performing, by the IoT device, an attachment procedure with a wireless network, wherein the attachment procedure includes authenticating the IoT device and establishing a bearer connection with a first network device of a core network of the wireless network; establishing, by the IoT device, a secure channel via the bearer connection with an authentication device, in response to successfully completing the attachment procedure, wherein the IoT device is route-restricted to the authentication device subsequent to completing the attachment procedure; transmitting, by the IoT device via the secure channel to the authentication device, a first request to authenticate the IoT device, wherein the first request includes the hardware identifier; receiving, by the IoT device via the secure channel from the authentication device, a first response that indicates whether the IoT device is authenticated; determining, by the IoT device, whether the IoT device is authenticated based on the first response; and transmitting, by the IoT device via the secure channel to the authentication device, a second request for a key in response to determining that the IoT device is authenticated.

OBJECTIVE OF THE INVENTION

[0023]. The principle objective of the present invention is to provide a System for secure authentication and inter-communication among networked IOT devices.

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF DRAWINGS

[0024]. To clarify various aspects of some example embodiments of the present invention, a more particular description of the invention will be rendered by reference to specific embodiments thereof which are illustrated in the appended drawings. It is appreciated that these drawings depict only illustrated embodiments of the invention and are therefore not to be considered limiting of its scope. The invention will be described and explained with additional specificity and detail through the use of the accompanying

drawings.

[0025]. In order that the advantages of the present invention will be easily understood, a detailed description of the invention is discussed below in conjunction with the appended drawings, which, however, should not be considered to limit the scope of the invention to the accompanying drawings, in which:

[0026]. Figure 1 shows a flow diagram representation of method for system for secure authentication and inter-communication among networked IOT devices., according to one of the embodiment of the present invention.

DETAIL DESCRIPTION

[0027]. The present invention is related to System for secure authentication and inter-communication among networked IOT devices

[0028]. Figure 1 shows a flow diagram representation of method for system for secure authentication and inter-communication among networked IOT devices., according to one of the embodiment of the present invention.

[0029]. Although the present disclosure has been described with the purpose of System for secure authentication and inter-communication among networked IOT devices, it should be appreciated that the same has been done merely to illustrate the invention in an exemplary manner and to highlight any other purpose or function for which explained structures or configurations could be used and is covered within the scope of the present disclosure.

[0030]. Some embodiments of this disclosure, illustrating all its features, will now be discussed in detail. The words and other forms thereof, are intended to be open ended in that an item or items following any one of these words are not meant to be an exhaustive listing of such item or items, or meant to be limited to only the listed item or items. It must also be noted that as used herein and in the appended claims, the singular forms "a," "an," and "the" include plural references unless the context clearly dictates otherwise. Although any systems and methods similar or equivalent to those described herein can be used in the

practice or testing of embodiments of the present disclosure, the exemplary systems and methods are now described. The disclosed embodiments are merely exemplary of the disclosure, which may be embodied in various forms.

[0031]. The system for secure authentication and inter-communication among networked IOT devices is disclosed in this present invention.

[0032]. A method, a device, and a non-transitory storage medium are provided to store a hardware identifier that uniquely identifies an IoT device; perform an attachment procedure with a wireless network, wherein the attachment procedure includes authenticating the IoT device by the wireless network and establishing a bearer connection; establish a secure channel with an authentication device via the bearer connection, in response to successfully completing the attachment procedure; transmit, to the authentication device, a first request to authenticate the IoT device, wherein the first request includes the hardware identifier; receive, from the authentication device, a first response that indicates whether the IoT device is authenticated; and determine that the IoT device is authenticated based on the first response.

[0033]. According to exemplary embodiments, an authentication service is provided. According to an exemplary embodiment, the authentication service provides authentication to IoT devices. According to an exemplary embodiment, the authentication service is provided subsequent to the attachment of the IoT device with a network (e.g., an access network, a core network), but before the IoT device is able to communicate with an external network. According to an exemplary embodiment, the authentication service authenticates the IoT device based on a hardware identifier that uniquely identifies the IoT device. According to an exemplary embodiment, when the authenticator service determines that the hardware identifier is not valid, the authentication service may invoke a detachment procedure. As a result, the authentication service may detect a security breach, subsequent to attachment and before any amount of data has been communicated by or to the IoT device via the attached network. According to an exemplary embodiment, the hardware identifier may be communicated by the IoT device to the authentication service via a secure channel such that any security risk of tampering (e.g., data integrity issue of the hardware identifier, etc.) may be minimized.

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

[0034]. Although implementations of the invention have been described in a language specific to structural features and/or methods, it is to be understood that the appended claims are not necessarily limited to the specific features or methods described. Rather, the specific features and methods are disclosed as examples of implementations of the invention.

DRAWINGS

Applicants: Dr. SK Dhakad & Other

FIGURE 1

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

Australian Government

IP Australia

CERTIFICATE OF GRANT INNOVATION PATENT

Patent number: 2021102149

The Commissioner of Patents has granted the above patent on 2 June 2021, and certifies that the below particulars have been registered in the Register of Patents.

Name and address of patentee(s):

N P Kavya of Professor & HoD, Department of AIML Engineering, RNS Institute of Technology Dr. Vishnuvardhan Road , Channasandra, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India

K. E. Prakash of Principal & Director, Shree Devi Institute of Technology, Airport Road, Kenjar, Mangalore DK District, Karnataka India

Dilip Kumar K of Principal and Director, K S Institute of Technology, Raghuvanahalli, Kanakapura Road Bengaluru India

Nethravathi P. S. of Professor, Dept. of Computer & Information Science, Srinivas University Mangalore, Karnataka India

Mamatha Balipa of Associate Professor, Department of MCA, NMAM Institute of Technology Nitte, Karkala Taluk Udupi District, Karnataka India

Mangala Shetty of Assistant Professor, Department of Master of Computer Applica, NMAM Institute of Technology Nitte, Karnataka India

Spoorthi B Shetty of Assistant Professor, Department of Master of Computer Applica, NMAM Institute of Technology, Nitte Karnataka India

Pallavi Shetty of Associate Professor, Department of MCA, NMAMIT, Nitte, Karkala Talk Udupi District, Karnataka India

Chetana Prakash of Professor, Dept. of Computer Science & Engineering, Bapuji Inst. of Engineering & Technology Shamnur road, Davangere Karnataka India

Pushparaj Nayak of Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education Manipal, Karnataka India

Sheetal A of Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education Manipal, Karnataka India

Krishna Prasad of Associate Professor, Dept. of Computer & Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore Karnataka India

Title of invention:

SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR ANALYZING TRANSACTION DATA IN CRYPTOCURRENCY TRADING USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE MODEL

Name of inventor(s):

Kavya, N. P.; Prakash, K. E.; Kumar K., Dilip; P. S., Nethravathi; Balipa, Mamatha; Shetty, Mangala; Shetty, Spoorthi B.; Shetty, Pallavi; Prakash, Chetana; Nayak, Pushparaj; A., Sheetal and Prasad, Krishna

Dated this 2nd day of June 2021

Commissioner of Patents

PATENTS ACT 1990

The Australian Patents Register is the official record and should be referred to for the full details pertaining to the IP Right.

This data, for application number 2021102149, is current as of 2021-07-26 21:00 AEST

Australian Government

IP Australia

CERTIFICATE OF GRANT INNOVATION PATENT

Patent number: 2021102149

Term of Patent:

Eight years from 22 April 2021

NOTE: This Innovation Patent cannot be enforced unless and until it has been examined by the Commissioner of Patents and a Certificate of Examination has been issued. See sections 120(1A) and 129A of the Patents Act 1990, set out on the reverse of this document.

Dated this 2nd day of June 2021

Commissioner of Patents

PATENTS ACT 1990

The Australian Patents Register is the official record and should be referred to for the full details pertaining to this IP Right.

Extracts from the Patents Act, 1990

- Sec 120(1A)** Infringement proceedings in respect of an innovation patent cannot be started unless the patent has been certified.
- Sec 128** **Application for relief from unjustified threats**
- (1) Where a person, by means of circulars, advertisements or otherwise, threatens a person with infringement proceedings or other similar proceedings a person aggrieved may apply to a prescribed court, or to another court having jurisdiction to hear and determine the application, for:
- (a) a declaration that the threats are unjustifiable; and
- (b) an injunction against the continuance of the threats; and
- (c) the recovery of any damages sustained by the applicant as a result of the threats.
- (2) Subsection (1) applies whether or not the person who made the threats is entitled to, or interested in, the patent or a patent application.
- Sec 129A** **Threats related to an innovation patent application or innovation patent and courts power to grant relief.**
- Certain threats of infringement proceedings are always unjustifiable.*
- (1) If:
- (a) a person:
- (i) has applied for an innovation patent, but the application has not been determined; or
- (ii) has an innovation patent that has not been certified; and
- (b) the person, by means of circulars, advertisements or otherwise, threatens a person with infringement proceedings or other similar proceedings in respect of the patent applied for, or the patent, as the case may be; then, for the purposes of an application for relief under section 128 by the person threatened, the threats are unjustifiable.
- Courts power to grant relief in respect of threats made by the applicant for an innovation patent or the patentee of an uncertified innovation patent*
- (2) If an application under section 128 for relief relates to threats made in respect of an innovation patent that has not been certified or an application for an innovation patent, the court may grant the application the relief applied for.
- Courts power to grant relief in respect of threats made by the patentee of certified innovation patent*
- (3) If an application under section 128 for relief relates to threats made in respect of a certified innovation patent, the court may grant the applicant the relief applied for unless the respondent satisfies the court that the acts about which the threats were made infringed, or would infringe, a claim that is not shown by the applicant to be invalid.
- Schedule 1** **Dictionary**
- certified**, in respect of an innovation patent other than in section 19, means a certificate of examination issued by the Commissioner under paragraph 101E(e) in respect of the patent

**SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR ANALYZING TRANSACTION
DATA IN CRYPTOCURRENCY TRADING USING
ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE MODEL**

ABSTRACT

The present invention relates to System and method for analyzing transaction data in cryptocurrency trading using artificial intelligence model. The objective of the present invention is to solve the problems in the prior art related to adequacies in technologies of secure transaction of cryptocurrency trading using artificial intelligence.

SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR ANALYZING TRANSACTION DATA IN CRYPTOCURRENCY TRADING USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE MODEL

FIELD OF INVENTION

[001]. The present invention relates to the technical field of digital systems and methods for exchanging value such as, for example, cryptocurrency systems.

[002]. The present invention relates to the technical field a method, as a computer program for an encrypted account transaction of digital currency using artificial intelligence.

[003]. More particularly, the present invention is related to system and method for analyzing transaction data in cryptocurrency trading using artificial intelligence model.

BACKGROUND & PRIOR ART

[004]. The subject matter discussed in the background section should not be assumed to be prior art merely as a result of its mention in the background section. Similarly, a problem mentioned in the background section or associated with the subject matter of the background section should not be assumed to have been previously recognized in the prior art. The subject matter in the background section merely represents different approaches, which in-and-of-themselves may also be inventions.

[005]. Cryptocurrency are a relatively new market and are generally associated with high volatility, profit, and risk, as well as limited historical data. As with many nascent markets, many cryptocurrency investors rushed into the market without adequate knowledge and experience in either trading or cryptocurrencies. In fact, many of the cryptocurrency investors were trapped by short-term market movement and lost money quickly.

[006]. Further, unlike many other markets, cryptocurrencies trade 24/7, thereby requiring traders to make decisions at all times throughout the day. As such, in order to make the most-

informed decision possible, the traders are also required to monitor information from a variety of sources.

[007]. For example, a cryptocurrency's market price may be influenced by reported news (e.g., regulatory news, news about exchanges, stock market performance news, etc.), rumors, discussions, influencer's opinions on social media (e.g., Twitter, Reddit, YouTube, Telegram, etc.), and special events such as initial coin offerings (ICOs).

[008]. Further, the informed investor would also need to know about the block chain technology behind the coins or tokens as well as their intended use cases, roadmap, and progress. However, it would be impossible for human traders to track all of the above-mentioned cryptocurrency-related data and respond to that data in real time. Further, it would also be difficult to verify the credibility of the cryptocurrency-related information in real time. In particular, it is difficult to verify the credibility of speculation, rumors, opinions, and other information posted on social media and elsewhere.

[009]. Accordingly, there is a need for a centralized platform that analyzes speculation, news, and other cryptocurrency-related information as well as provides a recommendation and/or implements the provided recommendation.

[0010]. Some of the work listed herewith:

[0011]. KR102215034B1 - SYSTEM FOR INTEGRATED MEDIATION AND TRANSACTION OF CRYPTOCURRENCY BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE presents "an artificial intelligence based encryption money integrated mediation transaction system. a system and a method for providing various payment services and additional services through an API are provided to enable a user to perform a real-time agent transaction through an encryption money or a national currency by providing a user with separate time information and real-time transaction information of each encryption money exchange place by using an API provided in each transaction station, thereby enabling a user to perform a real-time agency transaction through encryption or national currency."

[0012]. US10902320B2 - Architectures, systems and methods for program defined transaction system and decentralized cryptocurrency system distributed ledger. First, the system includes an application plane layer adapted to receive instructions regarding operation of the transaction statesystem. Preferably, the application plane layer is coupled to the applicationplane layer interface. Second, a control plane layer is provided,

[0013]. The control plane layer including an adaptive control unit, such as a cognitive computing unit, artificial intelligence unit or machine-learning unit. Third, a data plane layer includes an input interface to receive data input from one or more data sources and to provide output coupled to a decentralized distributed ledger, the data plane layer is coupled to the control plane layer. Optionally the decentralized distributed ledger stores data on cryptocurrency.”

[0014]. KR102112798B1 - METHOD, APPARATUS AND COMPUTER PROGRAM FOR CLUSTERING CRYPTOCURRENCY ACCOUNTS ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE presents “a method for clustering cryptocurrency accounts using artificial intelligence, a device thereof and a computer program thereof. According to various embodiments of the present invention, the method for clustering cryptocurrency accounts using artificial intelligence, in a method performed by a computing device, comprises the steps of: collecting cryptocurrency transaction information generated among a plurality of cryptocurrency accounts; generating a clustering rule clustering the plurality of cryptocurrency accounts by using the cryptocurrency transaction information; and clustering the plurality of cryptocurrency accounts by using the generated clustering rule”

[0015]. KR102113347B1 - METHOD, APPARATUS AND COMPUTER PROGRAM FOR CLASSIFYING CRYPTOCURRENCY ACCOUNTS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE Presents “a method, device, and computer program for classifying cryptocurrency accounts using artificialintelligence. According to various embodiments of the present invention,the method performed by a computer device comprises the steps of: collecting information on cryptocurrency transaction occurred between a plurality of cryptocurrency accounts;

[0016]. Visualizing the collected information on the cryptocurrency transaction; analyzing

the visualized information on the cryptocurrency transaction; and determining an attribute of each of the plurality of cryptocurrency accounts based on an analysis result of the visualized information on the cryptocurrency transaction”

[0017]. KR102142524B1 - METHOD, APPARATUS AND COMPUTER PROGRAM FOR FORECASTING CRYPTOCURRENCY COST VARIABILITY USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE Presents “a method, device, and computer program for forecasting price variability of cryptocurrency using artificial intelligence. According to various embodiments of the present invention, the method may comprise the steps of: determining use of each of the plurality of cryptocurrency account by using information on cryptocurrency transaction occurred between the plurality of cryptocurrency accounts; collecting information related to the cryptocurrency for each of the plurality of cryptocurrency accounts that the use is determined; and forecasting price variability of the cryptocurrency by

[0018]. KR102096654B1 - Apparatus and method for approving instant deposit of cryptocurrency presents “a device for approving an immediate deposit of a cryptocurrency exchange using a dynamic fee, and a method thereof. The device for approving an immediate deposit of a cryptocurrency

[0019]. Exchange comprises: a rejection probability prediction module including an artificial intelligence program code which predicts a rejection probability of an exchange deposit transaction based on transaction information of the exchange deposit transaction to generate rejection probability information; a dynamic fee calculation module generating an immediate deposit fee which is an expected loss which is dynamically calculated based on the rejection probability information generated by the rejection probability prediction module; and a deposit approval module determining whether a deposit for the exchange deposit transaction is approved based on approval of a user account for the immediate deposit fee.

[0020]. US20190197635A1 - Eleutheria (Freedom), Digital Cryptocurrency for Virtual Electricity Trading Platform digital cryptocurrency named Eleutheria, throughout this patent that can be used within a virtual electricity trading platform to virtually transact real and digital currencies, smart contracts, financial derivatives, and electricity based on

Distributed Electricity Generation (“DG”) plants using Distributed

[0021]. Energy Resources (“DERs”) and Energy Storage Systems (“ESS”) by utilizing new technologies including Internet of Things (IoT). Information and Communication Technology (ICT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Smart Grid. Eleutheria, is composed of four basic and two derivative cryptocurrencies: (i) y 1 (k.t) Cryptocurrency..te. transact “Currency Exchange” in a designated country and time: (ii) y 2 (k.t) Cryptocurrency to transact “Smart Contracts” in a designated country and time: (iii) y 3 (k.t)-Cryptocurrency to transact “Financial Derivatives” in a designated country and time ; (iv) 4 (k.t)«Cryptocurrency to transact “Electricity” in a designated country and time; (v) y own (k,t) Cryptocurrency to transact “Ownership of DG plants” in a designated country and time:”

[0022]. US20200410480A1- METHOD AND SYSTEM FOR PREDICTING CRYPTOCURRENCY PRICE USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE presents “method and system for predicting a cryptocurrency price using artificial intelligence. The cryptocurrency price prediction method includes the steps of: receiving information on each cryptocurrency from a cryptocurrency exchange server through an API and extracting a plurality of price data, by a data extraction unit; processing and storing the extracted price data in a storage unit, by a data refinement unit; creating a dataset configured of a mean and a standard deviation of each cryptocurrency, by a dataset construction unit; and creating a model using a dataset read function of each cryptocurrency, by a modeling unit.”

[0023]. | KR102096659B1 - Apparatus and method for approving deposit of cryptocurrency presents “an apparatus for approving a deposit of cryptocurrency, using artificial intelligence (AI) to increase a deposit approval speed and a method thereof, To this end, according to the present invention, the apparatus comprises: a transaction collection module receiving transaction information of an exchange deposit transaction,

[0024]. Which is a transaction for transferring predetermined cryptocurrency to an exchange account from a user account from a connection node which is at least one of a plurality of nodes forming a distributed network of the predetermined blockchain, wherein the exchange account is an account of an exchange in a predetermined blockchain and the user

account is an account of a user in the predetermined blockchain; a rejection possibility prediction module including an artificial intelligence program code for predicting a rejection possibility of the exchange deposit transaction based on the transaction information of the exchange deposit transaction to generate rejection possibility information; and a deposit approval module determining whether to approve a deposit of the exchange deposit transaction based on the rejection possibility information.”

[0025]. KR102180192B1 - Method for buying and selling a crypto currencybased on artificial intelligence, and Terminal device performing the method Presents “method for selling a cryptocurrency and a method for buying a cryptocurrency based on artificial intelligence and a terminal deviceperforming the same which efficiently buy and sell a cryptocurrency. The terminal device buys and sells a cryptocurrency based on artificial intelligence. The terminal device comprises: a memory to store commandsreadable by a computer; and a processor realized to execute the commands. The processor uses at least one between a moving average line for specifictime zones calculated by using previous market price information of the cryptocurrency and an emotion of a cryptocurrency-related posting posedon SNS to determine whether to buy the cryptocurrency and uses a profitrate of the cryptocurrency if buying the cryptocurrency, a standard deviation of a closing price of the cryptocurrency in a preset time zone calculated by using the previous market price information of the cryptocurrency, and a slope in accordance with a current price of the cryptocurrency and a predicted closing price of the next day of the cryptocurrency to determine whether to sell the cryptocurrency.”

[0026]. Groupings of alternative elements or embodiments of the inventiondisclosed herein are not to be construed as limitations. Each group membercan be referred to and claimed individually or in any combination with other members of the group or other elements found herein. One or more membersof a group can be included in, or deleted from, a group for reasons of convenience and/or patentability. When any such inclusion or deletion occurs, the specification is herein deemed to contain the group as modified, thus fulfilling the written description of all Markus groups used in the appended claims.

[0027]. Ag.used in the description herein and throughout the claims that follow, the meaning of “a,” “an,” and “the” includes plural reference unless the context clearly dictates otherwise. Also, as used in the description herein, the meaning of “in” includes “in” and “on” unlessg the context clearly dictates otherwise.

[0028]. The recitation of ranges of values herein is merely intended to serve as a shorthand method of referring individually to each separate value falling within the range. Unless otherwise indicated herein, each individual value is incorporated into the specification as if it were individually recited herein. All methods described herein can be performed in any suitable order unless otherwise indicated herein or otherwise clearly contradicted by context.

[0029]. The use of any and all examples, or exemplary language (e.g. “Such as”) provided with respect to certain embodiments herein is intended merely to better illuminate the invention and does not pose a limitation on the scope of the invention otherwise claimed. No language in the specification should be construed as indicating any non-claimed element essential to the practice of the invention.

[0030]. The above information disclosed in this Background section is only for the enhancement of understanding of the background of the invention and therefore it may contain information that does not form the prior art that is already known in this country to a person of ordinary skill in the art.

SUMMARY

[0031]. Before the present systems and methods, are described, it is to be understood that this application is not limited to the particular systems, and methodologies described, as there can be multiple possible embodiments which are not expressly illustrated in the present disclosure. It is also to be understood that the terminology used in the description is for the purpose of describing the particular versions or embodiments only and is not intended to limit the scope of the present application.

[0032]. The present invention mainly cures and solves the technical problems existing in the prior art. In response to these problems, the present invention discloses a System and method for analyzing transaction data in cryptocurrency trading using artificial intelligence model.

[0033]. As an aspect of the present invention, it presents a system for analyzing transaction data in cryptocurrency trading using artificial intelligence model, wherein the system

comprises: an Input cryptocurrency module, in the form of structured or unstructured cryptocurrency; a cryptocurrency analyzer to parse the input cryptocurrency and identify the classes and subclasses from cryptocurrency; a cryptocurrency identifier, is a collection class cryptocurrency sets and sub-class cryptocurrency sets which are used to classify the transaction data related to the input cryptocurrency; a processing unit, used computing methods like artificial intelligence, artificial intelligence to classify and predict the class and sub-class cryptocurrency with respect to identified transaction data which determine the deep analysis view the cryptocurrency and to generate classified cryptocurrency sets and such processed class and sub-class cryptocurrency sets are stored in the cryptocurrency identifier, used as a utilized as training cryptocurrency sets for artificial intelligence models; and a cryptocurrency center control unit, used to monitor the classified cryptocurrency and facilitates cryptocurrency cleaning; wherein wherein the processing unit is configured to: access a distributed ledger comprising a plurality of cryptocurrency (cryptocurrency corresponding to a plurality of cryptocurrency assets, wherein the plurality of cryptocurrency assets comprises an aggregate stack of cryptocurrency; Assigning the plurality of cryptocurrency cryptocurrency; interpret a distributed ledger operation corresponding to at least one of the plurality of cryptocurrency assets; determining an analytic result value in response to the distributed ledger operation and the tokenized plurality of cryptocurrency cryptocurrency, wherein the analytic result value comprises statistical information corresponding to: access events for the at least one of the plurality of cryptocurrency assets; and an output device, used to display and enable access to the classified cryptocurrency to the user.

OBJECTIVE OF THE INVENTION

[0034]. The principle objective of the present invention is to provide a System and method for analyzing transaction data in cryptocurrency trading using artificial intelligence model.

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF DRAWINGS

[0035]. To clarify various aspects of some example embodiments of the present invention, a more particular description of the invention will be rendered by reference to specific embodiments thereof which are illustrated in the appended drawings. It is appreciated that these drawings depict only illustrated embodiments of the invention and are therefore not to be considered limiting of its scope. The invention will be described and explained

with additional specificity and detail through the use of the accompanying drawings.

[0036]. In order that the advantages of the present invention will be easily understood, a detailed description of the invention is discussed below in conjunction with the appended drawings, which, however, should not be considered to limit the scope of the invention to the accompanying drawings, in which:

[0037]. Figure 1 shows a flow diagram representation of method for system and method for analyzing transaction data in cryptocurrency trading using artificial intelligence model., according to one of the embodiment of the present invention.

DETAIL DESCRIPTION

[0038]. The present invention is related to System and method for analyzing transaction data in cryptocurrency trading using artificial intelligence model

[0039]. Figure 1 shows a flow diagram representation of method for system and method for analyzing transaction data in cryptocurrency trading using artificial intelligence model., according to one of the embodiment of the present invention.

[0040]. Although the present disclosure has been described with the purpose of System and method for analyzing transaction data in cryptocurrency trading using artificial intelligence model, it should be appreciated that the same has been done merely to illustrate the invention in an exemplary manner and to highlight any other purpose or function for which explained structures or configurations could be used and is covered within the scope of the present disclosure.

[0041]. Some embodiments of this disclosure, illustrating all its features, will now be discussed in detail. The words and other forms thereof, are intended to be open ended in that an item or items following any one of these words are not meant to be an exhaustive listing of such item or items, or meant to be limited to only the listed item or items. It must also be noted that as used herein and in the appended claims, the singular forms "a," "an," and "the" include plural references unless the context clearly dictates otherwise. Although any systems and methods similar or equivalent to those described herein can be used in the

practice or testing of embodiments of the present disclosure, the exemplary systems and methods are now described. The disclosed embodiments are merely exemplary of the disclosure, which may be embodied in various forms.

[0042]. A system for analyzing transaction data in cryptocurrency trading using artificial intelligence model, comprises an input cryptocurrency module, a cryptocurrency analyzer, a cryptocurrency identifier, a processing unit, a cryptocurrency center control unit and an output device.

[0043]. The Input cryptocurrency module is presented in the form of structured or unstructured cryptocurrency.

[0044]. The cryptocurrency analyzer is used to parse the input cryptocurrency and identify the classes and subclasses from cryptocurrency.

[0045]. The cryptocurrency identifier is a collection class cryptocurrency sets and sub-class cryptocurrency sets which are used to classify the transaction data related to the input cryptocurrency.

[0046]. The processing unit is used computing methods like artificial intelligence, artificial intelligence to classify and predict the class and sub-class cryptocurrency with respect to identified transaction data which determine the deep analysis view the cryptocurrency and to generate classified cryptocurrency sets and such processed class and sub-class cryptocurrency sets are stored in the cryptocurrency identifier, used as a utilized as training cryptocurrency sets for artificial intelligence models

[0047]. The cryptocurrency center control unit is used to monitor the classified cryptocurrency and facilitates cryptocurrency cleaning;

[0048]. The processing unit is configured to: access a distributed ledger comprising a plurality of cryptocurrency (cryptocurrency corresponding to a plurality of cryptocurrency assets, wherein the plurality of cryptocurrency assets comprises an aggregate stack of cryptocurrency; Assigning the plurality of cryptocurrency cryptocurrency; interpret a distributed ledger operation corresponding to at least one of the plurality of cryptocurrency

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

assets; determining an analytic result value in response to the distributed ledger operation and the tokenized plurality of cryptocurrency crypto currency, wherein the analytic result value comprises statistical information corresponding to: access events for the at least one of the plurality of cryptocurrency assets.

[0049]. The output device is used to display and enabling access to the classified cryptocurrency to the user.

[0050]. Although implementations of the invention have been described in a language specific to structural features and/or methods, it is to be understood that the appended claims are not necessarily limited to the specific features or methods described. Rather, the specific features and methods are disclosed as examples of implementations of the invention.

CLAIMS

We claim:

1. A system for analyzing transaction data in cryptocurrency trading using artificial intelligence model, wherein the system comprises: An Input cryptocurrency module, in the form of structured or unstructured cryptocurrency; A cryptocurrency analyzer to parse the input cryptocurrency and identify the classes and subclasses from cryptocurrency; A cryptocurrency identifier, is a collection class cryptocurrency sets and subclass cryptocurrency sets which are used to classify the transaction data related to the input cryptocurrency; a processing unit , used computing methods like artificial intelligence, artificial intelligence to classify and predict the class and sub-class cryptocurrency with respect to identified transaction data which determine the deep analysis view the cryptocurrency and to generate classified cryptocurrency sets and such processed class and sub-class cryptocurrency sets are stored in the cryptocurrency identifier, used as a utilized as training cryptocurrency sets for artificial intelligence methods; and A cryptocurrency center control unit , used to monitors the classified cryptocurrency and facilitates cryptocurrency cleaning; wherein the processing unit is configured to: access a distributed ledger comprising a plurality of cryptocurrency (cryptocurrency corresponding to a plurality of cryptocurrency assets, wherein the plurality of cryptocurrency assets comprises an aggregate stack of cryptocurrency; Assigning the plurality of cryptocurrency crypto currency; interpret a distributed ledger operation corresponding to at least one of the plurality of cryptocurrency assets; determining an analytic result value in response to the distributed ledger operation and the tokenized plurality of cryptocurrency crypto currency, wherein the analytic result value comprises statistical information corresponding to: access events for the at least one of the plurality of cryptocurrency assets; and An output device, used to display and enabling access to the classified cryptocurrency to the user.

DRAWINGS

Applicants: Dr. N P Kavya & Other

FIGURE 1

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

3/26/2021

PATENT eFiling

Sr.No.	Name	Nationality	Address	Country	State
1	Dr. Vidya Bai G	India	Associate Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
2	Dr. Nethravathi P. S.	India	Professor, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
3	Dr. Krishna Prasad K	India	Associate Professor, Director- College Research Council, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
4	Mr. Daniel Frank	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
5	Mrs. Sheetal A	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education,	India	Karnataka

<https://ipindiaonline.gov.in/epatentfiling/DraftedForm/ListofDraftedForm>

1/5

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

3/26/2021

PATENT eFiling

			Manipal, Karnataka, India		
6	Mr. Pushparaj Nayak	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
7	Mr. Nidheesh K	India	Android Developer, Near Shiva Temple, Pernadka Road, Kudlu, Kasaragod- 671124, Kerala, India	India	Kerala

2. INVENTOR(S):

Sr.No.	Name	Nationality	Address	Country	State
1	Dr. Vidya Bai G	India	Associate Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
2	Dr. Nethravathi P. S.	India	Professor, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
3	Dr. Krishna Prasad K	India	Associate Professor, Director- College Research Council, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
4	Mr. Daniel Frank	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka

<https://ipindiaonline.gov.in/epatentfiling/DraftedForm/ListofDraftedForm>

2/5

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

3/26/2021

PATENT eFiling

5	Mrs. Sheetal A	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
6	Mr. Pushparaj Nayak	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
7	Mr. Nidheesh K	India	Android Developer, Near Shiva Temple, Pernadka Road, Kudlu, Kasaragod- 671124, Kerala, India	India	Kerala

3. TITLE OF THE INVENTION: SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT TO IMPROVE SERVICES OF SUPERMARKET USING COMPUTERIZED ONLINE PLATFORM

4. ADDRESS FOR CORRESPONDENCE OF APPLICANT / Telephone No.:
AUTHORISED PATENT AGENT IN INDIA: Fax No.:
 Dr. Nethravathi P. S. Professor, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India **Mobile No:**
E-mail: nethrakumar590@gmail.com

5. PRIORITY PARTICULARS OF THE APPLICATION(S) FILED IN CONVENTION COUNTRY:

Sr.No.	Country	Application Number	Filing Date	Name of the Applicant	Title of the Invention
--------	---------	--------------------	-------------	-----------------------	------------------------

6. PARTICULARS FOR FILING PATENT COOPERATION TREATY (PCT) NATIONAL PHASE APPLICATION:

International Application Number	International Filing Date as Allotted by the Receiving Office
PCT//	

7. PARTICULARS FOR FILING DIVISIONAL APPLICATION

Original (first) Application Number	Date of Filing of Original (first) Application
-------------------------------------	--

<https://pindiaonline.gov.in/epatentfiling/DraftedForm/ListofDraftedForm>

3/5

8. PARTICULARS FOR FILING PATENT OF ADDITION:

Main Application / Patent Number:	Date of Filing of Main Application
--	---

9. DECLARATIONS:

(i) Declaration by the inventor(s)

I/We ,Dr. Vidya Bai G,Dr. Nethravathi P. S.,Dr. Krishna Prasad K,Mr. Daniel Frank,Mrs. Sheetal A,Mr. Pushparaj Nayak,Mr. Nidheesh K, is/are the true & first inventor(s) for this invention and declare that the applicant(s) herein is/are my/our assignee or legal representative.

(a) Date: ----

(b) Signature(s) of the inventor(s):

(c) Name(s): Dr. Vidya Bai G,Dr. Nethravathi P. S.,Dr. Krishna Prasad K,Mr. Daniel Frank,Mrs. Sheetal A,Mr. Pushparaj Nayak,Mr. Nidheesh K

(ii) Declaration by the applicant(s) in the convention country

I/We, the applicant(s) in the convention country declare that the applicant(s) herein is/are my/our assignee or legal representative.

(a) Date: ----

(b) Signature(s) :

(c) Name(s) of the singnatory: Dr. Vidya Bai G,Dr. Nethravathi P. S.,Dr. Krishna Prasad K,Mr. Daniel Frank,Mrs. Sheetal A,Mr. Pushparaj Nayak,Mr. Nidheesh K

(iii) Declaration by the applicant(s)

- The Complete specification relating to the invention is filed with this application.
- I am/We are, in the possession of the above mentioned invention.
- There is no lawful ground of objection to the grant of the Patent to me/us.

10. FOLLOWING ARE THE ATTACHMENTS WITH THE APPLICATION:

Sr.	Document Description	FileName
1	REQUEST FOR EARLY PUBLICATION(FORM-9)	Form 9.pdf
2	COMPLETE SPECIFICATION	FORM 2.pdf
3	DRAWINGS	Drawing.pdf
4	STATEMENT OF UNDERTAKING (FORM 3)	Form 3.pdf
5	DECLARATION OF INVENTORSHIP (FORM 5)	Form 5.pdf

I/We hereby declare that to the best of my/our knowledge, information and belief the fact and matters stated hereing are correct and I/We request that a patent may be granted to me/us for the said invention.

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

3/26/2021

PATENT eFiling

Dated this(Final Payment Date): -----	Signature: -----
	Name: Balram Singh Yadav
To The Controller of Patents	
The Patent office at CHENNAI	

This form is electronically generated.

Print

FORM 2

THE PATENTS ACT, 1970(39 of 1970) &

THE PATENTS RULES, 2003

COMPLETE SPECIFICATION

(See section 10, rule 13)

1. TITLE OF THE INVENTION:

**SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR HUMAN RESOURCE
MANAGEMENT TO IMPROVESERVICES OF
SUPERMARKET USING COMPUTERIZED ONLINE
PLATFORM**

2. APPLICANTS

Sr.No.	Name	Nationality	Address
1	Dr. Vidya Bai G	India	Associate Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, Karnataka, India
2	Dr. Nethravathi P. S.	India	Professor, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India
3	Dr. Krishna Prasad K	India	Associate Professor, Director- College Research Council, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Karnataka, India
4	Mr Daniel Frank	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, Karnataka, India

5	Mrs. Sheetal A	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, Karnataka, India
6	Mr. Pushparaj Nayak	India	Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Manipal, Karnataka, India
7	Mr. Nidheesh K	India	Android Developer, Near Shiva Temple, Pernadka Road, Kudlu, Kasaragod- 671124, Kerala, India

3. PREAMBLE TO THE DESCRIPTION

COMPLETE SPECIFICATION

The following specification particularly describes the invention and the manner in which it is to be performed.

**SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR HUMAN RESOURCE
MANAGEMENT TO IMPROVE SERVICES OF
SUPERMARKET USING COMPUTERIZED ONLINE
PLATFORM**

FIELD OF INVENTION

The present invention relates to the technical field of computerized human resource management.

The present invention relates to field of an online interactive management system of supermarket service staff and a method thereof.

The present invention relates to the technical field to automatic management system relates to, smart phone and carried automatically by checking & managing employee working, feedback of an employee using the same product for automatically managing service and method of thereof.

More particularly, the present invention is related to system and method for human resource management to improve services of supermarket using computerized online platform.

BACKGROUND & PRIOR ART

The subject matter discussed in the background section should not be assumed to be prior art merely as a result of its mention in the background section. Similarly, a problem mentioned in the background section or associated with the subject matter of the background section should not be assumed to have been previously recognized in the prior art. The subject matter in the background section merely represents different approaches, which in-and-of-themselves may also be inventions.

The API OR App (s) or computer application OR mobile software are used synonyms in this disclosure.

The present disclosure present *ConnectMartApp*, as presented in the detail description, as a one example of the present invention. The term *ConnectMartApp* is taken as a synonyms of the present invention.

In the Existing system, all the news, innovation ideas, feedback, updates, notifications, inter-supermarket communication in the company is through the mail, tele-communication and sites. It's a time consuming task to check the mails and site each and every time for any updated

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

information. For management, it's a hectic task to ask or convey the news, message, questionnaires with all the employee who are working under the big company. In existing system admin or management has more work compared to the employee. He/She has to contact all the managers or sub-ordinates if he wants to say something. Even in this case, it is difficult to remember names of the contacted person and the person couldn't able to contact. The management has to spend his/her time to do these kind of activities every time. As an enquiry with employees, some of the corporate company get to know that most of the existing system provides web sites for employees to get their salary slip, history, leave management approvals and promotion, feedback and notifications. In some of the system, the lower grade employees do not have any option to report his/her problem with management. If so, he/she to take the permission of superiors, superiors-HR so on till the end and it's not sure whether it will reach to management. Lower grade or middle grade designation role people always work for short period of time in the companies due to comfortable environment and system. As a point of business logistic we cannot grow up only with customer satisfaction. if the employee is also satisfied with the rules and regulations, environment, getting solution for their problem then they give their 100% contribution. In a corporate company thousands employees will be there, so shaving those people name and contact in an employee phone is not an easy job or if an employee wants his colleague number which is not saved in his/her phone abusively he/has to contact some other person to get it. While doing survey, it is observed that some company apps provides only official information, some app provides social interface related things.

Some of the prior related works as follows:

TW201926159A - Method for facilitating positive interaction among employees and their companies by acquiring reward points and redeeming feedback benefits comprising a plurality of terminal devices, Internet, and a cloud management server for each employee to gradually accumulate the reward points presents "a method for facilitating positive interaction among employees and their companies by acquiring reward points and redeeming feedback benefits. The method is applied to an interactive management system comprising a plurality of terminal devices (for example, a smart phone or a computer), Internet, and a cloud management server, wherein each of the terminal devices is owned by a company or an employee thereof, and can connect online with the cloud management server through Internet respectively. The cloud management server can at least initiate a random lottery mechanism and read the employee's attendance record, so that the corresponding reward points

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

are stored in the employee reward point account, the total reward points accumulated by the employee can be presented, and other reward mechanisms are initiated and enabled. As a result, during the tenure of working in the company, each employee can gradually accumulate the reward points to effectively motivate the employees' morale and enthusiasm in the company work, and often enable employees to maintain good interaction and communication with each other and with the decision-makers in the company.”

KR102146545B1 - Field management information system in specialty construction company based on mobile phone presents “a field information management system in a professional construction industry. The present invention relates to a company server for comprehensively managing field information in a main office of a professional construction company, a manager terminal in which a manager of a professional construction company is installed, and a mobile communication terminal which is a mobile communication terminal that works in the construction site. The application server provides a dedicated application to the manager terminal and the employee terminal through the dedicated application, and provides the function of registering construction site information including work time, daily life, daily work, work time, facility charge, flow input, consistency, process photographs, instructions, and measures. A field information management system based on a mobile communication terminal such as a smart phone and a tablet PC is provided to systematically and efficiently manage construction site by providing a field information management system based on a mobile communication terminal such as a smart phone and a tablet PC.”

JP2016099799A - ORDER INFORMATION INPUT DEVICE MANAGEMENT METHOD, AND PROGRAM presents “system, in order to store the information input device and employee identification information for identifying the input information, the input device or the order information stored in a storage device store, employees, order information input device or the like is transmitted to the server Nano order identification information, the server side Nano order, previously recorded position information of the store, employee information, and information relating to the order information input device, inspected, processing to determine whether of acceptance, result is sent to the order information input device and a control mean”

CN107818446A - Enterprise human resource management device presents “an enterprise human resource management device, which comprises a management module, a personnel

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

module, an attendance checking module, a salary module, a scheduling module, airport module, a welfare module, a terminal connection module, a network connection module, a terminal device and an attendance checking device, wherein the management module, the personnel module, the attendance checking module, the salary module, the scheduling module, the report module, the welfare module, the terminal connection module and the network connection module are arranged in a central server, the terminal device and the attendance checking device are connected with the central server, the attendance checking device comprises one or more of a timer, a card punching machine, a fingerprint recognizer and an iris recognizer, and the terminal device comprises one or more of a computer, an intelligent mobile phone or a tablet computer. The management device can solve a series of management problems of an enterprise for human resource in the reality, thereby improving the working efficiency of the enterprise and human resource management, and improving the development power of the enterprise.”

CN107833020A - Enterprise internal management and control system presents “an enterprise internal management and control system. An enterprise port is a port used by an administrator, and utilizes a smart phone to perform data interaction with an enterprise server. An employee port is portused by an enterprise employee, and uses the smart phone to perform data interaction with the enterprise server. The enterprise server at least includes a memory for storing data, a processor for data processing, and a network communication unit for data interaction. The processor of the enterprise server connects to an external network database or a server through the network communication unit, and stores the obtained information in the memory and/or sends the obtained information to the enterprise terminal and the employee terminal. The system changes the enterprise's changeless welfare content, combines the use and consumption habits and group characteristics of enterprises and employees, and intelligently provides different welfare services, soaps to enrich the leisure and cultural entertainment life of employees, enhance employee's stability and efficiency, indirectly reduce labor cost, and embody the uniqueness of each employee.”

IN201641033863A - ATTENDANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM USING RASPBERRY PI presents “Attendance management systems and the employee’s attendance are taken to be the most mandatory issue in day to day working environment of that company or the organization. Nowadays the attendance of the employees is marked using RFID, Eye detection, Smart card access and Finger print scanners. But in some cases it may go in vain.

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

Here we have used Raspberry Pi to manage the attendance. This invention involves in dual verification of the presence of the employee. We are using face manipulation & detection also Wi-Fi module access from the mobile phone of the employee. The MAC ID of the mobile phone will be acting as the unique and also the primary key of the database. The MAC IDs can only be modified or removed only by the administrator of the organization. The faces of the employees are prior detected and programmed and also the dimension of the face of employees are comparatively interlinked to the primary key of the database and here we are using MySQLdb module of Python. It is our responsibility to encourage such an innovation where it can get into the world of Smart things i.e. Internet of Things.”

CN110363507A - Enterprise attendance management system presents “an enterprise attendance management system and relates to the technical field of enterprise management. The system comprises an employee mobile phone terminal, an attendance card punching terminal, a server and a management terminal, and is characterized in that the employee mobile phone terminal is wirelessly connected with the attendance card punching terminal, the server and the management terminal. The attendance card punching terminal is electrically connected with the server, and the server is wirelessly connected with the management terminal. According to the invention, attendance of employees of enterprises is managed in a manner of combining multiple clock-in modes. Employees can normally punch cards under various conditions. The attendance of the employees can be uniformly managed in an offline and online statistics mode. The probability of attendance errors of the employees is reduced, and the attendance related affairs of the employees can be uniformly managed on line.”

CN107944819A - Enterprise personnel management system based on computer and GPS technology presents “an enterprise personnel management system based on the computer and the GPS technology, and relates to the technical field of enterprise information management. The enterprise personnel management system comprises a personal client side which is used for transmitting real-time positioning information and is installed on the mobile phone of the enterprise personnel; an enterprise management side which is installed on the computer of the enterprise management layer; and a cloud side server which is used for storing data information, wherein the personal client side transmits the positioning information of the employees to the enterprise management side in real time during the working hours. The positioning information of the employees is transmitted in real time during the working hours through the personal client side and the action information of the employees is managed

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

through the enterprise management side so that the action information of the employees is enabled to be known in real time by the management layer, the alarm module alarms to the manager and warns the employee to return to the working position when the employee leaves the working position during the working hours and management of the employees is facilitated for the management layer, and the business trip situation of the employees is managed through business trip setting.”

CN108846627A - Enterprise management system based on sales management and implementation method thereof present “an enterprise management system based on sales management. The enterprise management system comprises a sales information management module. The sales information management module acts as the center to be associated with an employee management module, a customer management module, a production, supply and marketing management module, an operation management module, a problem management module and a database module. Communication between all the modules is realized through the internet technology and operation is performed through the client side. The invention has the advantages that: the employee management module is designed to systematically and regularly train the employees so as to improve the business ability; the problem management module collects the problems produced by system operation, which is convenient for the management level to collect and classify the problems and deal with the problems centrally, cooperate with the staff management module to solve the problems and improve the efficiency of problem treatment; t”

CN106920075A - Work attendance checking management method based on WeChat official account presents “a work attendance checking management method based on a WeChat official account. A device according to the method comprises mobile terminal on which WeChat client software is installed, a WeChat official account platform, an enterprise server and an enterprise management terminal. Mobile terminal is connected with a WeChat official account client through a network and follows the WeChat official account which is applied by an enterprise. The WeChat official account platform is configured for being connected with the enterprise server. The enterprise management terminal is connected with the enterprise server. An employee can utilize mobile equipment such as mobile phone and notebook computer for finishing mobile work attendance checking. The work attendance checking management method settles a problem of incapability of managing employee outgoing and evection by the enterprise. The employee can utilize the mobile equipment such as mobile

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

phone for finishing work attendance checking and searches personal work attendance checking condition anytime and anywhere, thereby facilitating use by the employee”

CN109862155A - Special mobile phone system presents “a special mobile phone system. The special mobile phone system includes a mobile phone, a gateway server, and a service end; the mobile phone comprises a number write-in module, a number storage module, a number dialing module, a short message receiving module, a short message storage module, a short message sending module, a number limiting module, a built-in APP module, data storage module, and a data sending module. The special mobile phone system is convenient to use, principle is simple; the use of dialing, short messages, internet surfing and APPs of mobile phones of employees can be limited, so that work irrelevant things of the employees are reduced when the employees go to work, the working efficiency is improved, the use conditions of the mobile phones can be stored through the central storage module, managers can conveniently know the working states and the working conditions of the employees, and enterprise management is facilitate”

CN105488858A - Work attendance information identification system for enterprise presents “a work attendance information identification system for an enterprise. The work attendance information identification system comprises an RFID card, a client, a background server and a work attendance machine connected with the client and the background server. The work attendance machine comprises a shell, and a controller, an RFID reader, an identification module, a display module, a wireless communication module and a power supply module arranged in the shell, wherein the controller is a one-chip microcomputer, the client is a smart phone, the background server is a cloud server, the display module is a touch-screen display, and the identification module comprises an iris scanner. The work attendance information identification system provided by the invention utilizes the iris scanner to scan irises of employees for comparison and identification and employs the RFID reader to read information of the RFID card of a user, thereby preventing the employees from cheating in work attendance.’.

Groupings of alternative elements or embodiments of the invention disclosed herein are not to be construed as limitations. Each group member can be referred to and claimed individually or in any combination with other members of the group or other elements found herein. One or more members of a group can be included in, or deleted from, a group for reasons of

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

convenience and/or patentability. When any such inclusion or deletion occurs, the specification is herein deemed to contain the group as modified, thus fulfilling the written description of all Markus groups used in the appended claims.

As used in the description herein and throughout the claims that follow, the meaning of “a,” “an,” and “the” includes plural reference unless the context clearly dictates otherwise. Also, as used in the description herein, the meaning of “in” includes “in” and “on” unless the context clearly dictates otherwise.

The recitation of ranges of values herein is merely intended to serve as a shorthand method of referring individually to each separate value falling within the range. Unless otherwise indicated herein, each individual value is incorporated into the specification as if it were individually recited herein. All methods described herein can be performed in any suitable order unless otherwise indicated herein or otherwise clearly contradicted by context.

The use of any and all examples, or exemplary language (e.g. “Such as”) provided with respect to certain embodiments herein is intended merely to better illuminate the invention and does not pose a limitation on the scope of the invention otherwise claimed. No language in the specification should be construed as indicating any non-claimed element essential to the practice of the invention.

The above information disclosed in this Background section is only for the enhancement of understanding of the background of the invention and therefore it may contain information that does not form the prior art that is already known in this country to a person of ordinary skill in the art.

SUMMARY

Before the present systems and methods, are described, it is to be understood that this application is not limited to the particular systems, and methodologies described, as there can be multiple possible embodiments which are not expressly illustrated in the present disclosure. It is also to be understood that the terminology used in the description is for the purpose of describing the particular versions or embodiments only and is not intended to limit the scope of the present application.

The present invention mainly cures and solves the technical problems existing in the prior art. In response to these problems, the present invention discloses system and method for human resource management to improve services of supermarket using computerized online platform.

OBJECTIVE OF THE INVENTION

The principle objective of the present invention is to provide a system and method for human resource management to improve services of supermarket using computerized online platform.

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF DRAWINGS

To clarify various aspects of some example embodiments of the present invention, a more particular description of the invention will be rendered by reference to specific embodiments thereof which are illustrated in the appended drawings. It is appreciated that these drawings depict only illustrated embodiments of the invention and are therefore not to be considered limiting of its scope. The invention will be described and explained with additional specificity and detail through the use of the accompanying drawings.

In order that the advantages of the present invention will be easily understood, a detailed description of the invention is discussed below in conjunction with the appended drawings, which, however, should not be considered to limit the scope of the invention to the accompanying drawings, in which:

Figure 1 shows detail block diagram representation of the system and for human resource management to improve services of supermarket using computerized online platform.

Figure 2 shows block diagram representation server & database for the system and for human resource management to improve services of supermarket using computerized online platform.

DETAIL DESCRIPTION

The present invention is related to system and method for human resource management to improve services of supermarket using computerized online platform.

Figure 1 shows Block diagram representation of the system and for human resource management to improve services of supermarket using computerized online platform.

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

Although the present disclosure has been described with the purpose of system and method for human resource management to improve services of supermarket using computerized online platform, it should be appreciated that the same has been done merely to illustrate the invention in an exemplary manner and to highlight any other purpose or function for which explained structures or configurations could be used and is covered within the scope of the present disclosure.

Some embodiments of this disclosure, illustrating all its features, will now be discussed in detail. The words and other forms thereof, are intended to be open ended in that an item or items following any one of these words are not meant to be an exhaustive listing of such item or items, or meant to be limited to only the listed item or items. It must also be noted that as used herein and in the appended claims, the singular forms "a," "an," and "the" include plural references unless the context clearly dictates otherwise. Although any systems and methods similar or equivalent to those described herein can be used in the practice or testing of embodiments of the present disclosure, the exemplary systems and methods are now described. The disclosed embodiments are merely exemplary of the disclosure, which may be embodied in various forms.

The system and method for human resource management to improve services of supermarket using computerized online platform is disclosed in the present invention.

In the proposed system, it will eliminate all the problems which are mentioned in the existing system after the implementation of this app. It will completely eliminate usage of site for employees. This app is beneficial not only for employees but also for admin. Admin need not worry about "how to convey the news to employees", "how to get their idea to improve in the area of product, process and service", "ask questionnaires and get the feedback", "proposing idea from management side to employees side", "make feel free environment to employees", "providing salary slip", "leave management", "compliant box" and so on are included in this app. Reachability of admin to employee and employee to admin is just a matter of seconds in this app. This app includes real time push notification feature when admin adds or updates any of the information to the server. Automatically server sends push notification to the employees devices. It will alert in employee's phone, he/she can see those received notification from notification bar without opening the app, when tap on those notifications it will automatically navigate to respected page on the app. It provides auto login

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

feature as how other app provides. There is no surety that all people may know English so that **ConnectMartApp** introduced another attractive feature is “language translation” it will have included some state languages therefore it be will easier for employee to use the app in their known language.

Id	Question	Location	Role	Type	option
1	Are you satisfied with new night shift from 2am-9am..	India/Mumbai/central Mall	Stock checker	Radio button	1.Yes 2.No
2.	Is your supervisors and managers solves your problem facing at hypermarket and supermarket	All	Stockchekers, supervisors	Checkbox	1. All the time 2. Some times 3.Not at all 4.Partiality
3.	Customers feedback	All	All	textbox	Comment

The above given table shows list of questions, answering type for which designation role is asked for certain region branch/mall/shop. It gives clear picture about the feedback or survey is taken place

The above figure shows how the user gets the questionnaires and its respective answering type. Answering type will be based on admin provided option. All the questionnaires will display in the form of list views. When user click on particular survey question from the list view, it will navigate to detailed view page as above figure. The page includes last date of submission, question and answering type. When user clicks on submit button, the data will be sent to the server through API call.

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

ConnectMartApp server manages all API calls in the system. When app initiates an API call to the server, it fetches the data which is sent along the API call and also it will identify the device, user related details using these data. Server contains a lot of function with respect to API call. This function writes sql query to insert survey input data into survey table of ConnectMartApp database. When data is saved in the database, the server sends response through the app. Based on the user input, he/she will get the success or an error message. Figure 2 shows block diagram representation server & database for the system and for human resource management to improve services of supermarket using computerized online platform.

News

News Module includes three categories.

[1] All News: It includes all category news

[2] Company: It includes news related to ConnectMartApp

[3] Other: It includes the news that is indirectly related to the employees or company.

Eg: When a product is introduced to market. The News will display as scrollable *card view*. *Cardview* consists of photo or video, title of the news, like and comment button. When user taps on particular news it will navigate to another screen where it will display in detail. If the employee likes or supports the news, he/she can tap on like button it will change to red heart emoji. If the employee wants to share his/her opinion to news, they can ping through the comment. Employee can able to see others comments.

a. Innovation & Creative Idea

It consist of 3 categories.

[1] EmployeeIdea : It shows the ideas which uploaded by the employees and employee can add their idea in area such as service, product, process.

[2] Company Innovation: It shows the idea which uploaded by the company.

[3] Approved: It shows the Ideas which is approved by the management followed by employees support.

The Innovation & Creative Idea will display as scrollable *card view*. *Cardview* consists of photo, video, sketch, file, title of the idea, like and comment button. when user tap on particular idea, it will navigate to another screen where it will display in detail. If the employee likes or supports the idea, he/she can tap on like button it will change to red heart emoji. If the employee want to say his/her opinion or add more to existing idea, employee can ping it through

comment. Employee can see other comments given by employees for that idea.

b. FeedBack or Survey

If company wants to ask anything with employee, company will put up questionnaires to the system. Admin can decide type of answering, it can be radio button, checkbox, textbox and toggle button. It will display as a list view in the employee screen based on the date of submission in ascending date format.

c. Chat

Chat feature will be similar to other chat app but two things are added in this app. Top of the chat list, ConnectMartApp group will be by default. When admin want to inform any important message to all it will be received to top chat list. Employee can text with admin directly.

d. Leave Management

It provides an option for employee to apply for the leave. The leave can be of type sick, maternity, casual, earned, half pay so on. Employee has to choose 'From' to 'To date' to apply the leave and he/she can add comment along with that. Once he/she have applied for the leave, status of the applied one will displayed.

e. History

It includes all the records such as salary slip, previously taken leave, promotion details .

f. Notification

It is a trigger or a simpler interface where all the details will be pointed out which is related to the employee. App consist lot of features so employee doesnot know what admin has added to the system. In the notification screen it will display the notification based on the time and date it is initiated to the system. When we click on a particular notification it will trigger to the respected screen.

g. Vacancy & Benefits

This module will provides list of vacancies in the company so that employee can refer someone from the outside to the company and can use the benefits that includes amenities which is getting from the company to the employee.

Result & Analysis

The project gives a glance about how it is advanced from ancient way of analysis. In olden days and feedback, acquiring suggestion takes place at all branches of Hypermarket. The management has to prepare the questionnaires that they want to ask with employees, then the admin will mail those files to all the branch managers or particular branch managers. They carry the hardcopy of it and share it to supervisors forwarded to employees on hand. Once the employee fills the survey forms, same cycle flows reversibly. The branch managers will analyse his/her branch survey data and prepares a soft copy.

All the branch managers will send their respective branch survey details to prime manager who will merge all survey data into one and send it to admin who will analysis with the help of some tool. When the technology turned into websites all the employee has to login to the system, has the option of replying to the updated survey, only literate people check usually other will leave due difficulty in using websites. In older system around 60% to 77% people only make use of it and the older system it involves a lot of paper work more over time consuming task but the ConnectMartApp will eliminate all these problems

Questionnaires, ideas, news, leave management etc. data will be saved in the ConnectMartDatabase. When admin open his/her analysis page or dashboard, all the process will happen in background such that it will initiate an API call to server to get the data. Along with API call, the system will add authentication data in order to get the access to the server. When server gets an API call, it will identify the method with respected to API call. Server retrieves data from the ConnectMartDatabase using SQL query and convert it into json format and send response to the API call which is made by admin. The received data will be saved as model, the response of json data. It contains list of questions and array of user input. Using this model data pie chart, bar graph will be drawn with php, js, css and bootstrap tools. In the same way, analysis can be done for other modules. We can build server with any platform such as python, php, java etc. The given figure below describes how data is retrieved from database to the system.

All the data will be stored in respective table of HYPER-E-MART database system. When we get the relevant data, its time to perform the business logistic and analysis process to evaluate standing position. Admin go through the received data and considers it as time consuming task. The solution is a day's graphical representation which is more popular for data analysis.

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

When employee open his/her app they have an option to show their happiness level. It consists of 3 levels:-happy, satisfied and sad. Even they can mention comment. Twice in a day, employee has an option to show his/her happiness mood. Using this data, admin can generate graph of Happiness Level of the employee for a day, week or month.

Answering type for the feedback or survey questionnaires will decide by admin. Usually it will be in the form of radio button or checkboxes so the analysis can be done in ease. The given below figure is an example for analysis of questionnaires. Taking an example :-If company has made any changes in the rules and regulation and company accept opinion from employee about the new change. While looking into the analysis, admin can easily get to know how employees are taking the things. Third person is not in need to collect the information of person, it's just a 2 way information strategy.

Business ideas and creative thoughts can be shared by employees and admin to the system. The ideas with higher support will be approved for the implementation. The system considers employees' likes and comments for this analysis process. Using these data admin will generate support count of each idea in terms of line graph or bar graph. The given below graph is an example of an idea. It represents how many of them are supporting for the idea out of the total number of employees to how many of them shared their opinion. In the same manner, admin can analyse all the data for business intelligence. It gives a proper clarity to the admin. Admin can trace total number of employees who use this app in the company and admin can also analyse how many people are using Android smartphone and IOS smart phone. These information directly or indirectly helps the mobile companies to know the type of OS which are commonly used by and its ratio. Admin can generate graph for news as he analyses the ideas. Admin can read the posted comments as well. All the corporate companies keep record of payroll, personal information, leave management in database of an employee, therefore no need of creating separate database for this system, we can fetch data from an existing database itself.

In Leave Management, employee will apply for leave, instantly, it populates in the admin panel henceforth admin will process it. In this module, employee can trace the status of applied leave such as approved, rejected and processing. Company itself provides various types of insurances for the employee. If an employee applies for that, he can pay through this app. Employee can get status of applied one. Similarly, employee can check the status related to

applied promotions.

The figures and the foregoing description give examples of embodiments. Those skilled in the art will appreciate that one or more of the described elements may well be combined into a single functional element. Alternatively, certain elements may be split into multiple functional elements. Elements from one embodiment may be added to another embodiment. For example, order of processes described herein may be changed and are not limited to the manner described herein. Moreover, the actions of any flow diagram need not be implemented in the order shown; nor do all of the acts need to be necessarily performed. Also, those acts that are not dependent on other acts may be performed in parallel with the other acts. The scope of embodiments is by no means limited by these specific examples.

Although implementations of the invention have been described in a language specific to structural features and/or methods, it is to be understood that the appended claims are not necessarily limited to the specific features or methods described. Rather, the specific features and methods are disclosed as examples of implementations of the invention.

CLAIMS

We claim:

1. A system for human resource management to improve services of supermarket using computerized online platform, wherein the system characteristic in that :

A database ;

A server, wherein the server is used to manages all the online platform associated with the system, the server sends & receive data and response to /from the online platform associated with the system;

An employee online platform, connected to the server, wherein the employee online platform is used by the employee after proper authorization in a mobile computing device associated with the particular employee, wherein employee online platform provides facilitation including:

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

a new update module, presents three type of news, [1] All News: It includes all category news, [2] Company: It includes news related to company, [3] Other news: It includes the news that is indirectly related to the employees or company, wherein If the employee likes or supports the news, he/she can tap on like button it will change to redheart emoji,

An Innovation & Creative Idea module, wherein Innovation & Creative Idea module consist of three categories: [1] an Employee Idea: It shows the ideas which uploaded by the employees and employee can add their idea in area such as service, product, process, [2] a Company Innovation: It shows the idea which uploaded by the company, [3] an Approved: It shows the Ideas which is approved by the management followed by employees support,

Wherein the Innovation & Creative Idea displays as scrollable *card view*, the *Card view* consists of photo, video, sketch, file, title of the idea, like and comment button, when user tap on particular idea, it will navigate to another screen where it will display in detail, If the employee likes or supports the idea, he/she can tap on like button it will change to red heart emoji, If the employee wants to say his/her opinion or add more to existing idea, employee can ping it through comment,

A Feedback or Survey module, wherein the Feedback or Survey module, if company wants to ask anything with employee, company will put up questionnaires to the system, wherein the Admin can decide type of answering, it can be radio button, checkbox, textbox and toggle button, it will display as a list view in the employee screen based on the date of submission in ascending date format;

A Leave Management module, wherein Leave Management module provides an option for employee to apply for the leave, the leave can be of type sick, maternity, casual, earned, half pay so on, wherein Employee has to choose 'From' to 'To date' to apply the leave and he/she can add comment along with that, once he/she have applied for the leave, status of the applied one will displayed,

A History module, wherein the History module includes all the records such as salary slip, previously taken leave, promotion details,

A Vacancy & Benefits module, wherein Vacancy & Benefits module provides list of vacancies

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

in the company so that employee can refer someone from the outside to the company and can use the benefits that includes amenities which is getting from the company to the employee; and An Admin online platform, wherein the Admin online platform is used to analysis, administrate and control the operation data input, processed and stored in database through the server and the database, by the authorized admin.

2. The system for human resource management to improve services of supermarket using computerized online platform as claimed in claim1, wherein the mobile computing device is a smart phone.

3. The system for human resource management to improve services of supermarket using computerized online platform as claimed in claim 1, wherein the system is worked in computer program with a graphic user interface, wherein the computer program is processed by at least one processor of the mobile computing device.

4. The system for human resource management to improve services of supermarket using computerized online platform as claimed in claim 1, wherein the computer program is a mobile phone application.

**SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR HUMAN RESOURCE
MANAGEMENT TO IMPROVESERVICES OF
SUPERMARKET USING COMPUTERIZED ONLINE
PLATFORM**

ABSTRACT

The present invention relates to system and method for human resource management to improve services of supermarket using computerizedonline platform. The objective of the present invention is to solve the problems in the prior art related to technologies of computerized online management of human resource in a workplace.

DRAWINGS

Applicants: **Dr. Vidya Bai G & others**

Sheet No. 1 of Total 2

FIGURE 1

Dated 26th Day of March, 2021

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

Applicants: Dr. Vidya Bai G & others

Sheet No. 2 of Total 2

FIGURE 2

Dated 26th Day of March, 2021

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

9/7/2021

PATENT eFiling

Sr.No.	Name	Nationality	Address	Country	State
1	Abdul Shareef Pallivalappil	India	Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
2	Dr. Krishna Prasad K	India	Associate Professor, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka

2. INVENTOR(S):

Sr.No.	Name	Nationality	Address	Country	State
1	Abdul Shareef Pallivalappil	India	Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka
2	Dr. Krishna Prasad K	India	Associate Professor, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India	India	Karnataka

3. TITLE OF THE INVENTION: COMPUTER IMPLEMENTED METHOD FOR SPECIFIC

<https://ipindiaonline.gov.in/ePatentFiling/DraftedForm/ListofDraftedForm>

1/3

RESPONSE AND INTERACTION FROM RETAILERS ACCORDING TO USER GENERATED SEARCH REQUESTS

4. ADDRESS FOR CORRESPONDENCE OF APPLICANT / Telephone No.:
AUTHORISED PATENT AGENT IN INDIA: Fax No.:
 Abdul Shareef Pallivalappil Research Scholar, College of Mobile No: 8085217942
 Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas E-mail: patentpublication@gmail.com
 University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

5. PRIORITY PARTICULARS OF THE APPLICATION(S) FILED IN CONVENTION COUNTRY:

Sr.No.	Country	Application Number	Filing Date	Name of the Applicant	Title of the Invention
--------	---------	--------------------	-------------	-----------------------	------------------------

6. PARTICULARS FOR FILING PATENT COOPERATION TREATY (PCT) NATIONAL PHASE APPLICATION:

International Application Number	International Filing Date as Allotted by the Receiving Office
PCT//	

7. PARTICULARS FOR FILING DIVISIONAL APPLICATION

Original (first) Application Number	Date of Filing of Original (first) Application
-------------------------------------	--

8. PARTICULARS FOR FILING PATENT OF ADDITION:

Main Application / Patent Number:	Date of Filing of Main Application
-----------------------------------	------------------------------------

9. DECLARATIONS:

(i) Declaration by the inventor(s)

I/We ,Abdul Shareef Pallivalappil,Dr. Krishna Prasad K, is/are the true & first inventor(s) for this invention and declare that the applicant(s) herein is/are my/our assignee or legal representative.

(a) Date: ----

(b) Signature(s) of the inventor(s):

(c) Name(s): Abdul Shareef Pallivalappil,Dr. Krishna Prasad K.

(ii) Declaration by the applicant(s) in the convention country

I/We, the applicant(s) in the convention country declare that the applicant(s) herein is/are my/our assignee or legal representative.

(a) Date: ----

(b) Signature(s) :

(c) Name(s) of the singnatory: Abdul Shareef Pallivalappil,Dr. Krishna Prasad K

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

9/7/2021

PATENT eFiling

(iii) Declaration by the applicant(s)

- The Complete specification relating to the invention is filed with this application.
- I am/We are, in the possession of the above mentioned invention.
- There is no lawful ground of objection to the grant of the Patent to me/us.

10. FOLLOWING ARE THE ATTACHMENTS WITH THE APPLICATION:

Sr.	Document Description	FileName
1	REQUEST FOR EARLY PUBLICATION(FORM-9)	form 9.pdf
2	COMPLETE SPECIFICATION	FORM 2.pdf
3	DRAWINGS	Drawing.pdf
4	STATEMENT OF UNDERTAKING (FORM 3)	Form 3.pdf
5	DECLARATION OF INVENTORSHIP (FORM 5)	Form 5.pdf

I/We hereby declare that to the best of my/our knowledge, information and belief the fact and matters stated hereing are correct and I/We request that a patent may be granted to me/us for the said invention.

Dated this(Final Payment Date): -----

Signature:

Name: Balram Singh Yadav

To The Controller of Patents

The Patent office at CHENNAI

This form is electronically generated.

Print

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

9/7/2021

PATENT eFiling

<p>FORM 13</p> <p>THE PATENT ACT, 1970 (39 of 1970) & THE PATENTS RULES, 2003</p> <p>APPLICATION FOR AMENDMENT OF THE APPLICATION FOR PATENT/COMPLETE SPECIFICATION/ANY DOCUMENT RELATED THERE TO</p> <p>[See section 57; rule 81(1)]</p>
I/We
<p>1. Applicant Name: Abdul Shareef Pallivalappil Applicant Address is: Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India India .</p> <p>2. Applicant Name: Dr. Krishna Prasad K Applicant Address is: Associate Professor, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India India .</p>
request leave to amend the application/complete specification with respect application for patent No 202141040541 DATED 07/09/2021
reasons for making the above request are as follows-
Amendment in the summary part of the description to rectify the clerical errors. No new subject matter is added in the description.
patentpublication@gmail.com
I/We decelare that no action for infringement or for the revocation of the Patent in Question is Pending before Appellate Board or Court.
I/we declare that the facts and matters stated herein are true to the best of my/our knowledge ,information and belief.
Signature (.....)
To, The Controller of Patents, The Patent Office AT CHENNAI

This form is electronically generated.

Print

CLEAN COPY

FORM 2

THE PATENTS ACT, 1970(39 of
1970) &

THE PATENTS RULES, 2003
COMPLETE SPECIFICATION

(See section 10, rule 13)

1. TITLE OF THE INVENTION:

**COMPUTER IMPLEMENTED METHODFOR
SPECIFIC RESPONSE AND INTERACTION
FROM RETAILERS ACCORDING TO USER
GENERATED SEARCH REQUESTS**

2. APPLICANTS

Sr.No.	Name	Nationality	Address
1	Abdul Shareef Pallivalappil	India	Research Scholar, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India
2	Dr. Krishna Prasad K	India	Associate Professor, College of Computer Science and Information Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India

3. PREAMBLE TO THE DESCRIPTION

COMPLETE SPECIFICATION

The following specification particularly describes the invention and the manner in which it is to be performed.

COMPUTER IMPLEMENTED METHOD FOR SPECIFIC RESPONSE AND INTERACTION FROM RETAILERS ACCORDING TO USER GENERATED SEARCH REQUESTS

FIELD OF INVENTION

The present invention relates to the field of online ecommerce. The present invention is related to field of user specific response and interaction generation.

The present invention relates to the field of computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers during online shopping.

More particularly, the present invention is related to Computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests.

BACKGROUND & PRIOR ART

The subject matter discussed in the background section should not be assumed to be prior art merely as a result of its mention in the background section. Similarly, a problem mentioned in the background section or associated with the subject matter of the background section should not be assumed to have been previously recognized in the prior art. The subject matter in the background section merely represents different approaches, which in-and-of-themselves may also be inventions.

Some of the prior work listed herewith:

2014063508 COLOR COLLATION TOOL BOX JP - 10.04.2014 Int. Class G06F 17/30 Appl.No 013237481 Applicant LTU TECHNOLOGIES Coinventor ALEXANDRE WINTER PROBLEM TO BE SOLVED: To provide a system and a method for a search request based on a color in a merchandise collection. SOLUTION: A system and a method are provided for specifying a plurality of merchandises within a collection of merchandise images in an online shopping environment. This method includes the steps of: providing the collection of images displaying a merchandise on sale; and receiving an inputted search condition. The condition includes at least one color of search request. This method also

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

includes the steps of: specifying and extracting a color within a collection of images on the basis of a main color existing in the image; and determining whether or not the specified and extracted main color and the search requested color match by comparison. This method includes a step of specifying merchandise having a matched color with the search requested color from within the collection of the images in a range of a predetermined accuracy and making a presentation to a prospective consumer by a graphical user interface.

6466915CUSTOMER HISTORY MANAGEMENT METHOD AND SYSTEM IN ONLINE SHOPPING US - 15.10.2002 Nicklas G06F 17/00Appl.No 08679098 Applicant Fujitsu Limited Inventor azuki, TetsujiroIn online shopping, customer information when a customer selects and buys a desired article from goods information provided to a customer terminal from a center which provides online shopping information including the goods information to the customer terminal is managed. When the customer performs the online shopping, the goods information is stored for each customer individually, which goods information is goods information selected by the customer from goods information provided by the center. Then, the stored goods information is read out the next time a goods information search request is made by the customer, and the read goods information is displayed for the customer.

1020110120241SEARCHING SERVICE METHOD FOR AN ONLINE SHOPPING AND RECORD MEDIUM FOR EXECUTING AN APPARATUS AND SEARCHING METHOD KR - 03.11.2011Int.Class G06F 17/30Appl.No 1020110039495ApplicantEBAY KOREA CO., LTD.Inventor LEE, JU CHEOLPURPOSE: A searching service method for an online shopping and record medium for executing an apparatus and a searching method are provided to effectively satisfy various desires of a user by searching a desired product using a combination selection method. CONSTITUTION: A good information database (1127) stores basic specification information and specification information according to characteristic. When a search request message including searching condition information is received from a client, an information search block(1125) outputs product information by searching a product information database. The searching condition information includes the basic specification information of the product and the specification information according to the characteristic. A searching list creation block(1129) creates a searching list including product breakdown based on the outputted product information. COPYRIGHT KIPO 2012

WO/2017/099364METHOD, DEVICE, AND COMPUTER PROGRAM FOR MANAGING

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

SHOPPING INFORMATION WO -15.06.2017Int.Class 06Q 30/06Appl.No

PCT/KR2016/012586Applicant ODD CONCEPTS INC.Inventor KIM,Jung Tae The present invention relates to a method for integrating and managing online shopping information by an electronic device, comprising the steps of: (a) displaying a shopping information add icon on at least one of a notification list or a shared menu list while displaying an arbitrary page; (b) when a user selects the add icon, extracting a product on the page, indexing a source of the extracted product, and reflecting the product to a first shopping cart for the integrated management of shopping information by using at least one of a log recording of a web browser executing the page, data extracted from the log recording, uploadable data extracted from the page, and a screenshot of the page; (c) when a shopping information search request for the product is received, transmitting a query for the product together with information representing a source data or a corresponding data; and (d) displaying shopping information matching the product.

108399224NETWORK SHOPPING INFORMATION PUSHING METHOD CN -

14.08.2018Int.Class G06F 17/30Appl.No 201810145491.7Applicant ANHUI

QIANYUNDU INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY CO., LTD.Inventor YANG LIANGJUN

The invention discloses a network shopping information pushing method, and relates to the technical field of data processing. The method comprises the following steps of converting obtained data information into a computer language, and transmitting the computer language to an information processing system through a data transmission network; performing extraction analysis on a keyword of information of an online purchased commodity through a structured information extraction module; receiving a search request released by a user client through the internet by the information processing system, and performing matching storage on a search keyword and a user client account; matching the keyword of the online purchased commodity with the search keyword stored in the client account, and if the key word matching fails, performing re-matching; and after the keyword matching is finished, pushing the commodity information to the matched user client through the internet by a server. External data information of the system is obtained through an information collection system; the information obtaining range is wide; and data update and database improvement are facilitated.

1020170067976METHOD, DEVICE AND COMPUTER PROGRAM OF MANAGING SHOPPING INFORMATION KR - 19.06.2017Int.Class G06Q 30/06Appl.No

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

1020150174592Applicant ODD ONCEPTS INC. Inventor KIM, JUNG TAE The present invention relates to a method of consolidating and managing online shopping information by an electronic device, the method comprising the following steps of: (a) displaying a shopping information adding icon onto at least one of a notification list or a shared menu list, in a state in which an arbitrary page is displayed; (b) extracting a product from the page by using at least one among a recording log of a web browser executing the page, a data extracted from the recording log, an uploadable data extracted from the page, and a screen shot of the page, when a user selects the adding icon, indexing a source of the extracted product, and incorporating the product into a first shopping cart for integrated shopping information management; (c) transmitting a query for the product together with the source data or information representing the data, when a shopping information search request for the product is received; and (d) displaying shopping information which matches the product. Users can manage shopping information including shopping carts, purchase history and the like from multiple shopping malls via one application. COPYRIGHT KIPO 2017

6125353 MALL SERVER WITH PRODUCT SEARCH CAPABILITY US 26.09.2000 Int. Class G06F 7/60 Appl. No 08917202 Applicant Fujitsu Limited Inventor Yagasaki Isao A mall server with a product search function, in which each product category has a particular effective period during which it is presented to customers as a selectable search key. In a virtual shopping mall system, customers can conduct a search for a set of products by designating a particular product category as a search key. As part of a mall server, a category master table stores a plurality of product categories accompanied by information on their respective effective periods, and a product master table stores information on various online products along with their respective category definitions. Based on the category master table, a product search screen generation unit produces product search screen data containing a set of categories whose effective periods include the present date. Receiving the product search screen data from the mall server, the customer terminal displays a product search screen including a category selection menu to provide the customer with a list of selectable categories. The customer issues a search request after selecting one category from the list. A product searching unit searches the product master table for the products that fall under the selected category. The customer terminal displays a product list screen upon receipt of the product list screen data from the mall server.

105677810 ONLINE SHOPPING PRODUCT SEARCHING SYSTEM BASED ON

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

KEYWORD ANALYSIS CN-15.06.2016Int.Class G06F 17/30Appl.No 201511032977.2ApplicantTIANJIN HENGGOU TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENT CO., LTD.Inventor CHEN BINGFUThe invention provides an online shopping product searching system based on keyword analysis. According to the system, after a search data request of an onlineshopping customer is received, a dynamic database containing multi-dimensional keywords such as a commodity brand and name, accessory names, commodity attribute information description and search hot spots is inquired according to an algorithm, and commodity informationbetter meeting the actual search requirements of the customer is obtained by adopting a mode of combining word segmentation hot degree grading, user input habit judging and browsing habit judging. The online shopping product searching system based on keyword analysis can improve the search efficiency of the customer, meet the customer requirements and increase purchasing conversion rate of the customer.

108171584VIRTUAL REALITY-BASED INTELLIGENT SUPERMARKET SHOPPING SYSTEM CN - 5.06.2018Int.Class G06Q 30/06Appl.No 201810050065.5Applicant WU JINGInventor WU ING The invention discloses a virtual reality-based intelligent supermarket shopping system. The system comprises a server, a user terminal, a supermarket terminal and a virtual reality device, wherein the virtual reality device comprises a microphone, a loudspeaker and a camera; the server comprises a wireless module, a user registration module, a registration storage module, a request search module, a shopping analysis module, a supermarket search module, a supermarket modeling module, a modeling transmission module, a virtual reality module, a voice interaction module, a shopping processing module, a collision prompting module, an electronic contract module, an online payment platform and a fee display module; the supermarket modeling module comprises a scene modeling module, a commodity modeling module, a shopping trolley module and a guide modeling module; the voice interaction module comprises a voice obtaining module, a voice recognition module and a voice transmission module; the shopping processing module comprises a shopping confirmation module, a receipt sending module and a delivery reservation module; and the virtual reality module comprises an environment shooting module, an environment analysis module and a virtual planning module.

Groupings of alternative elements or embodiments of the invention disclosed herein are not to be construed as limitations. Each group member can be referred to and claimed individually or in any combination with other members of the group or other elements found

herein. One or more members of a group can be included in, or deleted from, a group for reasons of convenience and/or patentability. When any such inclusion or deletion occurs, the specification is herein deemed to contain the group as modified, thus fulfilling the written description of all Markus groups used in the appended claims.

As used in the description herein and throughout the claims that follow, the meaning of “a,” “an,” and “the” includes plural reference unless the context clearly dictates otherwise. Also, as used in the description herein, the meaning of “in” includes “in” and “on” unless the context clearly dictates otherwise.

The recitation of ranges of values herein is merely intended to serve as a shorthand method of referring individually to each separate value falling within the range. Unless otherwise indicated herein, each individual value is incorporated into the specification as if it were individually recited herein. All methods described herein can be performed in any suitable order unless otherwise indicated herein or otherwise clearly contradicted by context.

The use of any and all examples, or exemplary language (e.g. “Such as”) provided with respect to certain embodiments herein is intended merely to better illuminate the invention and does not pose a limitation on the scope of the invention otherwise claimed. No language in the specification should be construed as indicating any non-claimed element essential to the practice of the invention.

The above information disclosed in this Background section is only for the enhancement of understanding of the background of the invention and therefore it may contain information that does not form the prior art that is already known in this country to a person of ordinary skill in the art.

OBJECTIVE OF THE INVENTION

The principal objective of the present invention is to provide a Computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests.

SUMMARY

Before the present systems and methods, are described, it is to be understood that this application is not limited to the particular systems, and methodologies described, as there can be multiple possible embodiments which are not expressly illustrated in the present disclosure. It is also to be understood that the terminology used in the description is for the purpose of describing the particular versions or embodiments only and is not intended to limit the scope of the present application.

The present invention mainly cures and solves the technical problems existing in the prior art. In response to these problems, the present invention discloses a computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests.

As one aspect of the present invention is to present “A computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests, wherein a computer implemented method is processed by at least one processor, wherein the computer implemented method allows the retailers through an online portal to provide response according to search requests associated with the user, wherein the method comprising steps of: Allowing online customers to request and receive product selected on products or services prospects electronically on an online portal, the online portal comprising: a products or services database system which maintains at least one products or services database containing prospect products or services data; a receiving system for receiving products or services user generated search requests from online customers, each product or services user generated search request containing at least one search criteria upon which a products or services report is desired by the online customer; a query system which upon receipt of a products or services user generated search request from the receiving system will perform a products or services search of the products or services database using the search criteria contained in the products or services user generated search request; A reporting system which generates and sends product selected to online customers based on the results of products or services searches received from the query system, each the products or services report corresponding to a products or services user generated search request; and Generating according to the search requests of the user according to a response generating module..”

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF DRAWINGS

To clarify various aspects of some example embodiments of the present invention, a more particular description of the invention will be rendered by reference to specific embodiments thereof which are illustrated in the appended drawings. It is appreciated that these drawings depict only illustrated embodiments of the invention and are therefore not to be considered limiting of its scope. The invention will be described and explained with additional specificity and detail through the use of the accompanying drawings.

In order that the advantages of the present invention will be easily understood, a detailed description of the invention is discussed below in conjunction with the appended drawings, which, however, should not be considered to limit the scope of the invention to the accompanying drawings, in which:

Figure 1 shows detail flow diagram representation of Computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests.

DETAIL DESCRIPTION

The present invention is related to Computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests.

Figure 1 shows detail block diagram representation of Computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests.

Although the present disclosure has been described with the purpose of Computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests, it should be appreciated that the same has been done merely to illustrate the invention in an exemplary manner and to highlight any other purpose or function for which explained structures or configurations could be used and is covered within the scope of the present disclosure.

The computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests is disclosed.

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

The computer implemented method is processed by at least one processor.

The computer implemented method allows the retailers through an online portal to provide response according to search requests associated with the user.

The method comprising steps of allowing online customers to request and receive product selected on products or services prospects electronically on an online portal.

The online portal comprising a products or services database, a receiving system, a query system, a reporting system and a response generating module.

A products or services database system maintains at least one products or services database containing prospect products or services data.

A receiving system is used for receiving products or services user generated search requests from online customers.

Each product or services user generated search request containing at least one search criteria upon which a products or services report is desired by the online customer.

A query system which upon receipt of a products or services user generated search request from the receiving system will perform a products or services search of the products or services database using the search criteria contained in the products or services user generated search request.

A reporting system which generates and sends product selected to online customers based on the results of products or services searches received from the query system.

Each the products or services report corresponding to a products or services is generated according to user generated search request.

The response generating module generated the search requests of the user according.

The computer implemented method is used in ecommerce based web portal.

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

The processing unit comprises a memory storage to store the history of the search request of the user according to the profile of the user.

The central processing unit used to process the information according to the location of the user and current trends of the particular user.

The response generating module improves the response on the feedback of the user, provided on by the user on generating the response by the response generating module.

The response generating module identity of the user generated search request form and at least one of a location and a movement of the user within the at least one search field relative to the user generated search request form.

The figures and the foregoing description give examples of embodiments. Those skilled in the art will appreciate that one or more of the described elements may well be combined into a single functional element. Alternatively, certain elements may be split into multiple functional elements. Elements from one embodiment may be added to another embodiment. For example, order of processes described herein may be changed and are not limited to the manner described herein. Moreover, the actions of any block diagram need not be implemented in the order shown; nor do all of the acts need to be necessarily performed. Also, those acts that are not dependent on other acts may be performed in parallel with the other acts. The scope of embodiments is by no means limited by these specific examples.

Although implementations of the invention have been described in a language specific to structural features and/or methods, it is to be understood that the appended claims are not necessarily limited to the specific features or methods described. Rather, the specific features and methods are disclosed as examples of implementations of the invention.

CLAIMS

We claim:

1. A computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests, wherein computer implemented method is processed by at least one processor, wherein the computer implemented method allows the retailers through an online portal to provide response according to search requests associated with the user, wherein the method comprising steps of:

Allowing online customers to request and receive product selected on products or services prospects electronically on an online portal, the online portal comprising:

a products or services database system which maintains at least one products or services database containing prospect products or services data;

a receiving system for receiving products or services user generated search requests from online customers, each product or services user generated search request containing at least one search criteria upon which a products or services report is desired by the online customer;

a query system which upon receipt of a products or services user generated search request from the receiving system will perform a products or services search of the products or services database using the search criteria contained in the products or services user generated search request;

A reporting system which generates and sends product selected to online customers based on the results of products or services searches received from the query system, each the products or services report corresponding to a products or services user generated search request; and
Generating according to the search requests of the user according to a response generating module.

2. The computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests as claimed in claim 1, wherein the computer implemented method is used in ecommerce based web portal.

3. The computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests as claimed in claim 1, wherein the processing unit comprises a memory storage to store the history of the search request of the

user according to the profile of the user.

4. The computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests as claimed in claim 1, the central processing unit used to process the information according to the location of the user and current trends of the particular user.

5. The computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests as claimed in claim 1, the response generating module improves the response on the feedback of the user, provided on by the user on generating the response by the response generating module.

6. The computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests as claimed in claim 1, the response generating module identity of the user generated search request form and at least one of a location and a movement of the user within the at least one search field relative to the user generated search request form.

**COMPUTER IMPLEMENTED METHOD FOR SPECIFIC
RESPONSE AND INTERACTION FROM RETAILERS
ACCORDING TO USER GENERATED SEARCH REQUESTS**

ABSTRACT

The present invention relates to Computer implemented method for specific response and interaction from retailers according to user generated search requests. The objective of the present invention is to solve the problems in the prior art technologies related to online user specific response generation and interaction using user search requests.

DRAWINGS

Applicants: **Abdul Shareef Pallivalappil and Dr. Krishna Prasad K**

Sheet No. 1 of Total 1

FIGURE 1

CONCLUSION

Face recognition technology is currently a hot spot in predicting customer purchase pattern in any business. Facial emotion recognition is a major concern in the fields of computer vision and Artificial Intelligence owing to its significant academic and commercial potential. Hence, quantification of consumer interest is an interesting, innovative, and promising trend in marketing research. For example, an approach for a salesperson is to observe consumer behaviour during the shopping phase and then recall his interest. However, the salesperson needs unique skills because every person may interpret their behaviour in a different manner. This research work is carried out in two parts. The first part proposed a method that detects the visual centre of attention by first recognizing human face and then estimating head posture orientation. This work could be useful for identifying things like marketing campaigns and other company efforts that clients could be interested in. Salespeople can also make changes to their marketing materials based on client feedback. The second part introduces body orientation in customer posture estimate. Novel deep learning architecture combines this with local pair-wise joint connection. It also use the visibility mask to model both inter and self-occlusion. Body orientation is also linked to the visibility mask and local joint connections, global body orientation, customer mobility, and occluding objects are all taken into account in this approach.

The suggested system is made up of three CNN structures in a cascade. The first CNN's task is to estimate head posture. Face segmentation was taught to the second CNN structure. The third CNN was programmed to recognize and classify facial expressions. The last two steps allow for guided picture grouping and the integration of part-based and holistic data. On the RaFD dataset, testing test results showed 99.43 percent precision posture prediction and 93.20 percent accuracy for face appearance detection. The average accuracy of positive and negative emotions is 93.99.

The proposed approach can aid in the measurement of relevant marketing and product likability as well as the quantification of the client interest. It can also be used to identify sales-boosting company initiatives. According to customer feedback, marketing efforts can alter their methods. Future direction includes the temporal analysis of the data and the optimization space used in the architecture. Track human faces and use object localization so that the system can watch and index an individual's facial expressions over time. Exploring the proposed

Real Time Customer Satisfaction Analysis using Facial Expressions, Headpose Estimation and Body Orientation

architecture with people of different regions and cultural background and testing it on various other domains

The purpose of this research is to track client interest based on head pose positioning and facial expression recognition. We have developed a quantifiable system for measuring customer interest. This system recognizes the important facial expression and then processes current client photos and does not save them for later processing. This work described a deep learning-based system for observing customer actions, focusing on interest identification. The suggested approach determines client attention by estimating head posture. The system monitors facial expressions and reports customer interest. The proposed method identified frontal face postures, and then segments facial mechanisms that are critical for facial expression identification and creating an iconized face image. Finally, the obtained values of the resulting image are merged with the original one to analyze facial emotions.

In the second part of this work, for customer pose estimation, a novel architecture using the concepts of deep learning is proposed. Furthermore, the occluding object detection clearly provides inter-occlusion by object cues. As a result, local joint connections, the global body orientation, occluding object, and human motion to address the occlusion problems and the left-right similarity, the proposed network combines the visibility mask and the body orientation. Information is all taken into account as part of a single deep neural network architecture. In future work, we intend to address customer pose estimates in numerous consumers' inter-occlusion. Further optimizations can be done to improve the effectiveness of the system. The robustness of the systems needs to be explored with data from various regions. The impact of the VPCK on customer satisfaction in different shopping sectors needs to be explored.